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Dr. H. H. A. Karunarathna

**Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences
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Editorial Note

This is the second volume of Nagananda International Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences. The first Volume has been issued for the period from January to June 2021.

The research articles written by young scholars as well as eminent scholars in our country under various disciplines can be found in this Volume too.

I would express my heartfelt gratitude to all the scholars who have contributed to the success of this volume providing the article of great value and reviewing them.

Moreover, I would extend my honorable gratitude to Ven. Bodagama Chandima Thera, the Vice Chancellor and Ven. Professor Induragare Dhammarathana Thera, Acting Dean of the Faculty of Humanities and Social Sciences, guided this valuable academic endeavor towards success.

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Pre historic Life in the Jaffna Peninsula - A Preliminary Investigations for the study of Stone Age culture based on Archaeological Evidences.

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Abstract:

The investigation undertaken here on prehistoric life in the Jaffna Peninsula is a preliminary study of the stone age culture based on archaeological evidences. Having considered the remarkable collection of stone implements from the Jaffna Peninsula, it is expected to stratify the cultural successions before the historical records came to use in the Peninsula. Most of the excavation missions so far have been deployed in this region which focused light on the Megalithic cultural layers and material culture of the period. But for the first time an excavation mission was targeted by the Department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka with finding of prehistoric layer deposits and prehistoric remains at Kantarodai and Mayakkai in 2011 and 2020 respectively in the Peninsula. The concept of prehistoric settlements in the Jaffna Peninsula had been developed from the research findings of this author who has been working since more than 30 years in collecting of material like stone tools in many variety which had been used by the mankind lived in this Peninsula before the written records come to the usage. This investigation has been categorized into the three main divisions based on the material we received in relation to the prehistoric life adopted in this land. Having conducted explorations, surface collections and unexpected discoveries of artifacts from the archaeological sites like Mayakkai Cave site in Point Pedro District and the Lower Valley of Thondamanaru salt water basin site have yielded much stone implements from time to time. The most important discovery was held that the 31st Layer of the 2nd Trench Pit at Kantarodai (excavation held in 2011) which exposes the prehistoric sediments. Thus, the morphology of the stone tools found so far from the Peninsula stimulate us to develop a room for research space for prehistoric life existed in this peninsular region. Though the time span of the prehistoric culture is much wider, our material collections are very narrow for this particular period of research as the title indicates the aim and scope of the investigation is a preliminary studies. Our proposed hypotheses have enhanced to highlight the prehistoric cultural strata with the life style of the people who lived before the historic ages. Therefore, this is not an entity of un-witnessed mission or concepts but the collection of accumulated man made implements from the surface basins of Thondamanaru and Valukiyaru have testified our hypotheses that 'The prehistoric settlement was formed from the sand dune area which was located in Vadamaradchi- East, as the northern edge of the expansion of Iranaimadu Culture ends. B.) Deviation of Neolithic Life and Microlithic culture intermingled in the Lower part of Thondamanaru Salt basin and C.) Prehistoric Cultural epicenter was formed at Mayakkai in Vadamaradchi as socio- economic influences received from Iranaimadu Basin at the time. However, to make very clear cut phenomena of the prehistoric cultural phases from Palaeolithic, Microlithic and Neolithic cultural strata in the Jaffna Peninsula we need to have stratigraphic evidences which will be available when excavations taking place. However, in this introductory research a preliminary examination has been done in order to verifying the collected stone tools of the cultures.

Keywords: *Prehistory, Cultural Epicentre, Iranaimadu Culture, Stratigraphy, Trench. Morphology, Cultural Successions.*

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Introduction

An attempt has been made here to expose the hoary antiquity of beginning of human life in the Jaffna Peninsula with archaeological materials which were collected from time to time from the surface of the Jaffna Peninsula. Since the last 30 years of an intensive archaeological explorations and collections of human artefacts and archaeological remains from the Peninsular Jaffna, resulted with the remarkable evidences which facilitated to switch on the prehistoric research in the Northern Sri Lanka. Moreover, a foreign research team from Australia has arrived in 2019 and incorporated in the excavation mission with the department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka and due to this mission of excavations there are very fruitful results in searching of the beginning of prehistoric life in the Northern Sri Lanka. Professor Hiscock has led for the team from Sydney University and encamped in Jaffna in 2019 and carried out the preliminary excavations at Kantarodai and Mayakkai. Already the test-pits excavations conducted by the Department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka at Kantarodai under the leadership of Dr. Nimal Perera in 2011 was resulted with the finding of cultural layers even beyond the Megalithic culture at Kantarodai. A gravel layer with tinny –boney remains have been identified at the 31st layer in 30 meters depth where the particular layer was succeeded the Megalithic cultural layers. At the cave site at Mayakkai in Vadamaradchi the test-pit excavation was carried out by the Australian team in 2019 and no any remarkable findings from the test pit in the cave were exposed within the 03 meters depth and then the excavation mission was suspended for the time being in order to accelerate the excavation works at Kantarodai where the excavation works took place simultaneously with Mayakkai. However, it was able to confirmed that the cave and its surrounding areas were once had been occupied by the stone-age man and his kith & kin and therefore consequently the succession of pre-historic cultural traits prolonged up to proto- historic age in the Vadamaradchi Region. The collected materials from Mayakkai area are indicating the cultural developments taken place at the site were lasted until the late-Medieval times. Thus, at present, the collected Stone (Age) tools like hand-axes from this cave site have conformed and explicated that Mayakkai as a stone age habitation site and the reason why it has been declared as Mayakkai is one of the oldest Lower Palaeolithic sites in South and South-East Asian countries by the authoritative scholars of both Sri Lanka and Australia.

Map 1: Location of Iranaimadu in Vanni Region and the Paleolithic cave site at Mayakkai in Point Pedro *District* Point Pedro

Some Issues: Stone Age Culture in Sri Lanka & South India

Tamil Nadu and Kerala's commercial and cultural ties with the Northern Sri Lanka have played very important role to evolve the base of cultural layers and resulted as receiving and amalgamating the culture from South India rather than the Southern Sri Lanka. As a region of cultural buffer in between Southern Sri Lanka and Southern India, the Northern Sri Lanka (including the Islands of the Jaffna Peninsula) have paved the cultural foundation and construct the superstructure throughout the years of its history. Therefore, the interchanging of the material culture in the Northern region begun from the early periods, and the peninsular Jaffna had played as a bridge between South India and Sri Lanka. But we do not know much of the prehistoric interlinks between South East Asia and Sri Lanka. Now due to the recent archaeological findings it is believed that the migration had taken place from South India to Sri Lanka during the Palaeolithic period onwards and the cultural exchanges were very active from the Sub-Continent to Sri Lanka. But the Eastern sea shore of Sri Lanka was often influenced from Malaysian Archipelago during the historical periods as literatures and the monuments of that region have been testifying. On that way scholars do believe that the origin and development of Iranaimadu Culture were boosted from the South East Asian countries otherwise Atirampakkam of Kotalaiyaru basin from South India. Thus the stone tool makers who were influenced by Indo-Asian countries penetrated to Iranaimadu Region and then might have penetrated into the region of Vadamarachi-East where the Stone Age settlers found the Rock-shelter at Mayakkai gravel area. It is with this intention in this brief research, we are attempting to trace the history of antiquity of man in Jaffna as it was confirmed with the Acheulean type Hand-Axe found at this cave where the stone implement was used by the Homo-erectus man. Thus, considering the prehistoric environments of the region in Vadamaradchi had launched the first settlement of human beings in Jaffna, i.e. Homo erectus and the first man-made shelter was at Mayakkai cave around 600000 BP. For the datum line for living Homo-erectus man we should have a look at the distribution of the same cultures in the neighborhood i.e. in South India as Dr V.Selvakumar gives a potential brief records on the Stone Age material Culture of South India recently in his research work which as follows (Selvakumar, 2010:17-27).

“...Now scholars generally agree that the Acheulian culture emerged in India due to the migration of the Homo erectus species from Africa. In India, the Lower Paleolithic phase is dated to about 700000 years to 20000 years BP. The Achulian tradition also continues into the Middle Paleolithic period. Lower Paleolithic sites are found in several parts of India... Aitirampakkam is one of the earliest Palaeolithic sites in to be discovered in India. Several scholars have studied this site from early 19th century onwards. Shanti Pappu and her team excavated this site recently. These excavations have revealed very important evidence for early human occupations. Achulian living floor and animal foot prints and animal fossil bones have been excavated at this site. Palaeomagnetic measurements suggest an age within the Bruhes-Matuyama chronology of 730000 years BP.”

There is no doubt that in the Southern tip of South Indian progress on Prehistoric Archaeology now have reached to a remarkable achievement. There are many sites have been plotted for the existence of Palaeolithic culture in South India and even in the regions located to the South of Madurai for this settlement in Tamil Nadu are very important in our research view point.

K. Indrapala in his recent research publication gives a summary of pre and proto historical developments in both, South India and Sri Lanka under the caption of ‘Peopling of the Region–The common Gene Pool’ (Indrapala, 2005:36).

“Not much can be learned about these early humans other than about their obvious activities of hunting and gathering. The techniques employed by them to make their stone tools were basically very similar to those found in west Asia, Europe and Africa. The majority of the Lower Palaeolithic artefacts were made of quartzite. Some developments began to occur in the Middle Palaeolithic period which was „a time of regional and local diversity both in terms of stone technology and artifact types“. In the Upper Palaeolithic period, the stone industries „represent a marked and fairly consistent change in methods of making stone tools” (Indrapala, 2005:38).

Scholars from the universities of Sri Lanka have not much paid the attention on investigations pertaining to the prehistoric archaeology of the Northern part of Sri Lanka for a long period, but they are very rigorously and intentionally working on the Buddhist culture and sometimes the pre-Buddhist and the Megalithic culture in the Central and the Southern Regions of Sri Lanka. The reason was why that the unbalanced political situations prevailed in the North and East with South for a long time is the main fact that prevented their attention of the mission of deployment of Archaeological activities in the North and the East. But now the political situation in the North has completely changed and a new enthusiasm has developed in this particular field of investigations and the members and the officers of the department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka now has turned amicably to consider on the antiquity of the past of this Northern region. Therefore, the situation has now provoked to the researchers from Southern Sri Lanka to make data analysis of the archaeological and inscriptional evidences from the Northern region. Thus, the benefits and results of the investigations of this region definitely promote the inter-cultural relationships not only among the Sri Lankan communities but among the academicians and researchers from South India and interNational countries. The recent discussions made on the prehistoric findings of artifacts in Jaffna with V. Selvakumar and S.Rajan of Tanjore and Pondichery universities respectively were resulted with mutual exchanges of ideas which enhance to establish the prehistoric culture in this region. Therefore, to investigate on the stone age material culture in the Jaffna peninsula, we should have a look at the distribution of the same cultures in the neighborhood i.e. in South India.

Archaeologists of South India and Sri Lanka have defined on the distribution of Palaeolithic culture in South Asia situated along with the gravel deposits which contain the gravel layer along the coast of the semi-arid zones belonging to the quaternary period

is one of the most important locations that yields prehistoric evidence. On the basis of this theory they have tried to advocate that there will be no Palaeolithic life pattern and Palaeolithic phase to the south of Madurai in South India. This objectified statement is meant for the inclusion of Sri Lanka too and in Sri Lanka there are no any possibilities to find anything in regards to stratum of Paleolithic cultural life. K. Indrapala has decisively believing the same theory regarding the Paleolithic culture in Sri Lanka. However, in the current status of progress of the investigation in finding the stone tools of Acheulean type (of the Lower Palaeolithic Culture) has provoked us not only to change the time limit on the existence of Palaeolithic culture in Sri Lanka in particular but also this new finding motivate the Archaeologists to avail new interpretations of prehistoric culture in the Jaffna Peninsula and to find new dating line for Palaeolithic strata with South Asian context.

A simple summary of the evidence relating to the Palaeolithic period as given by F.R Allchin who has studied the prehistory of South Asia almost throughout the second half of the twentieth century. F. R. Allchin's statement runs which as follow: "...the Palaeolithic industries of the Pleistocene can be divided into three major groups, on the basis of the shape, size and method of manufacture of the principal artefact types. The Lower Palaeolithic is characterized by hand axes, cleavers, chopping tools, and related artefact forms. Middle Palaeolithic industries are characterized by smaller, lighter tools based upon flacks struck from cores, which in some cases are carefully shaped and prepared in advance; the Upper Palaeolithic by yet lighter artefacts and parallel-sided blades and burins" (Allchin & Allchin 1982:33).

However, a concept on prehistoric life in the Jaffna Peninsula has been developed on an archaeological basis one decade back by P. Ragupathy and that the view is now under the review because of the earliest cultural layers in the Peninsula preceded to Megalithic strata at Kantarodai (2011), Kalabhumi and Thus the opinion that the early settlements in the Jaffna Peninsula by the Megalithic settlers are now has been replaced as weaken up and a new theory has been forwarded with recent discoveries. The first huts in the Jaffna peninsula appeared not from Karainagar (Kalabhumi) but from Mayakkai and then from Thondamanaru salt river basin (Achuvely to Kopay). Further, the recent exploration works conducted by the author in the Myliddy harbor and its hinterland area which revealed the Microlithic tools along with the Megalithic artefacts. Thus, by keeping concerned on the morphology of the stone tools found so far in the Jaffna peninsula in particular, we able to confirm that the Palaeolithic man was living here in the first phase and in the third phase, Microlithic people have been identified in three main sites such as the major sites in the Peninsula like Karainagar-Kalabhumi, Kantarodai and Myliddy Harbour. Then in the fourth phase, Megalithic settlements came into the social formation in the Jaffna Peninsula. Megalithic settlements in the third century B.C. onwards were embraced the Buddhist culture in its inception in the Jaffna Peninsula. Of the three major Microlithic sites in the Peninsula, Karainagar-Kalabhumi is indicating the intermingled cultural developments of Microlithic culture with Megalithic culture likewise Mayakkai and Myliddy cultures are also had cultural fusion with Megalithic culture. These both

prehistoric sites in the Jaffna Peninsula are receiving very keen attention of the scholars now as the Iranaimadu culture gave the route of developments of prehistoric settlers in the Jaffna Peninsula. Therefore, a feasibility of environment of existing Microlithic culture is indicating and enhancing to develop the prehistoric life system prevailed prior to the Megalithic culture in the Jaffna Peninsula. In this way prior to the Microlithic culture in the Peninsula the Palaeolithic culture existed here as the Mayakkai Cave site was identified as Palaeolithic stone age settlements area.

Iranaimadu Basin and Iranaimadu Culture

It is felt to spell out briefly on the Iranaimadu Culture which enhanced our hypothesis of this research because of our discovery of Achuelian Hand Axe from Vadamaradchi has intimately related with the kind of hand-axe unearthed from Iranaimadu Basin. Of course, Iranaimadu is nowadays well known to archaeologists as it is located in Kilinochchi district but its cultural influences from the dawn of life of man kinds in this Island Nation mat not be known to all. The researchers and the students of prehistory of Sri Lanka have no any way to unknown from Iranaimadu Culture. The term ‘*Iranaimadu Formation*’ is often used by the prehistoric archaeologists in Sri Lanka and S. Deraniyagala, the champion of prehistoric wellversed archaeologist of Sri Lanka, is the scholar who using this terminology often on his monumental works, *The Prehistory of Sri Lanka Vol. I & II*. According to him this Iranaimadu *Formation* is running towards south up to Mankulam and towards west up to Murungan in Mannar Di strict. When Deraniyagala define the prehistoric man’s habitation site in Sri Lanka, he divides into three categories of deposits in which archaeological remains were unearthed such as 1). The Ratnapura river Basin deposits of the lowland wet Zone, 2). The coastal alluvial deposits and sand dunes of the Iranaimadu Formation in the semi-arid Zone and 3). The Rock shelters and open air sites of the lowland wet Zone. ‘Out of these the second category, the gravel layer along the coast of the semi-arid zones belonging to the Quaternary period is one of the most important locations that yields prehistoric evidence. Due to erosion these deposits have turned from a dark red to a reddish brown. This deposit which is spread in a large area was first identified by E.J. Weyland as *plato deposit* and latter known as the *Iranaimadu Formation IFm*’. Further, S.Deraniyagala has stressing a view that on the Lower Palaeolithic strata in Sri Lanka was not clearly well documented so far but many stone implements have been collected stand for the period of Lower Palaeolithic culture in Sri Lanka. The following note of his view is very important to us at present (Deraniyagala, 1992:82).

The Lower Palaeolithic has not been reliably documented in Sri Lanka. The alluvial (gem bearing gravels of the Ratnapura district referred to as the Ratnapura beds, have yielded manmade chopping and cutting tools (Ratnapura Industry), in association with a fossil fauna (Ratnapura fauna), which could tentatively be assigned to the Palaeolithic. Tools found associated with high level coastal deposits in the North and South-East of the island (Irannaimadu Formation) and recent finding from Jaffna can also be assigned tentatively to the Lower Paleolithic and pending scientific dating of these occurrences.

In these background though the Iranaimadu Culture is termed by the British prehistoric archaeologists to denote the *three stages of Stone Age strata* such as the Palaeolithic, Microlithic and Megalithic cultural arena, to compare and contrast the Acheulean type of Hand Axe found from the Mayakkai Cave shelter Iranamadu stone implements are very important from our point of view. Thus, having considered the hand-axe implement found from Mayakkai Cave would have been a course way to open of the demised Hand–Axe culture in Vadamaradchi and disclose the way of relations with the Iranaimadu culture.

Mayakkai: It's Location in Vadamaradchi.

Now we are able to discuss and analysis on the phase of Stone Age Culture of the Jaffna Peninsula for the first time. Scholars may ask a question now that how far is it reliable to determine ‘a stone age’ of the Peninsular Jaffna before confirming the Palaeolithic culture or Neolithic culture in Sri Lanka. But the fact that the recent archaeological research in the Jaffna Peninsula has resulted with material evidences of stone age cultural strata from the site, Kantarodai in the Jaffna Peninsula. Now we have good enough space in archaeology with definite material remains of Stone Age phase from the Jaffna Peninsula in relation to the culture of cave dwellers from Vadamaradchi area. In 1983 and thereafter we were able to collect stone tools like hand axes from Mayakkai Cave, located near to Thampaciddy in Point Pedro. In 2011 a team from the Department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka had visited to this cave site and Dr. Siran Deraniyagala also was one among them. At the cave site itself after the careful explorations and the examination of the collected kit of stone tools, Dr. Siran Deraniyagala has declared that the cave was once occupied by the *Homo erectus* man who lived at this cave site probably 600000 years BP. However, it was realized that until we have evidences like skeletons, food fossils and any associated remains with stratigraphic evidences for the conformation of the site and the date of the cave dweller at Mayakkai. Thus, this situation paved the new development in the Jaffna Peninsula to facilitate firmly to the researchers on the prehistoric investigations combined work with the Archaeologists from Sydney University of Australia. So that there is a new cultural phase of Stone Age brought up methodically to the research horizon in the field of archaeology of the Jaffna Peninsula. Few scholars have been refuting of the Hand Axe discovered at Mayakkai in the Jaffna Peninsula. They are by stating by that as to the dawn south of Madurai there are no any evidence for Palaeolithic culture existed and so far no solid evidences had been recovered from the layer of Palaeolithic culture. So, then how far is it possible to have evidences for Palaeolithic culture in the Jaffna Peninsula?

These are the few negative interpretations of scholars at present day. But in Archaeology everything will change in due course of time. However, the reports of British archaeological missions which held in the Iranamadu basin in the latter part of 19th century give the detail of presents of Palaeolithic stone Age culture and the date along with Microlithic culture and the Megalithic sediments. Due to this the culture had been framed as ‘Iranaimadu Culture’ which seems to be extended towards North up to

Vadamaradchi-East as it was extended in the main land up to Mankulam in the south and up to Mannar in the west. So far there is anyone did not switch on to study the expansion of Iranaimadu Culture towards the Northern frontier, i.e. into Vadamaradchi-East. Due to the absence of pre-historians in the North and East the investigation related to the many aspects in cultural history have been left behind.

Discussion

This portion is of the result of the rigorous research and consultations with Deraniyagala, an eminent prehistoric archaeologist of Sri Lanka, regarding the collections of stone implements from a cave site, namely, Mayakkai, located in Puloly-Thambacetty, in Point Petro region in Vadamaradchi (Plate nos. 23,45,295 & 296). It was wonder for that in Jaffna when a team from the Department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka collaterally confirmed with very confidence that the stone implements collected from inside and outside of the cave of Mayakkai were belonging for a period of Lower Palaeolithic Stone Age culture. After the 30 years of civil war which came to an end on the month of July, 2009, the excavation programs in the Northern part of Sri Lanka also has been initiated by the Department of Archaeology and there are the two very important sites such as Kantarodai and the Jaffna Dutch-Fort. When the joint team (the University's staff and students together with the staff and the workers of Archaeology epartment of Colombo) was working at Kantarodai in 2011, I have placed the all collected stone implements from Mayakkai, in front of them. At the day of the visit to the habitation site at Mayakkai, Dr. Deraniyagala, Dr. Nimal Perera and other experts of excavation team were present and they confirmed unanimously that these stone implements are belong to a period of 600000 years, during which the Lower Palaeolithic stone age man, *Homo erecters* lived. The discovery of stone implements held by me in 1983, during which the civil war was taking place in the Northern part of Sri Lanka. Even though, during the civil war times, the academic activities of the University of Jaffna were running with very strength and stability. At that time most of the archaeological discoveries in the Northern part of Sri Lanka had been made and excavation and exploration works were carried out by the Department of History and Archaeology of the University of Jaffna within the Peninsula as well as in the Vanni area.

Fig.01. Acheulean Type unifacial Hand Axe (white Granite)) Hand Axe-(Chert material) spear Head (Lime stone?)

The site, *MAYAKKAI* was first identified by me in 1979 when an archaeological exploration work carried out in order to write a dissertation for the Final Year examination. ‘The main Archaeological Sites in the Jaffna Peninsula was the title of the dissertation which was guided by K. Indrapala even after the completion of that dissertation, few archaeological remains like roof tiles, iron slag, an Islamic or Arabic coin and earthen wares which were recovered from Mayakkai were included in the dissertation in the year 1979 as archaeological findings from an ancient site in Vadamarachchi. But, in 1983 after the completion of Masters of Arts degree from the University of Mysore, India, I returned to Jaffna. At that time I was able to recognize the site as Stone Age culture (Old Palaeolithic) on the basis of recovered stone implements from the site.

However, K. Indrapala and S.K. Sitrapalam both of them had hesitated and neglected to ensure the site for stone age culture and as the prehistoric environments and had refused to conduct further research or explorations at this cave site. That the reason was why the whole investigation on stone age culture in the Jaffna peninsula was totally given up by us and then after more than a three decades of time span, the time has come again unexpectedly to confirm that those implements are, as real, Palaeolithic stone tools by the experts of the department of Archaeology of Sri Lanka in 201 while an excavation mission was taking place at Kantarodai. This conformation, provided by them as Palaeolithic stone implements, which gave us an opportunity to chance the views on the history of Sri Lanka in general and the history of Jaffna in particular. This new tendency has put forward a new phenomenon on the beginning of Sri Lankan prehistory from the Northern Sri Lanka. S. Deraniyagala has firmly confirmed that these were being the tools of the Palaeolithic cultural site and he further visited directly with the team of the Department of Archaeology to the particular site and have collected ecological conditions of the area especially the distance between the caves dwelling site

Fig.02. Mayakkai. The middle one is Myliddy Harbour.

Some issues on the Third phase: Microlithic culture in Sri Lanka and South India.

The Palaeolithic industries lasted for a very long time and about ten thousand years BP we see the beginning of new stone industries in Northern Peninsular India. This particular period of culture is generally mentioned as Mesolithic period. Mesolithic and other stone industries of the Holocene period represent a further development of the stone

tools industries, particularly in microliths. By this time, there were settled communities of hunters, fishers, gatherers and pastoralists co-existed with settled communities up to the beginning of the Iron Age (about 1000 BC) and in some places even later. Mesolithic culture had its widest impact on the people of South India and Sri Lanka almost simultaneously but the life of the same in Sri Lanka had evolved densely rather prior to the South India because of the South–East –Asian influence of prehistoric culture reached first to this island. Even though, the Jaffna Peninsula had not consists of material culture relating to Mesolithic period, but the recent archaeological investigations here have done indicating that the life during the Mesolithic period had flourished even before the Megalithic cultural layers formed. There are places like Kantarodai in Valikamam, Chattirantai and Kalapumi in Karainagar have yield small (Micro) stone lithic tools and cultural layers prior to the Megalithic culture. This conducive situation is now with evidences to confirm the existence of Microlithic cultural life within the Jaffna Peninsula (Ragupathy, 1987:129).

Archaeologists from South India are still in paradox in viewing the date of Microlithic culture of Sri Lanka. Sri Lankan archaeologists though they have succeeded in dating of the Microlithic culture in Sri Lanka approximately in 29000 B.C., prior to South Indian complex, they have traced the parallel cultural affinities of life of the period between these both material cultural complex. S. Deraniyagala while demarking the final datum line for the Microlithic culture in Sri Lanka, he states that ‘the dating of the inception of the geometric Microlithic tradition of stone tool manufacture in Sri Lanka at ca. 30000 BP is very much earlier than what has so far been recorded from India. This appears to be the result of inadequate sampling. Excavations at the Teri sites are certain to produce dates for geometric Microliths that are comparable to these from Sri Lanka. Similarly, probes in caves located in the wetter parts of Southern India, as in Kerala, are likely to provide dates akin to those from the Sri Lankan caves’ (Deraniyagala, 2004:20-21).

The Microlithic site from Kerala has received much importance from South Indian archaeologists in recent days and Selvakumar has done more research works on these southern Microlithic sites. He has attributed a new theory on the origin and evolution of Dravidian language groups from these southern Microlithic cultural settlements and further he put forwarded a new concept of the origin and development of two major language groups in Sri Lanka through these extended settlement complexes of the Southern Microlithics through the North Eastern part and the upcountry sites. Moreover, V.Selvakumar has corroborated his evidences from the Southern Microlithic sites like in the Gundur Basin with place names as described in the early literatures, so that the development of a group of language in Southern India (proto Dravidian Languages) evolved and spoken through the extension of *Teri culture* from Kerala to Tamilnadu in dawn South . Further, he dated these cultural sites to 5000 years BP (Selvakumar, 2001:260). But Rita Gardener is dating for this Microlithic culture in South India as 20000 BP (Rita 2010 :13) In contrast to this dating of Microlithic culture of South India , the Microlithic phase in Sri Lanka deviate much time span as had been dated

from skeletal remains from Mesolithic (Balangoda) culture for 29000 B.C. South Indian archaeologists are still viewing that the Microlithic culture of Sri Lanka was inherited from South India. But they did not consider the South East Asian prehistoric links with this island existed prior to South Indian cultural links. Even the research results of Microlithic culture of South India were not in unanimous dating and not even comparable with the Sri Lankan dating. Therefore, it enhances our research theme here by viewing a brief recent interpretational development in Mesolithic culture in the dawn South India and South East Asia. There are still controversial which prevailing among the scholars who have had the uncertainty on the presence of Mesolithic culture between the western and Eastern Ghats in South India. Under these circumstances the Sri Lankan Microlithic has been dated on the datum line such as 30000 years BP (Recently it was discovered as pre-Mesolithic culture which is belonging to before 10000 BP). Thus, Vadamaradchi region has been vividly throw a light to confirm its peculiar inter-groups of cultural life system. The modern people of Vadamaradchi have been denying to get out from that region for marriage life and they never have had bride or bridegroom from out of the region. This behavioral mentality of these people prove that the continuation of a kind of groupies in life system which existed since the prehistoric period.

As new developments had been taken place in the discovery of archaeological remains in Vadamaradchi, we have a preamble to conclude that there are three stages of Stone Age phases stretched could be classified, such as the Paleolithic culture (Lower Palaeolithic or upper Paleolithic), Neolithic culture and Megalithic culture. The Mesolithic phase of life was completely absent in Vadamaradchi area, but in Valikamam–west area there are possibilities for Microlithic culture. The Neolithic cultural life in Vadamaradchi had a hinter land of an area of open space where naturally salt harvesting had held. From Karumanatpiddy to Mandan of Thondaimanaru basin the Neolithic cultural sediments seem to be spreader over in both sides of the Thondamanaru basin. The origin of cotton culture in Vadamaradchi begun from the Neolithic cultural period and weaving as well as winding grass mat also might had flourished side by side near to this period at the Nagarkoil area. The physical and climatic conditions of this area was very conducive for this developments of palaeo-industries like agriculture-based handy-craft, domestication of cattle keeping and the production of cotton. The village Amban had played very important dual role as market centre for the cattle keepers and as center of coin mint for administrators to entire region of Vadamaradchi during the colonial period. Due to this, the economic importance which was prolonged over the periods, the western colonial rulers like the Portuguese and the Dutch had occupied and controlled this market place. The high quantity of the Dutch coinage was minted at the village, AMBAN (in Java Island in South East Asia the Dutch authorities had a settlement place is called Amban where they developed an industrial complex as an economic zone under them) (Plate no. 39). The term Laadam (metal shoe nail for cattle) industry and the iron works for bullock-cart were also well designed at Amban and Kudattanai villages and this tradition is still prevailing. The making iron rim for the wheels of bullock-card is still being continued in these villages and the technology was adopted and used for this works would have been

inherited since the Neolithic cultural activities of this region. This development was not a sudden growth as we seen today at this area but it would have been inherited from the society of ancient passed, i.e. the people who lived at this region during the Neolithic period. The Neolithic culture here was succeeding by the Megalithic culture as we seen in the down South India. The identification and the location of ash mound in Vadamaradchi–East have been the source of material to investigate further in relation to the Neolithic culture in the Jaffna Peninsula. A site naming as Karumanatpitti in Nagar Kovil was an ash mound from where a spouted pot was unearthed. Due to the seasonal shifting of sand dunes here archaeologists are unable to locate the exact site and excavate any ash mound site in this region so far.

Fig.03. Archaeological field visit

As V.Selvakumar remarked, the Mesolithic cultural phase in the down South Indian context which differ on the regional basis as well as periodical basis which caused for the language diffusional development under one material culture (Selvakumar, 2010:25-27). According to him the development of South Indian language group had its embryo from the period of migration of the Microlithic people towards down south including Sri Lanka. But the Sri Lankan periodization for the Mesolithic culture seems to be earlier than the down South Indian one and further the distinctive character of Sri Lankan Microlithic phase is the skeletal remains which we unable to see in down Southern India but in North India skeletal remains were recovered from many regions. The last phase of Microlithic life of the people was intermingled with the Megalithic culture in many places in Sri Lanka except in the Jaffna Peninsula, around 800 B.C. According to Deraniyagala the Nagas Dynasty who terminated the Stone Age culture and initiated historic periods in Sri Lanka (Deraniyagala, 2001:321). As he has suggested, the stone age period ends in Sri Lanka with the rise of Nagas Dynasty simultaneously from the various local points in this island which resemble with South India as we seen at Brahmagiri where the Satavahanas flourished as the first dynasty of the historical period of Deccan from the Megalithic culture. Therefore, we have an assumption that wherever the Buddhism had gripped strongly in Sri Lanka that there the Megalithic culture preceded to the historical period and wherever non Buddhist influence prevailed here where either the Neolithic Culture or the Microlithic culture preceded to the historical period. The Jaffna Peninsula also had these Environments through material culture.

Fig.04. Microlithic Tools from Myliddy Harbour: (1) Milky Crystal Scrapper (2) Flint (Chert material) (3) Flack Tool (Hard Lime stone)

The Kalapumi excavation at Karainagar conducted by Ragupathy in 1981 revealed the Microliths and the Megalithic artifacts of both had intermingled together. But in the Jaffna peninsula, according to the excavation conducted by the government Department of Archaeology in 2011, the Microlithic culture was preceded to the Megalithic culture and the basement of beginning of life at Kantarodai with Microlithic phase (see the Excavation report annexed). The surface collection of material artifacts from the area from Nagar Kovil to Mandan of Karanavai along with Thondaimanaru basin in Vadamaradchi region indicate the intermingled of last phase of Microlithic culture with the Megalithic cultural phase which resulted the course for the sedentary agricultural development and domestication at this region. There were non-Buddhist influences had prevailed at the most places where the Neolithic or Microlithic influences have been found. Thondamanaru basin is the best example for this concept. The material culture of the villages at *Kudatanai* and *Amban in Vadamaradchi -East* are till now indicating the lively goods style that of the amalgamation of those both cultures. A village name „*Mandan*” is naming because of a verity of fish. This kind of fish is being called as silt fish. Many sub-varieties of silt fish have been available for the sustained life of the people who lived along with Thondamanaru basin. From Chundikkulam down to Mandan the material life of the people were interconnected with fishing and harvesting of grain crops like paddy .and millet along with Thondamanaru basin. *Mandan* was a place where naturally salt harvesting is taking place in season. The local people of the area have shown much concern with this natural consuming material which enhances the life of the local people for some time periodically.

Conclusion

The searching of the material culture of Stone Age period in Sri Lanka has very lengthy literature review. The reports and the scholarly works on stone age culture from. Pole to Siran Deraniyagala have comprise various approaches and yardsticks to measure the culture with corroborating archaeological materials. But, there are no any literatures or other evidences to mark the Stone Age cultures of the Jaffna Peninsula. While many pre historians have paid their interest to flash out the cultural activities of the pre historic people of Southern Sri Lanka in a comparative manner, only a single scholar, Nimal Perera, former Deputy Commissioner of Archaeology, has been showing

his earnest interest in bring out the elementary information on the Palaeolithic culture from the Peninsular Jaffna. In the meantime, the discovery of Stone Age settlement and its conformation with the Palaeolithic stone implements at Mayakkai cave in Vadamarachi gave an impact in writing of prehistory of Sri Lanka. Siran Deraniyagala directly visited to this site and studied the surrounding of this cave site and has fixed a time line for this stone age culture tentatively as to be 600000 years and the Homo erectus human being had used the stone implements which found in the cave. According to Siran Deraniyagala's view that it was the way of life in which the Jaffna Peninsula received a big impact either from South East Asia or from South India during the Pleistocene period. Thus, during the way of migration of the team of homo erectus for some time they had stayed at this cave sites and might left to Iranaimadu or other place. Further, besides of the stone implements a side in Mayakkai, there are the YAKSHA and NAGAS' traditions have still prevailed and rooted in the culture of Vadamarachi-East.

According to authorized and confirmed archaeological materials which have been collected recently, it is possible to come to a conclusion that the first inhabitants of Sri Lanka were the Paleolithic and the Neolithic people who lived not only within the caves or open air but they lived in different locations in both periods in Sri Lanka. As the first phase of Sri Lankan prehistory is now confirmed clearly by the *Iranaimadu culture* now it could be at least to say that the prehistory of the Jaffna Peninsula begins with the Mayakkai Paleolithic stone implements in association with Palaeolithic coastal gravels and the possibility of occurring this cultural layer is under the search by an Expedition from the Sydney University as engaged in excavation in the Jaffna Peninsula. In the previous decades many investigations conducted along with South-Eastern costal gravels of Sri Lanka with the cultural identity of *Iranamadu Formation*. As the results of this investigations on the coastal-gravel regions the different conclusions had been reached. From the Lower Palaeolithic up to the Megalithic phase of Iranamadu Cultural Formation (stratum -V, Site no-50_a. provides Black and Red Ware (BRW) comprises with the Carbon date of 2,800 BP.). There were different cultural phases had been shown under the *Iranaimadu Cultural Formation*. But the *Iranamadu Formation* is referred for mostly to indicate the Flack Tool phase (Stratum-II with Ferruginous quartz, the stratum -III with clay loam, and the stratum -IV with basal gravel deposited.) No one had indicated the same culture towards North because already it has been indicated the Microlithic culture was absent in the Peninsular Jaffna. But the result of the excavations were held at Kantarodai in 2011 and 2019 giving the positive evidence to the cultural layers of Prehistoric Basal gravel deposits which underlying to the BRW cultural layers have prevailing to give the feasible condition to determine the stone age in the Jaffna Peninsula. Therefore a new impetus has come to light to investigate on the Stone Age culture with the *Iranamadu Formation* for Palaeolithic cultural pheses in Sri Lanka. However, commendable works have been done recently by Dr Nimal Perera and Dr. S.U.Deraniyagala in unveiling the Palaeolithic and the Neolithic phases of Sri Lanka and thanks to them the efforts for confirming the Palaeolithic phase of settlement at Mayakkai cave in Point Pedro region and for giving a tentative date for the hand axes (as *Homo erectus man used*), which could be made around

600000 years back, as Siran Deraniyagala presumed the chronological boundary for this prehistoric habitation site. In 2004, S.U. Deraniyagala while delivering Second Vesak Commemoration lecture on 'Prehistoric basis for the rise of Civilization in Sri Lanka and South India', he pointed out that a unified research design could conceivably clarify as to why the *Acheulean* techno-tradition of stone tool manufacture did not extend to South of Kaveri river in Tamil Nadu and Sri Lanka. The same concept also had been forwarded by Dr.V.Selvakumar before the year 2004. Even though this problem has already been discussed among few scholars in South India and Sri Lanka (Deraniyagala 2004:20). Deraniyagala is giving much more importance to investigate on *Acheulean Culture* in Sri Lanka after the finding of Hand axe implements from Mayakkai cave and the excavation mission was undertaken by an International Expedition from the Sydney University. Thus, a new phase of prehistoric stage from the Jaffna peninsula is one of the contributions for the Prehistoric cultural horizon of this region. This will be a very important change in the evolutionary cultural history of not only Jaffna peninsula but also the whole of Sri Lanka and for South Asia as well. It is, therefore, possible that humans were present in Sri Lanka from at least as early as one million years ago. There are ancient coastal sands and gravels, referred to as the *Iranamadu Formation*, in the North and Southeast of the Island which could be as old as 250,000 BP or even 700,000 - 500,000 BP.

The investigation on material culture in the Jaffna peninsula for Stone Age period needs a wide spectrum of non-partial approach to get a clear picture of the evolution of its cultural growth. A classification for Stone Age culture could be marginalized with a few stone (age) implements found from the cave site at Mayakkai in the Point Pedro district. As most of us do believe today that of absence of Microlithic cultural layer in the Jaffna peninsula does not mean that the previous Stone Age cultures are totally absent. Even though, we are due to bound with some theories for the reasons for the absence of some layers of prehistoric cultures in the Jaffna peninsula, the recent development of investigations in the extreme South of India confirms the 'those of missing cultural layers'. With the experience we gained through archaeological field works from the Jaffna peninsula, each major region of the peninsula indicates a different (pre)historic background which influenced each region with different characters. If we take the Vadamaradchi region, this area has been mostly influenced not by the Megalithic culture but by the Palaeolithic and Neolithic cultures. In contrast to this the Valikamam region was influenced mostly by the Megalithic culture based on mercantile activities even after the Roman trade ended. As far as Tenmaradchy is concerned the region has played its role for transitional cultural contacts through both the land and the sea routes. The original shape of the prehistoric villages can be seen in Vadamaradchi-East where the Nagas and Yakshas lived as described in the Pali-Buddhist literature of Sri Lanka.

References

- Begley, Vimala. (1967). *Archaeological Exploration in Northern Ceylon*, Expedition, 9 (4) Summer.
- Coningham, Robin and Young, Ruth. (2015). *The Archaeology of South Asia*, Cambridge University Press, U.S.A.
- Darsana, S.B. (1996). *Proto -historic investigations in the upper Palar Basin*, Tamil Nadu (Shodhganga <http://hdl.handle.net/148616>)
- Deraniyagala, P.E.P. (1957). 'Races of the Stone Age and Ferrolithic of Ceylon', JRASCB, Vol. V, pp.1-232.
- Deraniyagala, S.U., (1992). *The Prehistory of Sri Lanka, Part-I, Department of Archaeological Survey*, Government of Sri Lanka.
- Deraniyagala, S.U. (2004). *Pre-historic basis for the rise of Civilization in Sri Lanka and Southern India*, Second Vesak Commemoration Lecture, Chennai, Tamil Nadu.
- Hodder, Ian. (1985). 'Advances in Archaeological Method and Theory', *Postprocessual archaeology*, vol.8(1985), pp.1-26, published by Springer.
- Hodder, Ian. (1986). *Reading the Past*, Cambridge University Press, Cambridge.
- Hodder, Ian, 1986, *Symbolic and Structural Archaeology*, (ed) Pp 26-38, Cambridge University Press.
- Indrapala Karthigesu, (2005). *The Evolution of an Ethnic Identity: The Tamils in Sri Lanka C.300 BCE To 1200 CE*, MV Publication, Sydney
- Kennedy, K.A.R. (1990). 'Palaeodemography of Sri Lanka and Peninsular India: A cross Regional Survey', *Perspectives in Archaeology*: Leelananda Prematilleke Festschrift ed. Sudharsan Seneviratne, Peradeniya.
- Kennedy, K. A. R. (2016). 'To What extent were prehistoric Sri Lankans Isolated from the Indian Mainland? Biotic and Archaeological consideration' *Connection and Complexity*, taylorfrancis.com
- Senake Bandaranayake. (1986). *Urbanization and Royal City*: Recent Research Published by the Dept. of National Museum
- Selvakumar, V. (1997). *Investigations into the Prehistoric and Proto- historic cultures of the upper Gunder Basin Madurai District Tamil Nadu* (Shodhganga <http://hdl.handle.net/10603/149003>)
- Seyone, K. N.V. (1998). *Some old Coins Found in Early Ceylon*, Nawala, Sri Lanka
- Shaks, MK; Tilley, Michael. (1987). *Social Theory and Archaeology*, Polity Press, Oxford.
- Sitrampalam, S.K. (1980), *The Megalithic Culture of Sri Lanka*, Department of Archaeology, Deccan College, Poona (A doctoral thesis which is not published).
- Thiagarajah, Siva. (2011). *Peoples and Cultures of Early Sri Lanka: A study on Genetics and Archaeology*, London.
- Thiagarajah, Siva. (2016). *Kantarodai Civilization of Ancient Jaffna- A Study in Archaeology and other Disciplines*, Kumaran Book House, Colombo.
- Venkatraman, R. (1985). *Indian Archaeology: A survey*, M.K. University, Madurai.
- Visahan, Subramaniam. (2010). *Peopling of Sri Lanka: An Outline- Based on Genetic(DNA) Studies*, London.
- Vijayapala, W.H. (2007). 'Possible Neolithic Evidence in Sri Lanka', *History and Archaeology Of Sri Lanka-Vol.II*, pp97-119, Ed.by Prematilleke, L; Bandaranayake, S; Deraniyagala, S & Silva, R, Ministry of Cultural Affairs, Colombo.

Psychological Analysis of Language in Theravāda Tradition

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Abstract

Buddhism has mainly been propagated throughout the world over two thousand five hundred years by verbal communication. So, it includes a wealth of information regarding the nature of language and its usage which can be considered as a contribution to the existing knowledge of communication in the modern world. Our attention has mainly been focused on the psychological analysis of language with reference to the development of the abhidhammic concept of paññatti, the Theravada conception of expression. The main sources consulted for this study belong to the Pali traditional grammar and some important points mentioned in the early Buddhist sources have been explained in order to elucidate the background of the evolution of the concept of paññatti. Psychological basis of expression, hearing and comprehension has been clarified with reference to the abhidhammic analysis of paññatti in Theravada tradition.

Keywords: *Psychology, Theravada tradition, language, abhidhammic*

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Introduction

The theory of language in Theravada Buddhism has not been adequately dealt with in connection with the concept of *pannatti* in modern researches. Further, the information available in the vast literature of Pali grammar has not been taken into consideration in the modern research works related to Buddhist philosophy. Therefore, this article introduces a new research area for the future studies in the field of Buddhist communication.

Result and Discussion

Communication occupies an important position in the modern world. It has contributed much for the well-being of people all over the world. But it should be mentioned that it also has influenced. The origin of a number of problems in the context of modern society. So, we think that the theory of modern communication should be revived in the context of the ancient knowledge and experience of verbal communication in order to make it more profitable to the modern society. The insights revealed in this article regarding the psychological basis of verbal communication will make a positive contribution towards the revival of the modern understanding of the theory of communication.

Paññatti : Grammatical Analysis

Buddha's teachings have been recorded in several languages and *Pāli* is the medium of the canon of the *Theravāda* tradition. It is a historical fact that the *Pāli* canon has come down to us through an oral tradition extending over several centuries.¹ It developed into a written form by the first century B.C.² in Sri Lanka. After the Buddha's demise, his disciples understood the importance of the clarity of the medium in regard to the communication of his doctrines. As a result they showed a keen interest in compiling grammar books for the *Pāli* language. Unlike the other languages, *Pāli* has mostly been employed only for the elucidation of Buddha's teachings and to record the history of the order. Therefore, even the grammatical analyses of *Pāli* are mostly influenced by the doctrines of the Buddha. The necessity of writing grammar books has always been emphasised, quoting a passage from the *Aṅguttaranikāya*, which expresses the importance of clarity of sounds and meanings for the progress of the *dhamma*.³

Moreover, almost all the grammatical treatises written in *Pāli* explain their objective as providing a grammar suitable for the Buddha's words (*jinavacana*).⁴ By the term "*jinavacana*" they meant the *Pāli* canon which comprises the teachings of *Sutta*, *Vinaya* and *abhidhamma*.⁵

The traditional grammar books explain the principles of the *Pāli* language through the following:

- i. *Sutta*
- ii. *Vutti*
- iii. *Udāharaṇa*

The term *Sutta* means a very short statement of a principle of grammar which is made mainly for easy remembrance. Detailed explanation of the *Sutta* is called *Vutti*. By the third (*Udāharaṇa*) they give examples which prove the principle and also the relevant exceptions.

All the grammar books explain the alphabet as the first topic⁶ and the *Kaccāyana* which is considered to be the oldest, lays down a principle of characters by following sutta : “*Attho akkharasaññāto*”⁷

This *sutta* is considered to be delivered by the Buddha himself. There is an ancient story recorded in the grammar books which supplies the background for its delivering. Two *brahmins* called ‘*Yama*’ and ‘*Uppala*’ were practicing meditation near a river bank repeating the words ‘*khayavaya*’ (vanishing). One of them, seeing a crane catching a fish became confused and started reciting *udakabaka*, (crane in the water,) instead of ‘*khayavaya*’. The other one seeing a piece of cloth on a pot, started to recite words ‘*ghaṭapata*’, “cloth on a pot.” The Buddha seeing their confusion of the relationship between words and meanings, through his divine eye, made them understand the principle that ‘the meaning should be reflected through the characters’ (*attho- akkharasaññāto*). Having heard this principle, they rid themselves of their confusion, understanding the close connection among the words and meanings. On this basis, Ven. *Kaccāyana*, one of the chief disciples of the Buddha, composed the *Kaccāyana* grammar starting with the *sutta-attho akkharasaññāto*.⁸

Another fact that the grammarians emphasize is the necessity of the knowledge of *Pāli* for the realization of *nibbāna*. Because of the knowledge of the characters one can understand the canon as well as its commentaries.⁹ Through this knowledge one fulfils the practise of *sīla*, *samādhi*, and *paññā* (morality, concentration, and wisdom) which are the three main steps of the Buddhist path of deliverance. By this way the knowledge of language causes the three levels of attainments of the Order namely:

- i. *pariyatti* - learning the sacred texts
- ii. *paṭipatti* - the practice and
- iii. *paṭivedha* - realization of *nibbāna*.

The meanings, both mundane and supra-mundane, are expressed and understood through the characters or sounds which combine together in the form of words and sentences. If the nature of characters such as aspirated and non-aspirated is changed the meaning varies-e.g. *satta*-being, *sattha*-weapon. Therefore, the skillfulness in the letters is essential in understanding the Buddha’s word.¹⁰ The one who is not well versed in grammar will also not be clever in the doctrine (*dhamma* and *vinaya*). As a result, he will be unable to follow the path correctly and will be subjected to suffering in existences again and again.¹¹ It should be remembered here that the attainment of *catuṣṭambhidā* (four analytic insights) also has a close relationship with language and grammar and grammar. One of the conditions relevant to attainment of the four insights is to have a knowledge of hundred languages or dialects. Among the four *paṭisambhidās* (*attha*, *dhamma*, *nirutti*, *paṭibhāna*) *nirutti* is closely connected with the knowledge of grammar.¹² This fact is emphasised even by the grammarians.¹³

Because of the above reasons the Buddhist scholars have paid special attention to the following areas of language and have composed a number of books elucidating them throughout the history of the Order:

- i. writing
- ii. expression
- iii. hearing and
- iv. comprehension.

As pointed out by Ven. Buddhadatta,¹⁴ the number of *Pāli* grammars written in Sri Lanka and Burma exceeds fifty-three. Counted with their ancillary works written up to the fifteenth century, their number is more than two thousand.

Paññatti and Pāli Grammar

Most of the *Pāli* traditional grammars treat *paññatti* as an important and essential topic for their explanations of sounds and meanings.¹⁵ Here it is worthwhile to look at the reasons which caused their emphasis on *paññatti*.

According to traditional explanations *paññatti* entails Philological and psychological analysis of sounds and meanings of language. Even in a descriptive grammar, a prominent place is given to the sounds and meanings as they represent the two main divisions of a given language. Therefore, the grammarians who composed philological treatises depending on a Buddhist background, naturally tend to analyse *paññatti* as a preface for their discussion.

In the *Pāli* traditional grammar *paññatti* is always connected with the concept of ‘*liṅgatha*’. As a technical term ‘*liṅgatha*’ means the fundamental meaning of a noun. More correctly, it is the meaning of a noun before its declension in the noun-cases such as accusative and dative. The fundamental meaning of a noun is expressed through the nominative case. In the other cases its meaning is changed to some extent. Following examples of the noun ‘*nara*’ will clarify the fact:

Nominative	- <i>naro</i> – <i>the man</i> – <i>narā</i> - <i>the men</i>
Dative	- <i>narassa</i> – <i>to the man</i> – <i>narānaṃ</i> - <i>to the men</i>
Ablative	- <i>naramhā</i> - <i>from the man</i> – <i>narehi</i> – <i>from the men</i>

The fundamental unit of a given noun (*liṅga*) could be explained as a meaningful noun which is free from case endings, prefixes, suffixes etc. This is taken as the basis of the nouns before their declension in the cases.¹⁶ e.g. *purisa*, *mālā*, *citta*.¹⁷ The meanings of these fundamental units of the nouns (*liṅga*) are called ‘*liṅgatha*’.

‘*Liṅgatha*’ is also called ‘*upādāpaññatti*’. According to *Abhidhamma*, *paññatti* is divided into two main groups.

- i. ***atthapaññatti*** - conceptual and real meanings
- ii. ***nāmapaññatti*** - sounds, words, sentences.

Of them '*atthapaññatti*' is called '*upādāpaññatti*' because the nouns are always based on meanings. Thus the following are synonymous as far as their usage in the *paññatti* is concerned in comparison with the grammatical analysis of '*liṅgattha*'. *Liṅgattha* = *atthapaññatti*, *upādāpaññatti*, *tajjāpaññatti*, *paññāpiyattā paññatti*, *vacanīya*.

The two kinds of meanings, conceptual and real belong to the *upādāpaññatti* or *liṅgattha*. *ghaṭa*-pot, *paṭa*-cloth etc. are called conceptual meanings and *kakkhalaḷakkhaṇā paṭhavindhātu*- hardness of the element of earth etc. which are the characteristics of real *dhammas* are called real meanings.¹⁸ In other words, *liṅgattha* is two-fold as follows:

- i. *sammuti-attha* or *vohārattha*-conceptual or conventional meanings
- ii. *paramattha-attha*- meanings of the real *dhammas*.

The objects of our senses which appear as wholes are really the various combinations of fundamental elements of existence. Depending upon these various appearances the concepts such as *ghaṭa*-pot, *paṭa*-cloth, *ratha*-chariot are constructed in our minds. These are called *sammuti-attha* or *vohārattha*. The hardness of earth element (*pathvidhātu*), Viscosity of water element (*āpodhātu*), calorificity of fire element (*tejodhātu*), inflation of air element (*vāyodhātu*) etc. which are the characteristics of *dhammas* symbolised by the respective words are called *paramattha-attha*.¹⁹

A grammatical analysis of a language should consist of the explanations of expression, writing, hearing and comprehension. In this case articulation of sound and its physical and psychological basis should also be explained. In traditional grammars we find the descriptions relating to the origin of sounds and psychological background for their origination. On the other hand in such a grammar the psychological process and the task of comprehending in relation to the hearing of sounds should also be explained. In these analyses the grammarians seem to follow closely the *abhidhammic* explanations of *paññatti*. As the theory of *paññatti* is related to the two kinds of meanings (conventional and real), the grammarians also pay their attention to the two levels of truth (*sammutisacca* and *paramatthasacca*).

Now it is clear that the *abhidhammic* theory of *paññatti* is closely related to the *Pāli* traditional grammar.

Sound and meanings

The foregoing discussion justifies that the grammatical explanations of sounds and meanings should be introduced as a grammatical analysis of *paññatti*.

In the traditional grammar, the terms *vaṇṇa*, *akkhara* and *sadda* are used as synonyms for sounds. In the *abhidhammic* analysis of *paññatti*, the terms *nāmapaññatti*, *vācaka*, *abhidhāna* and *paññāpanato paññatti* have been used for sounds. It is the opinion of the grammarians as well as the ancient Buddhist scholars that the meanings are conveyed through the sounds are five-fold:

1. *saṅkhāra* - all things produced by causes and conditions
2. *vikāra* - deformity
3. *lakkhaṇa* - characteristics
4. *nibbana* - extinction of defilements
5. *pañatti* - concepts²⁰

The units of sound which express the meanings related to the above five areas are called '*akkhara*' (letters). When these *akkharas* are shown in written forms, various symbols are used. In the *Pāli* language there are forty-one *akkharas*.²¹ These are called *akkhara* because of several reasons:

1. Everything becomes extinct by use again and again. But the *akkharas* never become extinct though they have been used thousands of times to express meanings. Etymologically the term *akkhara* is defined as *na-kharanti* do not vanish.²²
2. Unlike nouns *akkharas* have no synonyms. Because of this reason *akkharas* possess a kind of uniqueness. They do not move or represent other *akkharas*. For example the noun '*nara*' is represented by '*manussa*'. But the letter 'a' cannot be represented by any other letter. Thus the definition '*na kharanti na calanti*' is given to the term '*akkhara*'.²³
3. Buddhism emphasizes the impermanence of every thing that exists.²⁴ If so, the *akkharas* cannot be explained as eternal or not vanishing. It is interesting that the grammarians explain the term *akkhara* as "not vanishing" (*na kharanti*) in a manner which is related to the *abhidhammic* philosophy. It is directly connected with the *abhidhammic* theory of *dhamma*.²⁵

The characteristics of arising and vanishing are applicable only to the *dhammas* which are conditioned by causes²⁶ Their limits, phases etc. are not accepted as real *dhammas*.²⁷ The common characteristics (*anicca, dukkha, anatta*) and own nature (*sabhāvalakkhaṇa*-hardness of *paṭhavindhātu* etc.) can be applied only to the real *dhammas*. It was pointed out that *akkhara* comes under the category of *pañatti*. *Pañattis* are not real *dhammas* according to the theory of *dhamma*. As the *akkharas* are not really conditioned *dhammas*, the characteristics, such as impermanence are not applicable to them.²⁸

To justify this, the grammarians quote the following statement of the Buddha:

Nāmagottaṃ na jīrati' (name and clan do not disappear).²⁹ Thus the traditional grammarians hold the opinion that the *akkharas* are so called because they do not perish. Grammatical analysis of *akkhara* does not end here. The whole process of their origination under five headings (*thāna, karaṇa, payatana, suti, kāla*-place, instrumentality, attempt, hearing and time) and the divisions such as aspirated, no-aspirated are discussed in detail.³⁰

Now it is worthwhile to direct our discussion towards the analysis of meaning and its relationship with sounds. It was said that ‘*attha*’ means the two kinds of meaning (conventional and real) comprehended through the sounds. Categories of meanings such as *ghaṭṭa*, *paṭṭa* which depend on conventional usages are called *sammuti-attha*, and five aggregates (*rūpa*, *vedanā*, *saññā*, *saṅkhāra*, *viññāṇa*) and *nibbāna*³¹ belong to *paramattha-attha*³² Some grammarians classify the meanings into three groups as follows:

i. *lokiya-attha* : meanings which are mundane

The *dhammas* (phenomena) with defilements related to the three spheres (*kāma*-sensual, *rūpa*-form, and *arūpa*-formless) belong to this category. They have many divisions such as *khandha*-aggregates, *āyatana*-bases, *dhātu*-elements³³

ii. *lokuttara-attha* : meanings which are supra-mundane

To this belong the following *dhammas* which are free from defilements: Four paths (*sotāpatti*, *sakadāgāmi*, *anāgāmi*, *arahatta*) and their results and *nibbāna*.

iii. *voḥāra-attha* - conventional meanings.

The conventional meanings are those which represent the various combinations, phases and limits of the real *dhammas*.³⁴ A single meaning may represent several nouns. eg. The meaning ‘king of gods’ is expressed by the nouns. *sakka*, *purindada*, *devarāja*, *vajirapāni*, *sujampati*, *sahassakkha*, *mahinda*, *vajirāvudha*.³⁵ Due to various reasons a particular meaning is conveyed through many nouns. Hence the definition of the term *Paññatti* fits in well to the above explanation.

‘*Paññatti* is so called because it makes the hearer’s mind pleasant in various ways and conveys meanings to improve his intelligence.’³⁶

The next problem the grammarians tried to solve is whether the meaning is conveyed through a single letter (sound) or a collection of letters. As the words comprise of several letters in many cases, no one can say that meaning is conveyed through a single letter. If so, the other letters in that particular word become redundant. On the other hand we do not experience the meanings coming out of each and every letter separately. Thus the saying “the meaning is conveyed through single letters’ becomes invalid. Again we notice that the letters disappear one by one when the words are spoken. Letters do not exist as a whole at the same time. So we cannot say that the meaning is conveyed through a collection of letters. And it is also not valid to say that the meaning is conveyed through any other way, either.³⁷ This is the problem that the grammarians had to solve in regard to sounds and meanings and in solving it they sought help in the *abhidhammic* analysis of *paññatti*. It is interesting, before we go to the solution, to have a look at the simile given by the grammarians to clarify the above problem.

- i. Though the spokes, rims, shafts etc. do not make the task of moving, when those parts are put together as a wheel they are capable of moving. Likewise though the individual letters do not convey the meaning, a combination is capable of conveying it.
- ii. The above solution is not acceptable as it is against the theory that “if a single unit of something is incapable of producing a particular result, a collection of them also would not be able to produce it. A single unit of sand as well as a collection of them do not produce oil.’
- iii. On one hand the first solution can be considered as valid. According to the Buddha’s teachings the causes are capable of producing the relevant results when the real conditions are present. A cause which does not produce a result owing to the lack of other relevant conditions cannot be considered as a non-cause because it is capable of producing that result when the required conditions are present. Likewise, a letter which has no meaning without the other letters cannot be considered as meaningless. For example, one is not counted as an unskillful person owing to the fact that one is unable to bear a litter which should be borne by a number of people. He is really unskillful if he is unable to bear it when the others are present.
- iv. This third argument is also not acceptable because in the case of a litter all the people are present at the same time but in the case of hearing, the sounds or letters disappear one by one when they are heard. When we hear the letter ‘*ṇa*’ of the term ‘*vaṇṇa*’ the former letter ‘*va*’ has disappeared.³⁸
- v. Now it is clear that the problem of sound and meanings has become more complex. In order to solve this, ne traditional grammarians have adopted the theory of *paññatti*. When a fire-brand is rotated it seems like a circle of fire though in reality there is none. After the arising of thousands of thoughts in relation to the appearances and disappearances of the fire-brand there arises a thought taking together all shapes of the fire-brand as its object and then the fire-brand appears as a circle. The reason for this is the speedy appearances and disappearances of the consciousness.³⁹

The sounds are called ‘*nāma*’ (nam-to bend) because of two reasons :

- i. the nouns seem to bend towards the meanings
- ii. the meaning seems to bend towards the nouns.

The grammarians are of the opinion that only the former one is applicable to the Buddha’s teachings because the meanings are more important than the nouns as far as the Buddhist philosophy is concerned.⁴⁰

Expression and Hearing

Expression:

Articulating sounds through the vocal organs and the related psychological process has been explained by the grammarians depending solely on such *abhidhammic* explanations.

There arises a thought of expression in the mind of the person who thinks to express something. At the same time, that thought causes the arising of the collection of eight material elements (*paṭhavi, āpo, tejo, vāyo, vaṇṇa, gandha, rasu, oḷā*, elements of extension, cohesion, heat, motion, colours odour, taste and nutriment)⁴¹ in one of the six places of the origination of sounds (*kaṇṭha*-throat *tālu*-palate, *muddha*-cerebrum, *danta*-teeth, *oṭṭha*-lips, *nāsikā*-nose). Again as a result of the former experience or *karma*, there the very same collection of eight material elements in some place. Then owing to the motion of the element of *vavo* the two elements of earth (*paṭhavi*) produced psychologically and karmatically, strike together. Because this striking, sounds are produced in one of the six places of origination of sounds. The sounds are named according to the places of their origination as *kaṅkhaḥa, tāluja* etc.⁴²

The above process of articulating sounds can be explained under six steps as follows:

- i. thinking
- ii. physical reaction to the psychological action
- iii. physical reaction caused by the former experience or *karma*
- iv. motion (*vāyu*-air)
- v. striking (*paṭhavi*-solidity)
- vi. origination of sounds

The above six steps clearly show that the *Theravāda* conception of the origination of vocal sounds is founded on a psychological basis.

It is a clear fact that the articulation is preceded by a thinking process. The arising of eight material elements can be regarded as a stimulation of the place of articulation caused by thinking. According to *abhidhamma* there arise seven thoughts (mental concomitants-*cetasika*) with each and every consciousness.⁴³ The first one of them is *phassa* (contact It means the contact between senses and their respective objects. This is a very subtle process unlike the striking two material things. It is compared to an arising of saliva when we see the others eating sour fruits.⁴⁴

Stimulation of the places of articulation caused by thinking can also be considered as a similar process. The material elements produced by kamma or former experience are nothing but the same places of articulation of the body. According to *abhidhamma* one of the main causes for the origin of physical body is *kamma* or former experience.⁴⁵

Thus we can understand the difference of two sets of the same material elements caused by thinking and *kamma*. In the process of articulation motion connects with the air-element. The air-stream that comes from lungs is pressed through the mouth and the nose in order to express sounds and the grammarians explain this as motion connected with the air-element. The next step *phassa* or contact is also caused by the air-element. In articulation, three places of the tongue (*jivhagga*, *jivhopagga*, *jivhāmajjha*-the end, near the end and the middle of the tongue)⁴⁶ are pressed to the places of articulation. These are called *karaṇaṭṭhāna*.⁴⁷ When the *karaṇa-ṭṭhānas* are pressed to the places of articulation the air-stream goes through them and as a result sounds are produced. The grammarians explain the above process as the task of motion by air-element and the task of contact by the earth-element. Now we can decide that grammarians have tried to explain the process of expression or articulation on a theoretical and scientific basis.

Hearing:

As in the case of expression, the details of the process of hearing in the grammar are compatible with those of the *abbidhamma*. The following quotation will prove the fact:

“In the mind of the person who hears a word like ‘*vaṇṇa*’ (letter), there arise two *javanas* (apperceptions) as present and past regarding each sound of that word. Then arises one *javana* regarding the whole collection of sounds. After this there arises another *javana* regarding *namapaññatti* (nominal concept) or the noun. Thus the *namapaññatti* becomes clear only after the *javana*-process to which the whole set of sounds becomes the object. After this meaning is understood.”⁴⁸ In order to understand the above quotation we should pay our attention to some other facts explained in the *abhidhamma*. The sound (*sadda*) which is the object of the ear is a real phenomenon (*dhamma*).⁴⁹ Noun or *namapaññatti* belongs to the category of concepts and therefore it is not a real *dhamma*.

As in the collection of many threads there arises the concept of cloth in our minds, in the same way numerous *namapatinnattis* are produced in our minds depending on various combinations of sounds.⁵⁰ Thus the nouns in reality are mental productions and they are *paññattis*. When the *paññatti* becomes an object of mind-door (*manodvāra*),⁵¹ after several thought moments there arise seven *javanas*.⁵²

The aboveprocess of hearing can also be explained under several steps

- i. hearing of sounds
- ii. assimilation of the memories of sounds past and present in the mind and their identification
- iii. understanding of the words which are the various combinations of sounds
- iv. understanding the relationship among the words and meanings.

In the process of hearing the first task is to identify the sounds. Depending on the former experience the present sounds are understood. Next to it there occurs the

understanding of various combinations of sounds or words (*vacana*). The final result of this process of hearing is to understand the meanings related to those words. Thus it is clear that the words as well as their meanings which we understand through communication are merely mental productions and they are not real. Hence the *ābhidhammikas* grouped them (*paññatti* or concepts) under two headings:

- i. *nāmapaññatti* - concepts related with sounds
- iii. *atthapaññatti* - concepts related with meanings.

Sounds are mental productions based on the space and air in our bodies.⁵³ According to *Theravāda* tradition sound is not a divine and unperishable element as is accepted in the Hindu tradition.⁵⁴

As a whole what the *Theravādins* try to say is that the process of hearing, expression and comprehension is a natural process caused by mental and physical reactions. We conceptualize meanings depending on various combinations of sounds as we guess the existence of fire depending on smoke.⁵⁵

End Notes:

1. Aclikaram, E.W., Early History of Buddhism in Ceylon, Colombo, 1953, pp. 24-26
2. op. cit. pp. 76-79
3. *Āṅguttaranikāya*, i, p. 116
4. *Mahārūpasiddhi*, ed. D.S. Dharmananda, p. 30.
Bālāvaṭāra, ed. Devarakkhita, p. 8.
Kaccāyanavaṇṇanā, ed. B. Pannalankara, H. Sumanasara, U. Piyatissa, p. 68.
5. *Buddhippasādani (Padasādhanatikā)*, ed. Dhirananda, Vacissara, p. 10.
6. *Kaccāyana, Māharūpasiddhi, Bālāvatāra, Moggallāyana, Saddanīti*
7. *Kaccāyanavannanā*, p. 8.
8. ibid.
9. *Māharūpasiddhiṭṭhā*, ed. D.S. Dharmananda, p. 3.
10. *Māharūpasiddhi*, p. 1
11. *Moggallāyanapañcīkā*, ed. D. Dharmananda, p. 4.
12. *Visuddhimagga*, ed. P. Buddhadatta, pp. 329-331.
13. *Saddanīti*, ed. A. Seelananda, p. 530.
14. Buddhadatta, A.P. *Pāli Sāhityaya*, Vol. II, pp. 460-526.
15. *Mahārūpasiddhi*, p. 101, *Māharūpasiddhiṭṭhā*, p. 51; *Saddanīti*, p. 626.
16. *Mahārūpasiddhi*, p. 101.
17. *Saddanīti*, p. 563.

18. Karunadasa, Y., The Abhidhammic Theory of *Paññatti* : The Category of the Norminal and the Conceptual, Buddhist Philosophy and Culture, Essays in Honour of N.A. Jayawickrama, pp. 71-74.
19. op. cit. pp. 75-88.
20. *Saddanīti*, p. 532.
21. *Bālāvatāra*, ed. *Devarakkhita*, p. 14.
22. *Saddanīti*, p. 532
23. *Buddhippasadanī*, p. 12
24. *Mahāvaggapāli*, Vol. I, ed. D. Pannasara, p. 11.
25. Y. Karunadasa, *ibid*, pp. 75-88.
26. *ibid*.
27. *Abhidharmārthasaṅgrahasannaya*, ed. Pannamolitissa, p. 158.
28. *Māharūpasiddhiṭṭhā*, p. 5.
29. *Rupaṃ jīratī maccānaṃ - nāmagottam na jīratī*
30. *Mhārupasiddhī*, pp. 2,3; *Bālāvatāra*, pp. 1,2; *Moggallāyanapañcīkā*, pp. 7-9
31. *Buddhippasādanī*, pp. 13, 14.
32. Cpd.,pp. 1-5.
33. Karunadasa, Y., *ibid*.
34. *Māharūpasiddhī*, pp. 13,14.
35. *Saddanīti*, p. 342.
36. op.cit. 797.
37. *Buddhippasādanī*, p. 14
38. *ibid*.
39. *ibid*, *Mukhamattadīpanī (Kaccāyanaṭṭhā)*, pp. 11,12.
40. *Buddhippasādanī*, p. 8
41. Cpd., pp. 154-157.
42. *Buddhippasādanī*, p. 16, *Saddanīti*, p. 1.
43. Karunadasa, Y., The Universal Concomitants of Consciousness in the Abhidhamma Psychology, International Buddhist Association, Japan, Bukkyo Kenkyu, Vol. Ixx, pp. 191-212.
44. ABHVT., p. 27.
45. Cpd., p. 165.
46. *Mahārūpasiddhī*, p. 2.
47. *ibid*.
48. *Buddhippasādanī*, p. 15
49. Cpd., pp. 198-201.
50. op. cit. introduction, pp. 3-6.

51. *ibid*, pp. 198-201.
52. *ibid*.
53. *Saddanīṭī*, p. 1
54. *Buddhippasādanī*, p. 15
55. *Māhārūpasiddhiṭīkā*, p. 4.

Bibliography

- Abhidhammatthasaṅgaha-Vibhāvinīṭīkā*, ed. W. Paññānanda, Colombo, 1898
- Abhidhammatthasaṅgaha*, ed. T.W. Rhys Davids, JPTS. 1884 (1-48)
- Abhidhammatthasaṅgahadīpanīpālī*, Rangoon, 1929
- Abhidhammatthavikāsinī*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, Colombo, 1961
- Abhidhammāvatāra*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, Buddhadatta's Manuals I (pp.1-142), PTS, 1915
- Abhidharmadīpa* (with) Vibhāṣāprabhāvṛtti, ed. P.s Jaini, Tibetan Sanskrit works series, IV, Patna, 1959
- Abhidharmakośavyākhyā* (Sinhalese Edition), ed. And tr. **M.Sāsanaratana**, Colombo, 1976
- Abhidharmakośavyākhyā (Sphutarāthā)* I-II, ed. S.Dvarikadas Sastri, Varanasi, 1970-1972
- Abhidharmasamuccayabhāṣya*, ed. N. Tatia, Patna, 1976
- Abhidharmārthasaṅgrahasannaya*, ed. *Paññāmolitissa*, Ambalangoda, 1926
- Abhidhānappadīpikā*, ed. W. Subhūti, W. Wāchissara, Colombo, 1938
- Aṅguttaranikāya Aṭṭhakathā (Manorathapūranī)*, I-II, ed. M. Walleser, H. Kopp, PTS, 1924-1956
- Aṅguttaranikāya*, I-IV, ed. R. Morris, E. Hardy, C.A.F. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1885-1910
- Bodhicaryāvatārapañjikā*, ed. P.L. Vaidya, Mithila Institute, Darbhanga, 1960
- Buddhippasādanī (Padasādhanāṭīkā)*, ed. *Dhirānanda, Vācissara*, Colombo, 1908
- Bālāvatāra*, ed. Devarakkhita, Colombo, 1904
- Bālāvatāraṭīkā (Sobhodhikā)*, ed. Siri Sumangala, Colombo, 1913
- Dhammapada*, ed. Ven. Narada, Colombo, 1973
- Dhammapada Aṭṭhakathā*, I, ed. H. Smith, H.C. Norman, L.S. Tailang, PTS, 1906-1915
- Dhammasaṅgani Aṭṭhakathā (Atthasālinī)*, Ed. E. Muller, PTS, 1897
- Dīghanikāya Aṭṭhakathā (Sumaṅgalavilāsinī)* I-III, ed. T.W. Rhys Davids, J.E. Carpenter, W. Stede, PTS, 1886-1932
- Dīghanikāya Aṭṭhakathā Ṭīkā (Līnatthavaṇṇanā)*, III, ed. Lily de Silva, PTS, 1970
- Dīghanikāya, I-III*, ed. T.W. Rhys Davids, J.E. Carpenter, PTS, 1890-1911
- Kaccāyana and Kaccāyanavaṇṇanā*, ed. B. Paññālaṅkāra, H. Sumanasāra, U. Piyatissa, Colombo, 1905

- Kathāvattu, I-II*, ed. A.C. Taylor, PTS, 1894-1897
- Kathāvattuhupakaraṇa Aṭṭhakathā*, ed. N.A. Jayawickrema, PTS, 1979
- Madhuṭṭikā, I, Rangoon, 1926-1928
- Mahāsaddanūṭi*, ed. A. Seelānanda, Colombo, 1909
- Mahāniddeśa Aṭṭhakathā (Niddesavaṇṇanā Saddhammapajjotikā) I-II*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, PTS, 1931-1941
- Mahārūpasiddhi and Mahārūpasiddhiṭṭikā*, ed. D.S. Dharmānanda, Colombo, 1915
- Majjhimanikāya Aṭṭhakathā (Papañcasūdani)*, I, ed. J.W. Woods, D. Kosambi, I.B. Horner, PTS, 1922-1938
- Majjhimanikāya, I-III*, ed. V. Trenckner, R. Chalmers, Mrs. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1888-1925
- Manisāramañjusūṭikā, I-II*, ed. Sixth Buddhist Council, Buddhasāsanasamiti, Rangoon, 1960-1964
- Milindapañha*, ed. V. Trenckner, PTS, 1962
- Moggallāna and Moggallānapañcīkā*, ed. D. Dhammānanda, Colombo, 1931
- Mohavicchedanī*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, A.K. Warder, PTS, 1961
- Mukhamattadīpanī (Kaccāyanaṭṭikā)*, Colombo, 1921
- Mūlamādhyamakakārikā*, ed. And tr. D.J. Kalupahana, Delhi, 1991
- Mūlamādhyamakakārikāvyaḅhyā* (Sinhalese), ed. M. Sāsanaratana, Colombo, 1963
- Mūlaṭṭikā*, ed. *D. Paññāsāra*, P. Wimaladhamma, Colombo, 1938
- Nettipakaraṇa Aṭṭhakathā*, ed. W. Piyatissa, Colombo, 1921
- Niddesavaṇṇanā (Saddhammapajjotikā= Mahāniddeśa Aṭṭhakathā) I-III*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, PTS, 1931-1941
- Nāmarūpapariccheda*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, JPTS, 1913-1914
- Nāmarūpasamāsa*, ed. P. Dhammārāma, JPTS, 1915-1916
- Paramatthavinicchaya*, ed. A.P. Buddhadatta, JPTS, 1985
- Paṭisambhidāmagga Aṭṭhakathā, II (Saddhammapakāsinī) II*, ed. C.V. Joshi, PTS, 1933-1947
- Paṭisambhidāmagga*, II, ed. A.C. Taylor, PTS, 1905-1907
- Puggalapaññatti*, ed. R. Morris, PTS, 1883
- Saccasaṅkhepa*, ed. *P. Dhammārāma*, JPTS, 1917-1919 (pp. 1-25)
- Saṅyuttanikaya*, I-V, ed. L. Feer, Mrs. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1884-1904
- Saṅkhepavaṇṇanāṭṭikā*, ed. *W. Paññānanda*, Colombo, 1899
- Sunhodhālanākāra*, ed. L. Lankānanda, Colombo, 1947
- Suttanipāta Aṭṭhakathā (Paramatthajotikā II)*, ed. H. Smith, PTS, 1916-1918
- Suttanipāta*, ed. D. Andersen, H. Smith, PTS, 1913
- Tattvasaṅgrahapañjikā II*, ed. S. Dwarikadas Sastri, Varanasi, 1968

Trimśatikā, ed. and tr. B.J. Bhaskar, India, 1971

Udāna, ed. P. Steithal, PTS, 1885

Vinaya Aṭṭhakathā (samantapāsādikā), I-II, ed. J. Takakusu, M. Nagai, PTS, 1924-1947

Vinayapiṭaka, I-V, ed. H. Oldenberg, London, 1879-1883

Visuddhimagga, ed. C.A.F. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1920-1921

Visuddhimaggaṭṭkā (Paramatthamañjusā), ed. M. Dhammānanda, Colombo, 1928

Viśuddhimārgasannaya, I-III, ed. B. *Saddhātissa*, Colombo, 1949-1955

Translations

A Manual of *Abhidhamma (Abhidhammatthasaṅgaha)*, tr. Nārada, Kandy, 1968

Buddhist Manual of Psychological Ethics (*Dhammasaṅgani*), tr. Mrs. Rhys Davids, Oriental Translation Fund, New Series, XII, London, 1923

Compendium of Philosophy (*Abhidhammatthasaṅgaha*), tr. S.Z. Aung, revised and ed. by Mrs. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1910

Dialogues of the Buddha (*Dīghanikāya*), I-III, tr. T.W. Rhys Davids, SBB, II-IV, London, 1899-1912

Middle Length Sayings (*Majjhimanikāya*) III, tr. I.B. Horner, PTS, 1954

Milinda's Questions (*Milindapañha*), I, tr. I.B. Horner, SBB, 1964-1969

Points of Controversy (*Kathāvatthu*), tr. S.Z. Aung, Mrs. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1915

Tattvasamgraha I, tr. Ganganatha Jha, Motilal Banarsidas, Delhi, 1937

The Book of the Discipline (*Vinayapiṭaka*) V (*Cullavagga*), SBB, tr. I.B. Horner, 1952

The Book of the Gradual Sayings (*Aṅguttaranikāya*), I, tr. F.L. Woodward, PTS, 1951

The Expositor (*Attasālinī*), I-II, tr. P. Tin, ed. and revised by Mrs. Rhys Davids, PTS, 1920-1921

The Guide (*Nettipakaraṇa*), tr. Bhikkhu Ñāṇamoli PTS, 1962

The Path of Discrimination (*Paṭisambhidāmagga*), tr. Bhikkhu Ñāṇamoli, PTS, 1982

The Path of Purification (*Visuddhimagga*), tr. Bhikkhu Ñāṇamoli, Colombo, 1964

Verses of Uplift (*Udāna*), tr. F.L. Woodward, London, 1948

Woven Cadences of Early Buddhist (*Suttanipāta*), tr. E.M. Hare, SBB, London, 1947

Secondary Sources

Adikaram, E.W., *Early History of Buddhism in Ceylon*, Colombo, 1953

Balingay, A. *Modern Introduction to Indian Logic*, India, 1976

Bhattacharya, B., *A Study in Language and meaning*, Calcutta, 1962

Bode, M.H., *The pali Literature of Burma*, Rangoon, 1965

Buddhadatta, A.P., *Pali Sāhityaya*, II, Colombo, 1957

Fromkin, Victoria and Robert Rodman, *An Introduction to language*, U.S.A., 1978

- Jaini, P.S., *The Vaibhāṣika Theory of Words and meanings*, BSOAS, vol. XXII, 1959 (pp.95-108)
- Jayatilleke, K.N., *Early Buddhist Theory of Knowledge*, Allen and Unwin Ltd., London, 1963
- Jayatilleke, K.N., *The Message of the Buddha*, ed. Ninian Smart, London, 1975
- Kalupahana, D.J., *Buddhist Philosophy, A Historical Analysis*, Hawaii, 1976
- Kalupahana, D.J., *Causality : The Central Philosophy of Buddhism*, Honolulu, 1933
- Kalupahana, D.J., *A History of Buddhist Philosophy Continuities and Discontinuities*, Motilal Banarsidass, India, 1994
- Karunadasa, Y., *Abhidamma Theory of Paññatti, Buddhist Philosophy and Culture*, Essays in Honour of N.A. Jayawikrema, Colombo, 1987
- Karunadasa, Y., *Buddhist Analysis of Matter*, Colombo, 1967
- Karunasasa, Y., *The Buddhist Theory of Double Truth*, JHSSUK, vol. III and IV, 1984-1985 (pp. 25-55)
- Karunadas, Y., *The Theravāda Version of Dharmavāda*, Annual Memoirs of the Otani University Shin Buddhist Comprehensive Research Institute, vol. 5, 1987
- Malalasekara, G.P., *The Pāli Literature of Ceylon*, Colombo, 1958
- Norman, K.R., *Pāli Literature*, Wiesbasen; Harrassowitz (History of Indian Literature, vol.7), 1988
- Nyānātīloka*, Guide Through the *Abhidhammapīṭaka*, Colombo, 1938
- Nānānanda*, Bhikkhu, *Concept and Reality in Early Buddhist Through*, Kandy, 1976
- Paul, Diana, *Paramartha's Theory of language.*, JIP. VII (pp.231-255)
- Pāli -English Dictionary*, ed. T.W. Rhys Davids and William Stede, PTS, 1972
- Warder, A.K., *The Concept of a Concept*, JIP vol. I, 1970-1972

A review on *Diyakaliya* in Yoda Ela. An unique structure of the canal irrigation system of ancient Sri Lanka.

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Abstract:

Long extending canals, distributing water for vast areas are one of the ancient irrigation structures of Sri Lanka. Normally, in terms of functionality, these canals are of four types. One; supply of water for paddy fields located at the destination point of the canal. Second; supply of water for small tanks located along the canal which ultimately feed paddy fields. Third; canals that distribute water for the entire downstream area enabling people to use free water or water diverted by temporally earth dams or *Amuna* (anicuit). Other types of canals were made to provide water to tanks located along its way as well as to its destination reservoir. Yoda ela, the longest and marvellous canal built by our ancient irrigation engineers belongs to the latter category. It starts from a large reservoir called Kalawewa being passed about 54 km to its destination reservoir *Tisawewa* located in Anuradapura ancient city. Yoda ela is mostly famous for its engineering aspect of carrying a large volume of water maintaining the same flowing capacity for a distance of 17 mile even though higher amount being provided for surroundings agricultural lands. On the other hand, Yoda ela has been constructed mostly in higher elevated sites in the downstream opposite to contours. The research explored that actually Yoda ela is not only a canal of water carrying, but also a water source freely flown on the ground can be denoted as a flown tank. At some places even today this is evident. In addition, archaeological investigation confirmed hundreds of small village tanks had been directly fed by the canal. Research explored in addition to tanks, many other unusual structures had been there. One of them is *Diyakaliya* that differs from tanks. The main concern was given to study these ancient structures focusing attention on their engineering, hydrological and water management aspects and the functionality. Present paper as an outcome of that research, first discusses structural layout of the *Diyakaliya* from engineering point of view and then highlights its functionality from a hydrological engineering and environmental perspectives. Research was basically undertaken with field investigation together with topographical map interpretation. By the present as Yoda ela canal has been damaged and subject to modify under the *Mahaweli* Development project undertaken in 1970s. Thus ruins and limited remnants of the canal were the focal point of concern of this research. A number of Archaeological excavations were done at that sites. Opinions of old persons in the area were also used to understand the ancient layout of the *Diyakaliya* and its functionality. Research explored that ancient *Diyakaliya* is a means of intensifying water flowing capacity of the canal. Furthermore it worked as an instrument of water purifying, sediment and flood controlling of the canal itself and the surrounding. It is also evident that these structures have played a considerable role in the canal based water management systems. Therefore *Diyakaliya* is an unique feature that our attention should be further focused.

Keywords:- Hydrology, Water Management, Irrigation, DiyaKaliya

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Introduction

Irrigation water management systems in ancient Sri Lanka were consisted of many structures. Village tanks that impounded free water from their individual catchments, medium scale tanks organised into cascading systems based on streams, large reservoirs of water storing and distribution, and canals diverting water from streams or from large reservoirs. Canal system is not a new thing to the world now, but it is evident that Sri Lanka has a long history of canal irrigation that goes back to 1st century BC. Evidences are available that impounding water for agricultural purposes in small ponds has been practiced by our ancient people even in the protohistoric times (Deranigala, 1992). After beginning of the written history, with migrations of Vijaya and his companions (according to our great chronicle *Mahavamsa*) this water impounding system, developed with construction of tanks. When they continued settling down in the river basins, they realised the necessity of harnessing water using advantages of the topographical conditions, monsoonal climate and drainage systems of the undulating land surface. In tank building, they have utilised technology they brought from their mother land (India), with the existing knowledge hardworking experiences of the aborigines. With the increase of population over the settled areas (Northern and Southern Dry zone) building of tanks became gradually developed with the advancement of technology. As a result, by the 3rd century B.C large tanks damming rivers came into existence. They understood that small tanks built based on steams are not sufficient to store water for long dry periods. They wanted to collect a large amount of water in reservoirs so that to convey water to necessary points such as small tanks and other irrigable lands. Accordingly, the concept of building long extended canals came into popular. Some canals functioned as connecting large tanks. Some were planned to directly provide water for paddy fields. Another type was to bring water for end tank while providing with water for small tanks as well as for irrigable lands located alone the canal area. Yoda ela belongs to the latter category.

Yoda Ela is a long canal of about 54 km miles runs from *Kalawewa* tank to *Tisawewa* tank in Anuradhapura city. Historians believe this canal has been made to provide necessary water for Anuradapura city requirement. But many researches have shown that the purpose might be irrigation water supply for a vast irrigable area where no other water sources were available (Brohier, 1935; Panapitiya, 2010). According to the contemporary irrigation works and spatial distribution, Yoda ela has been constructed in 3rd century of during the period of Anuradapura kingdom. The canal started at the point of sluice where water from the tank was released. At the beginning *Kalawewa* was a small tank, but time went on they realised a considerable amount water in *kalaoya* could be impounded. Thus it is evident at several times in the history *Kalawewa* has been expanded under patronage of King Dhatusena (459-477), in modern time in 1977 the first phase of *Mahaweli* Development Program implemented in this area and instead of Yoda ela a new canal (jaya Ganga) was constructed starting from a new sluice from *Kalawewa*. The old Yoda ela has been damaged at some places and at some sites Jaya Ganga connects to the Yoda ela. Under this complication, fully recognising of the structure old Yoda ela is a difficult task. However historical, archaeological and field investigations show that there had been a marvellous water management systems based on Yoda ela. In this regard, the main concern of the present study is given to view the specific structural of the canal *Diyakaliya* from hydrological environmental and water management perspectives.

Methodology

Yoda ela has been constructed high elevated ground, instead of the low laying valley bottom that normally engineers are used. Topographical survey on Yoda ela has done using contours analysing method. Accordingly, it was understood that the canal had flowed in a same contour line (300m) In order to confirm this, Geographical Position Systems (GPS) along the canal was used. The structural form of the canal route was identified with the use of software (GPS-Track option) with positioning of irrigational features, topographical variations of the area as well as structural changes of the canal. Topographical maps, contour data and aerial photo interpretation were also used to verify this information. Field investigations on broken parts of the ancient canal were done. Some information on functionality of canal in the past, were collected by hearing to the old persons in the area. Chronicles and other historic documents were referred to get essential information with regard to history of canal.

Result and Discussion

Diyakaliya is a feature exits in the canal at the bending parts of meanders. At this site, normally water flowing speed get slow down and some quantity is remained there being flown the rest into the normal flow. This feature is like ox-fold lakes formed naturally in rivers in the lower valley. The noteworthy fact that meanders in Yoda ela have been made by ancient engineers purposely to convey water for high grounds where there was a need of water for irrigable lands.

At the narrow parts of the bend, earthen dams or dam's stony dams have been made in order to remain a considerable amount of water in the *Diyakaliya*. When canal flow is zero, water in these elements remains for a considerable time enable to use water in the dry season. The normal size of this feature is about 35/40 the dam is about 500m length. Depth is about 20 feet. Investigation explored that these features have been constructed in high value counters being actual canal in the lower contours (fig. 1) the survey explored 50 *Diyakaliya* located within 17 miles of the canal.

Fig 1. Located of *Diyakaliya* in Mahailupallama

Map 1: Distribution of contour in Upper basin of *Kala oya*

Fig.2: Function of *Diyakaliya* in *Mahailuppallama*

No	<i>Diyakaliya</i>	<i>Wawe</i>
1	Position of higher land	Position of tank from high land to low land
2	Canal being connected to the <i>Diyakaliya</i>	Construction of canal in order to flow around the Tank
3	<i>Diyakaliya</i> being connected to natural stone ridge	Dam being contracted up to higher contour
4	Issue of water through a natural functioning	Release of water to tank through sluice installed on the bank of Yoda Ela canal
5	Controlling the Sediment	Controlling the sediment and providing water to tank
6	Providing water to land cultivate through <i>Diyakaliya</i>	Combined with settlement and cascade

Table No.01 Different of *Diyakaliya* and *Wewa*

Source. Field survey

In this research attention was paid to understand how *Diyakaliya* was built harnessing the topographical conditions of the canal area. It was confirmed that the altitudes above the mean sea level was higher in the sites of *Diyakaliya* located. Recovery shape of *Diyakaliya* named *Amunukolya* and *Mahailuppallama* good examples. They are located at about 103-107 m from mean sea level where *Yoda ela* flows about 93-98m elevation. It is apparent that the ancient irrigation technicians have worked and acted with a profound understanding and sound knowledge of geographical features. This can be revealed from the map which shows the gradient of the relevant earth zone.

***Diyakaliya* as an Instrument for Sediment Controlling.**

Investigation revealed that *Diyakaliya* positioned at a high altitude from the canal unlike normal tanks (Panabokke, 2009). Points out it has been used as a unit in which sediment gets deposited. As *Yoda Ela* has been planned to flow through elevated grounds in the left side of *Kalaoya* basin, water mixed with sediments flows to the canal on a higher scale. Therefore, the problem that arose here was whether sediments brought by the canal flowed for 54 miles or a technological method was adopted to collect them. Therefore, in order to control the impact made on the circulation of water by the sediments and to provide the kinetic power for water to flow ahead, *Diyakaliya* has been fixed in a zone with an even altitude. Just before scaling up a high land, the pressure caused by collecting a vast volume of water in the *Diyakaliya* would help flow water ahead.

When canal flowing characteristics are considered it is apparent that *Diyakaliya* has done a considerable role in sediment controlling of the *Yoda ela*. It is revealed from many researches that ancient irrigation systems of Sri Lanka has given an extraordinary attention on controlling of soil sedimentation in tanks. Hence ancient tanks, were equipped with three sluices placed at three level of the tank. The (high level) sluice was used to release water for irrigation when water available at full capacity of tank. The middle sluice was used when water levels goes down to tanks half capacity. The lowest sluice locally called *Mada sorowa* used to remove sediments deposited in the bottom of tank (Brohier, 1937; Parker, 1909; Awsadahami, 2015; Vithanachchi, 2015). It is apparent that

this concept has been applied in yoda ela through *Diyakaliya*. The process of depositing sediments in the *Diyakaliya* has a direct connection with the distribution of the contour lines of the relevant zone. After flowing for 1 1/2 miles, water gets collected inside *Diyakaliya*. There are three water levels inside the *Diyakaliya*; Top water level, filling water level and down water level (fig 01). The top and second water levels constantly fluctuate or sway around the *Diyakaliya* during which sediments gradually gets deposited in the bottom. At the third level, with a new flurry of water, the old water level emerge up and the pressure caused by it, the water flows ahead

Diyakaliya as a Water Storing Element

Fig.03: Distribution of contour in *Diyakaliya* Area

It is evident that *Diyakaliya* functioned as a water storing element like a pond. According to the people, at least for about 6 months, in the driest seasons water remains in these *Diyakaliya* even under the status of no flow of the canal. During that time, people who lived in the vicinity of *Diyakaliya* used water for homestead, drinking and sanitation and for small plots of paddy lands. There are some evidences small scale sluices have been made to take water from *Didiyakaliya* for their paddy lands located in between canal and *Diyakaliya*. Archeological survey conducted by the present research

confirmed that a large number of villages have been concentrated around these water storing ponds.

Hydrological Significance of *Diyakalia*

Hydraulically in a case of a river, water capacity, depth, its bottom characteristics, width and the land slope gradient are the major determinant factors of the water flow. In a strength linear canal, water flowing velocity is normally higher than that of meander shaped canal. Also in deeper canals, water flow is slower than wider canal unless slope is gentle. If the purpose is only carrying water to its destination point, canals path is designed to linear shape as possible as to flow maximum volume. But *Yoda ela* has been designed covering a large area to provide maximum water for its vicinity. Thus meander shape has been purposely planned in elevated area where water is essentially needed. Under this situation, *Diyakaliya* positioned in the bends of the canal, was a good structure that water could be impounded. On the other hand, it was understood that most parts of the area along the canal are high grounds, characterised with dryness. Thus ground water table in this land is very deeper than the surrounding area. Hence it is apparent that *Diyakaliya* has provided considerable discharge to ground water for the surrounding dry lands likewise what happened in small tanks in the Dry zone. Furthermore, it can be assumed that *Diyakaliya* has functioned as an element of rising up of water table.

When the shape and structure of *Diyakaliya* were studied deeply, it was understood that after water filling up of the *Diyakaliya*, excess water enters the main flow through a narrow gap of the bund. By this way, increased water pressure constituted by kinetic energy given from *Diyakalia* caused to increase the speed of water flow. When the difficulty of flowing the canal over the flat plains for 54 miles is taken into consideration, this extra pressure constituted by *Diyakalia* has been a good support to speed up of the flow. This is likewise structures made in modern canals.

Irrigation Water Management Aspect

There is no evidence to prove how *Diyakaliya* has been used for irrigation and water management. As *Diyakaliya* lies in higher elevation than the canal there is no possibility of carrying water for high ground beyond them, No extra canal or other technology has been used. But it is evident that *Diyakaliya* has been used for water supply for paddy fields located in the low land between the canal and the *Diyakalia*. The human settlement or villages located nearby it and people used it for domestic water purposes like drinking sanitation home grading and cattle feeding.

Fig.04: Sediment deposit process of Diyakaliya

Source: Field study

Maintaining of Soil Water Balance

Water relatively remains low than that of other zones. The main factor for this is the location of the bed rock. When constructing the *Yoda Ela* and positioning its irrigation devices and features, great care and attention has been paid to the maintaining of ground and soil water at a higher level. The most important factor that confirms and affirms this is the technology used for the construction of the *Diyakaliya* and its functioning. And working. As the state of balance between water and soil which are the two main factors needed for agricultural pursuits and activities is of vital importance for this, *Diyakaliya* can be introduced as an irrigation device or feature that performs this task very successfully and effectively. As the *Diyakaliya* is positioned in a plain valley at a higher altitude, it has a very close and constant connection and relationship with the bed rock. At the same time as there is a stable level of water being preserved, the circulation of soil-water too takes

place well. As a result of the ground being excavated deeply in the process of constructing the new Jaya Ganga (river), the level of the ground and soil water has dried up.

Fig.05 Ground water structural Functioning of Mahailuppallama Diyakaliya and Ancient Yodha

The main goal of constructing the Yoda Ela is to provide water to the human settlements found in the upper valley of the Kala Oya. As the altitude of the land is located towards the gradient or incline of Kala Oya, it has become quite a difficult task to provide water to the upper part of the land. In order to overcome this geographical difficulty, Kala Oya has been constructed across those valleys. The state of low level of water that exist of in this zone serves as a barrier for agricultural pursuits and such phenomena. As a remedy for this problem, the ancient irrigation technician had adopted two types of technological methods in the process of constructing the Yoda Ela i.e. enabling it to flow over the land and the Diyakaliya stretching across a large area of the upper zone of the Yoda Ela. Although water is provided to the lower tanks by the Yoda Ela, Diyakaliya provides water to the upper and lower land as groundwater.

Fig.06. Rough distribution of Mahailuppallama
Source: Field study

Fig. 07, According to slope menu level in Mahailuppallama
Source: Field study

Fig. 08, Levelling distribution and slope in Mahailuppallama
Source: Field study

According to the structural design, section indicated as E-F contributes to maintain the level of the ground water at a higher rate while A-E/C-D contributes to nurture and foster the level of the soil water. Maintaining the water level of E-F contributes to maintain the water level of A-E/ C-D at a definite rate, therefore, it has been of immensely helpful to build a very desirable and suitable zone for agricultural pursuits and activities.

Environmental Significance

Diyakaliya is an important feature that would help control the environmental evaporation and temperature, According to the geophysical setting and location of the North Central Province, it belongs to the Dry Zone resulting in a higher degree of evaporation and temperature. There are thorny shrubs and bushes and trees that can adapt and accommodate to this environmental condition. If the water level cannot remain the same due to evaporation, wilting and growth of trees will be hampered. Maintaining the humidity at a higher degree is the solution to this problem. As the water remains in the total area of the *Diyakaliya*, it has helped to maintain the humidity at a higher degree. As the evaporation becomes less, it has contributed to build an agricultural friendly environment.

The factors that influenced to position a *Diyakaliya* in the *Yoda Ela* have been found. Only the right bank of the *Yoda Ela* can be identified and the left bank has been made according to the slope of the land. Rain water that falls on to the upper land flows to the canal route from the right bank. This water is heavily mixed with sediments and as it is added to tanks or canal route makes a great the impact on the flow of water. Considering this situation, it is apparent that steps have been taken to build *Diyakaliya* in the areas with minimum longitudes where *Yoda Ela* flows. To maintain this *Diyakaliya* is considered an obligation of those who use water in those areas. In investigating the rules and regulations relevant to irrigation industry, old rules and regulations which were in force pertaining to maintenance of can be revealed. Accordingly, among the features of *Yoda Ela* irrigation technology, *Diyakaliya* serves as an important feature in water management and sustainable development in irrigation industry.

Engineering Aspect

Diyakaliya and its utility can be considered as a technological creation out of *Yoda Ela* irrigation industry. It is an irrigation feature which helps storing water, providing kinetic power for water to flow ahead, controlling the environmental temperature and evaporation, protecting moisture and controlling sediments brought by *Yoda Ela*. In order to confirm the quality of the research scope of this irrigation feature, both foreign and local research were taken use of. As there is limited research done on this subject, as a theoretical approach the book titled “Small Tank System of Sri Lanka: their Evaluation, Setting Distribution and Essential Functions” indicates that the pond built at the end of the canal is a strategy to collect sediments ^Panabokke, 2009&. In order to confirm the longitudes of *Diyakaliya* found in upper lands, the height of the real mean sea level of the *Mahaillupallama Diyakaliya* was calculated and its gap between the upper lands is 103-108 MSL and height of lower land is 98-93. Thus *Diyakaliya* was situated on an upper land. This location made an impact on the internal functioning of *Diyakajiya* and Tennakoon has pointed out that when water flows from upper tanks to lower tanks, water is filtered ^Tennakoon” 2005:40&. This is an approach to *Ellanga* system of tanks but the functioning and utility of *Diyakaliya* built being connected to *Yoda Ela* is investigated as

a more complex process. According to the Channel Morphology and typology experiment in 1992 has pointed out that when the slope and bends of the canal route increase, the stability of the canal route decrease resulting in the increase of sediments (Church, 1992). As Yoda Ela flows winding its way, depositing of sediments is on the increase. As *Diyakaliya* is built on a higher longitude, it was indicated that sediment gets collected easily. As Kellerhals points out in his study, the shape of the canal has a direct bearing for the sediment to deposit (Kellerhals et al, 1976). The scope of the research here falls within the double bank canal research. But the old *Yoda Ela* researched is a single bank canal. However, as the nature of the slope of the land on the right side performs the task of a canal or tank it is desirable to use the theoretical approach for this.

In building double bank canals, it has been pointed out that the shape and form and slope of the canal directly affects the depositing of sediment (Kellerhals et al, 1976; Church, 1992). As the single bank of old Yoda Ela involves a complex nature to this condition, depositing of sediment is very high compared with that of double bank canals i.e. the speed with which canal scale up a high land and flows down a low land and the fact that the right side of the canal serves as a catchment area will be greatly conducive for the depositing of sediment. As the right bank is slanted towards the area where the canal water flows and the rain water that falls on the upper land flows to the canal there is a high possibility of depositing a large heap of sediment in the canal. In order to prevent this condition, *Diyakaliya* has been positioned as a special irrigation feature in building *Yoda Ela*. Research has been done on the manner in which sediment gets deposited in canals or in tanks, but no study has been done on the alternative methods that should be taken. It can be pointed out that *Diyakaliya* positioned in the *Yoda Ela* in order to prevent the canal from being blocked by sediment is a method by which sediment can be collected to one place (Plan No. 01).

The biggest threat to irrigation industry is the functioning of sediment. The different remedies and solutions to this problem can be traced and confirmed through literary and archaeological sources and irrigation technician were able to control it through handling and dealing with landscapes. Dharmasena has drawn attention on how the functioning of sediment in rural tanks occurs and its resultant problems. The research on 'Magnitude of Sedimentation in village' shows that the amount of depositing sediment depends on the spatial arrangement of the area where the irrigation industry originated and three factors that affect this condition are also mentioned with the limitation of volume for water is collected the amount of sediment that gets deposited is on the rise. The effect of this condition irrigation industries is replete with sediment and water circulation will be inactive (Dharmasena, 1992). They are 1. less capacity for storing water, 2. Narrow surface on which water falls from upper land and stagnation of sediment caused by sluice gates and canal ways being blocked are which importance (Dharmasena, 1992:5-6). As a theoretical approach comparing conclusion of set experiment with the spatial arrangement of the *Yodha ela* and in managing the landscape of ancient *Yodha ela* irrigation industry attention has been paid to the above mentioned facts. As the right bank from which rain water falls is slightly slanted and remains as a catchment area of the *Yodha ela*. Its surface has a wider area. Accordingly upper land is subject to minimum erosion and the collecting of sediment is minimally controlled. It was pointed out that with the limited capacity for storing water the accumulation of sediment is on the rise. As a consequence of this condition, within relatively a short period the *yodha ela* irrigation Industry will be replete

with sediment and the water circulation will be inactive. *Yodha Ela* irrigation industry can be identified as a irrigation industry because due to the fact that *yodha Ela* performs a task of a long tank in addition to its normal work and due to rain water from upper land catchment area and water from *Kulu wewa* and *Olagan Wewa* and water from *kala wewa* get collected to *yodha Ela*, distribution of water throughout the year is done. According to the geophysical location of the canal although a high tendency of accumulation of sediment is indicated the construction technology and spatial arrangement have been made in order to control this condition. According to the structural design and irrigation features being positioned in the canal circulation of ground water and surface water for has been preparation. According in order to minimize the impact of sediment on the canal and sluice gates. Being fixed in lower contour in order to maintain water circulation process smoothly can be identified.

Fig. 08, Upper land and Lower land sluice gate of Yodha Ela
Source: Field study

As *Diyakaliya* has been positioned in higher contours and sluice gates have not been fixed, there is no alternative method to remove sediment being deposited. Therefore, removing the sediment is the responsibility of the people who use the water in the relevant part of the canal. It is mentioned in the *Samanthapasadhika* commentary on how to distribute water thus “..... this means from the common large pond (Could be a large tank) Digging a large canal common to all from this canal digging small canal and digging pit at the end of this. Canal for their personal use it is mentioned that the canal will be preserved during the time of water being taken (*Hewavitarana*” 1967:316). Accordingly it is the responsibility of the commonly to maintain the *Diyakaliya*.

Church and Jones who reveal that bank construction technology will impact on the controlling of sediment in the canal in their experiment “*Channel bars in gravel-bed rivers-in gravel Bar Rivers*” shows that bank construction technology and structural design of bank affect the controlling of the sediment in canal. Here four systems of bars have been introduced i.e 1. Longitudinal and Crescentic bars, 2. Transverse bars, 3. Media bars, 4. Diagonal bars, 5. Point of lateral bars (Church and Johes, 1982). It can be concluded that among these systems the *diyakaliya* connected to *Yodha ela* slanted to the left has been constructed according to the point of lateral bars or pointed of lateral bars. It has been clear that by fixing *Diyakaliya* slanted to the above lateral bars, the space has been arranged in such a way that the water mixed with sediment brought by the canal get collected and flows head.

It has not been emphasized through previous research on geographical features of the strategies used for deposition of sediment. Depositing sediment depends on the stagnation of deposits brought by water and *Diakaliya* is an important creation with a suitable landscape. Here, the *Diyakaliya* connected to the *Yoda Ela* is located in a higher land with a plain valley. *AluthWewa*, *Amunukolaya*, *Mahailuppallama* as places where *Diyakaliyas* are located by focusing on geographical features. Here, the *Diyakali* connected to the canal and inclined to the left is built at a slightly lower elevation. The landscape is adjusted so that the water that collects in the *Diyakaliya* rests and on depositing sediment the waters flows ahead (Plan No: 15). Fifteen such *Diyakali* can be identified in the *Yodha Ela* (canal). The mean sea level elevation analysis revealed that such irrigation elements may have influenced the geophysical and location area during the formation of the *Yodha Ela* (canal) (Fig.07).

Conclusion

Diyakaliya is a unique to the *Yodha Ela* canal irrigation industry that cannot be identified in other irrigation industries. Due to the structural nature of the canal, it maintains a high ground water level which is related to its operation. It performs a number of functions including, providing water for land cultivation, Evaporation control, providing water to the wild beats, Sediment control, Maintaining high level of ground water, obtaining the kinetic energy required for the canal to flow forward. Nearly 50 such water bodies can be identified in the *Yodha Ela* and they are connected to the *Mahailuppallama*, *Amunukolaya*, *Eppawala*, *Kuttikulama*, *Koon wewa*, *Kiralogama*, *Ihalawewa*, *Aluthwewa* tanks and other places where there are no water sources such as *Migessagama*, *Yakallegama*, *Puliyankulama*, *Medagama*, *Ihalagama*, *Getadiula*, *Kaduruwewa*, *Yakallegama*. It is clear that these irrigation features are designed with a broad understanding of environmental and water conservation.

References

- Awsadahami, U.B (2003), *Tank*, Hanguranketha; Siri Printers, P. 10-30.
- Awsadahami, U.B (2007), *Irrigation Heritage of Sri Lanka" Helagosa"* Colombo: Sesatha Publication" P.67-213-266.
- Awsadahami, U.B (2015), *Tank "A research done based on technology, Environment and Social economic View"* Boralessgamuwa: Pracheena Publication P.67-68,146-152.
- Bandaranayake, G.M. (2018), *Cascade Tank Systems and the Cultural Landscape of Sri Lanka"* Multi - Disciplinary Approach of Archaeology. eds. K.M. Alexsander, H. H. A. Karunarathna, Colombo: S.Godage and Son's' 26-29, pp.
- Brohier, R.L, (1934/1935), *Ancient Irrigation Works of Ceylon"* Volum III, Colombo: Government Press, Reprint Ministry of Mahaweli Development, 1996, Vol.1" 37 pp. vol 2, 42 pp vol.3, 69pp.
- Brohier, R.L. (1937), *The Inter Relation of Groups of Ancient of Reservoirs and Channels in Ceylon"* Journal of Royal Asiatic Society, Colombo: Published by Royal Asiatic Society' 64-85 pp.
- Church, M., Jones, D. (1982), *Channel bars in gravel-bed rivers. In: Gravel-bed rivers"* R.D. hey, J.C. bathurst and Sons, UK: Chichester, O.K. Wiley, chichester, 291-324 Pp.

- Church, M. (1992), *Channel morphology and Typology in:the river handbook: hydrological and ecological principles*” P. Calow and G. E. Petts. eds. Black well Scientific Publication, 126-143. Pp.
- Cooray, P.G. (1967), *The Geology of Ceylon*, Colombo: Government print’ 54. p
- Cooray, P.G. (1984), *The Geology of Sri Lanka*” (Ceylon). 2nd eds. Colombo: National Museum Publication’ 24-124. pp.
- Deraniyagala.S., (1992), *The Prehistory of Sri Lanka: an Ecological Perspective*, Archaeological Survey Department, Colombo.
- Dharmasena” P.B. (1992), *Magnitude of Sedimentation in Village tanks (1992)*, (Online), Trop. Agric Dep.of Agric, Peradeniya, Sri Lanka. Available from: <http://www.independent.edu> 148.97 (Accessed 11/02.05.18).
- Dharmasena, P.B. (2005)” *Traditional Village tank System For Conservation and Effective Use of Water*” (Online), Paper Presented at the International Seminar on “Management of Large–Scale Irrigation System For Better Conservation and Use of Water Resource September of 2005, 12-17 pp. Available from: <http://www.independent.edu> (Accessed 02.05.18).
- Horocks, N.K. (1976). *Physical geography and climatology, Colombo. M, D Gunasena and Company, P.50.*
- Hydraul. div. Am. Soc. Civil engi-102 813-829.15-16. Pp.
- Karunarathna, H.H.A.; Kapukotuwa, K.M and Ranasingha, G. (2018). *A study about water management of Ancient Yodha ela in Anuradhapura*. 3rd National Buddhist conference, Bhiksu University of Sri lanka. P.163-169.
- Karunarathna, H. H.A., Alexander, K. M. (2018), *A study an Irrigation Techniques of the Ancient Yoda ela in Anuradhapura*, International Conference on Multidisciplinary Approach 2018, Post Graduate Studies, Colombo: University of Sri Jayewardenepura’ 104,P.31/09/2018.
- Kellerhals, R.M. Church, D.I Bray. (1976), *Classification and Analysis of River Processes*, J.
- Nicholas, C.R. (1959), *History of Ceylon*, vol.I’ Chapter 6 and 8 on Irrigation and Agriculture. Colombo: University of Peradeniya’ 75 Pp.
- Panabokke, C.R. (1999), *The Small Tank Cascades Systems of Rajarata, their Setting, Distribution and Hydrography*, Colombo: International Water management Institute’ 39. P.
- Panabokke, C.R. (2009), *Small Village Tank Systems of Sri Lanka:Their Evolution, Setting, Distribution and Essential Functions*” Colombo: Hector Kobbekaduwa Agrarian Research and Training Institute.
- Panapitiya, M. (2010). *Stark reality behind the engineering design and planning of Irrigation project Development in the past Century, Economic discussion (2010)*. (2010 April- May) Colombo: Ministry of Economic, P1-10.
- Parker, H. (1909). *Ancient Ceylon*, New Delhi: Asian Educational Service Indian Office.
- Samantapasadika*. (1924-1927), eds. J. Takakusu and M. Nagai. London: Published by Pali Text Society.
- Tennakoon, M.U.A. (2004), *Tank are not Meno Functional They are Multi- Functional Symposium on small tank Settlements In Sri Lanka*, held in August’ 2004 Under The Auspicious, Colombo: The Hector Kobbekaduwa agrarian research and Training Institute’ 5 P.
- Wjethunga, S. (2005). *Water Supply and water resource management*, Published by Sarasavi, P.15-40

In the sea of influence, a world system perspective of the Sri Lankan sea ports (period from the eleventh to the fifteenth century AD)

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Abstract:

This research focuses on how trade and economic activity in the Indian Ocean has affected Sri Lanka. In that case, it is not possible to conduct research on Sri Lanka as a single country, as it is related to the functioning of the entire Indian Ocean in the international arena of the trade economy. Also, the world system analyzes that have been published so far on the trade economy of the Indian Ocean have been presented by external researchers and Sri Lanka is automatically included in the systematic analysis of all these researchers. However, as mentioned above, based on the research conducted on Sri Lanka in relation to the impact of trade activities in the entire Indian Ocean on Sri Lanka (Kekulawala, 2017). We hope to explain this research paper in relation to Sri Lankan marine ports from 11th to 15th century A.D. Historical and archaeological evidence reveals that Sri Lankan ports became more active during this period and established trade relations with China, Southeast Asia, India and the Arabian Sea. However, the study of pre-research world systems show that the developed areas of the Indian Ocean have changed over time. The importance of Sri Lankan ports in each period was assessed based on the demand and supply of raw materials, climate change in the Indian Ocean, and hegemonic changes. From the 11th to 15th century, changes in the functioning of Sri Lankan seaports took place due to changes in the overall global economic flow (Kekulawala, 2017). Accordingly, this research paper focuses on identifying the major world systems operating in the Indian Ocean during the relevant period.

Keywords- *Hegemony, world system, seaports, Bay of Bengal, Arabic Sea.*

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Introduction

World System Theory

This article will focus on Sri Lankan contribution to the functioning of the world system and its interpretation of the nature of inter-social relations developing on an economic basis in the Indian Ocean. The Research Question is how many developed areas in the Indian Ocean were important for the functioning of Sri Lankan trade relations from 11th to 15th centuries A.D.? Wallerstein is considered the founder of the world system. In 1974, he analyzed theoretical ideas under the modern world systems that could be used to describe the structures of transatlantic reactions that took place between distant nations in the Indian Ocean. After 1500 AD, he was able to present a new perspective on the world economy based on world capitalism and the division of labor around Europe (Wallerstein, 1974). Gills and Frank also point out that the history of world systems in 1991 and 1993 goes back to the third millennium BC (Gills and Frank 1991; Frank and Gills 1993, 2000). Gills has made a concerted effort to summarize the developmental conditions represented by world systems into three main frameworks (Gills, 1993) of such as cycles, crises, and hegemonic shifts. Explaining the political changes in different states, Gills pointed out that the socio - economic rhythms generated by the competition in world systems reflect the changes in each socio - economic sphere and resource. He further attempted to show that it is more justifiable to understand the functioning of the ancient world as a mere interaction between systems (Gills 1993).

Wallerstein's world systems are divided into three sub-regions, where the entire economy is divided into core, semi and periphery. Here the goods and services of the peripheral area reach the central region through the semi-peripheral areas (Wallerstein, 1974: 406-415) (Map 1). But one could argue that Wallerstein's theory dates back to the 15th century AD. According to Wallerstein, European capitalism originated about 500 years before the 15th century AD, with the decline of the feudal system (Shannon, 1996: 25). In here Sri Lanka is pointed out as a peripheral region. The 12th-century map of Wallerstein presented by Wallerstein illustrates that urban growth in Europe was not a one-time event, but the result of a long-running process (see Kekulawala, 2017). The map systematically shows population growth and their concentration around cities, further indicating that population growth is a major factor in measuring demand for goods. Accordingly, the period discussed in this research paper includes Wallerstein's hypothesis of the 11th-15th centuries AD. However, Braudel comments on capitalism further, pointing out that capitalism was growing in Europe by the 11th century AD. It reads,

“Innovation cities of the middle ages old strained to make profits and were shaped by the strain. Contemporary capitalism has invented nothing. By at least the twelfth century. everything seems to have been there in embryo... .. bills of exchange, credit, minted coins, banks, forward selling, Public Finance, loans, capitalism, colonialism- as well as social disturbances, sophisticated labor force,

class struggles, social oppression , political atrocities (Braudel, 1984) in Frank & Gills 2000: 17 ”.

In 1989, Abu Lughod cited Wallerstein’s criteria to describe the world systems of the book “Before the European Hegemony” (Singh, 2003). Abu Lughod’s hypothesis here is that the 13th century AD was a turning point in world history. She further points out the systematic relationship between China and Northwestern Europe as the best time for the international world economy this century (Lughod, 1989: 64). Her hypothesis about the inclusion of Sri Lanka in the two systemic regions of the Arabian Sea and the Bay of Bengal should be considered here (Map. 2).

Map 1- Wallerstein’s World-Systems Theory (Wallerstein, 1974)

Chaudhuri’s systematic analysis of the Indian Ocean trade civilization from the beginning of Islam to the 1750 A.D. (Chaudhuri, 1985) should be examined here. Thus, Chaudhuri presents a trilogy of major systems that further show the change in these regions along the Arabian Sea, the Bay of Bengal and the China Sea. In this analysis of the systems, Sri Lanka has been included at one time in the Bay of Bengal region and at other times in the Arabian Sea region, but a comprehensive description of Sri Lanka is required.

Map, 2 the 13th century world-system

Map based on Janet Abu-Lughod’s work (Lughod, 1989)

The above systems analysis emphasizes that the political dominance of Asia, the way in which the demand and supply of independent cities in Central Asia are functional, and environmental factors have influenced world systems operating in the Indian Ocean in the past. However, it is important to note that Sri Lanka, an island nation in the Indian Ocean, has been deeply concerned about the use of external factors operating in the Indian Ocean to shape its economic and political context. The relocation of the capital to Polonnaruwa and from there to Kotte, and the increasing importance of ports in each period, should be investigated as to whether external factors in the Indian Ocean were more active than internal factors. It is necessary to look in depth at what happened in the Indian Ocean and its suburbs from the 11th century to the 15th century outside Sri Lanka. It is important to focus on the developed nature and trade relations of Sri Lanka's coastal ports.

Result and Discussion

Evidence of Sri Lanka's naval ports adapting to trade activities in the Indian Ocean has been found since ancient times. The Sri Lankan port was an ideal hub for ships sailing through the monsoon winds in the Indian Ocean. The period relevant to this research paper, from the 12th to the 15th century AD, has been found to be important in the naval port of Sri Lanka in the trade between the East and the West. Examples of this can be found in local literature sources, foreign records, inscriptions and archaeological excavations.

The ports of Ceylon have been involved in trade in the Indian Ocean since prehistoric times. Archaeological excavations at Manthai by Carswell and Prickett in 1984, especially with the discovery of a Nestorian cross from the Sasanian period (224-651 AD) and a Persian inscription, further confirm its significance (Carswell and Prickett, 1984). The port was an ideal place for ships sailing across the Arabian Sea on monsoon winds. Islamic ceramics found in Manthai date back to the middle Ages. According to Tempoe (Tempoe, 1989, 100), these are similar to those found at Shiraf and Sohar ports of Arabian sea. Excavations at the port have also uncovered fragments of glassware dating back to the early Middle Ages (Ibid). But our hypothesis shows that there is little evidence of Arabic ceramics at the port since the 11th century AD. The items found are kept in the Archaeological Museums in Anuradhapura, Yapahuwa, Galle and Buduruwagala. Prickett points out that the northwestern Manthai port in Ceylon was temporarily used by the middle of the 11th century AD (Prickett, 1980, 22). But based on these facts, one cannot argue that Arab trade relations with this port did not exist from the eleventh century to the thirteenth century. After the 11th century AD, there is ample evidence that Arab traders engaged in trade with ports such as Chilaw, Negombo and Colombo on the west coast of Sri Lanka, as well as ports on the east and south coasts of Sri Lanka. According to Yamamoto, most of the Chinese ceramics dated to Manthai date back to the 9th and 10th centuries AD (Yamamoto, 2004: 61).

The ceramics found in the Alahana Pirivena are clear examples of the development of trade relations along the eastern ports of Sri Lanka. By the 11th century AD, trade relations between Sri Lanka and China had developed, as evidenced by the large number of Chinese ceramics found at the Alahana Pirivena. A comparative study of Chinese ceramics found in Alahana Pirivena with Chinese ceramics found in Anuradhapura explains that the ceramics found in Polonnaruwa are significantly more unique than the ceramics found in Anuradhapura (Prematilleke, 1990: 235). All but a few items of Islamic artefacts found at the Alahana Pirivena site have been identified as Chinese ceramic pots. This monastery complex belongs to the 12th century AD and belongs to the reign of Parakramabahu the Great (1153-1186 AD). It is very clear that these goods were brought to Polonnaruwa, the second capital of Sri Lanka, through the Eastern Maritime Ports of Sri Lanka.

A study of the naval ports pointed out to the Lankathilaka Inscription (Paranavitana, 1960: 16-26), which dates back to the third year of the reign of King Bhuvanekaba IV (1272-1284 AD) during the period when the Gampola Kingdom was the capital of Sri Lanka. This article mentions a donation made by the Merchant Society for the construction of the Lankathilaka Temple. Accordingly, this article contains the importation of goods from 18 countries through nine ports in Sri Lanka (ibid). This commodity circulates in the country through *thavalam* and returns lightly from the ports. Import or export commodities were taxed according to their value and clear information on how an interchange trade network was revealed. This reveals how Sri Lanka maintained trade relations with many parts of the Indian Ocean by the 13th century AD. In addition, the terms *Velupura* (ports), *Pattanana* (coastal area) and *Katikait-tavalam* in Sri Lankan Tamil inscriptions illustrate the relationship with the international market. For example, all three verses are mentioned in the Viharahinna Inscription (Karashima, 2002:249).

“The eulogy of the Viharahinna inscription states that possessed 500 charters called *Vira-Sasana*, were brave, who are adorned by Lakshmi.....eighteen *Pattanam* (costal area), thirty- two *velapura* (ports) and 64 *katikait-tavalam*”.

This inscription is dated to 1150 A.D., it was clear that Sri Lanka was a very famous trading hub for international trade. There is no doubt that this situation developed and functioned in parallel when the Lankathilaka inscription was written in the 13th century. Here we need to emphasize with which areas the Indian Ocean trade relations took place.

Manthai, Gokanna, Vankalai and Uraturei or Kayts are some of the unique ports located in the northwestern and Eastn Coast of Sri Lanka. Literary sources of the medieval period also mention the ports of *Gotapabbatha*, *Dondra*, *Nilwala Thitta (Matarata)*, *Mahavalukagama* (Weligama), *Gimha thiththa* (Gintota), *Bhimatiththa* (Bentota) and *Kalathitta* (Kalutara). The Deduru Oya is easily connected to the Chilaw port on the west coast of Sri Lanka. That is why the Deduru Oya is so significant in making connections with the *Dakkinadesa*. The period from the 13th to the 15th century AD is important for the trade economy of the kingdoms of Dambadeniya, Yapahuwa, Kurunegala and Gampola,

the capitals of Ceylon. This was due to the expansion of trade in the Arabian Sea after the 13th century AD. Waththala, Kaluthota, Beruwala, Colombo, Bentota, Dondra and Panadura ports are important here. The Culavamsa describes all the ports in Sri Lanka (except the Bentota port) from the *Kalathitta* (Kalutara) port to *Mahanagahula* present day Ambalantota (Cv LXXX: 80-81).

The Nikaya Sangrahaya mentions that the port of Madupadatittha was important by the 13th century AD (Nikaya Sangrahaya, 23). Nicholas points out that this is now known as Ilupakadavai (Nicholas, 1990: 81). But it is difficult to identify some of the ports mentioned in the chronicles, such as *Manthikaratittha*, *Pulachcheri*, *Balatittha*, *Debarapatan* (Mv: LX: 34; LXXXIII, 17; Pujavaliya, 34-511). There is another port called Pallavanka in the northeastern part of Sri Lanka, which was named Codrington (Codrington, 1939:69). With the selection of Polonnaruwa as the capital by the rulers of Sri Lanka, the importance of the eastern and northeastern ports increased as a developed trade network centered on South Asia and Asia around the Bay of Bengal. For example, the value of the Gokanna may have been particularly important in the Bay of Bengal trade. The Mahaweli River in Sri Lanka flows into the sea from Gokanna or Trincomalee. The Hattavanagalla Viharavamsa (Hattavanagalla Viharavamsa 78) mentions thousands of Chola, Kerala and other hostile people living in Pulasthipura. Silva is of the opinion that the Chola king made connection the port of Gokanna as his eastern port in his trade (Silva, 1959-1973:112).

There is evidence that the Weligama also developed into a very important trading center by the 12th century. Accordingly, traders have arrived at the Mahawalukagama (Weligama). For the convenience of traders traveling in the Indian Ocean, the port on the southern coast of Sri Lanka may have been used for accommodation as well as for the purchase and exchange of merchandise. Mostly Southeast Asian, Chinese and Indian traders have used this port to navigate around Sri Lanka and enter the Arabian Sea. Ships coming from the east of the Indian Ocean through the Nicobar Islands, the natural harbor on the southern coast of Sri Lanka was an ideal stop for entry into the western Indian Ocean. In particular, it is clear that the location of the Kushtarajagala statue near the Weligama port was based on trade relations. South and Southeast Asia is important as an area where the Mahayana Dhamma was prevalent. Accordingly, the Weligama port was maintained as a place of attraction for traders from the East Indian Ocean to the west of the Indian Ocean. According to the Kalyani inscription, a ship sent to Sri Lanka by King Bames arrived at Weligama (Buddadatta 1959: 23). According to the Thisara Sandeshaya, Paravi Sandeshaya and Kokila Sandeshaya poems, Weligama was a very prosperous port by the 15th century AD (Thisara Sandeshaya, V.43; Paravi Sandeshaya, 103-104; Kokila Sandesaya, 55-57).

By the beginning of the 13th century AD, the ports of Wattala, Negombo, Puttalam and Chilaw were important for maritime trade. The port of Chilaw is said to have been a shipyard in the 12th century AD, and Paronavitana describes how the Cholas docked at the port of Chilaw based on a story from the Mahavamsa (Paronavitana, 1929:385).

Dambadeni Asna indicates that foreigners were staying at this port (Dambadeni Asna: 62). According to the Nikaya Sangraha, in the middle of the 14th century AD, the Aryan Chakravarty made temporary accommodation at Colombo, Wattala, Negombo, Puttalam and Chilaw (Nikaya Sangrahaya, 36). Ibn Battuta's report also gives clear information about some of these ports. When Battuta arrived in Sri Lanka, he accidentally landed at the port of Battala. At that time the houses of the Aryan emperors could be seen. After his ship arrived at the port, the sailors were reluctant to land there. At the time of Battuta's arrival, Aryan Chakravarty was examining pearl diving resources (Ibn Battuta, Vol. IV, 79). By the 13th century AD, the development of the Arabian Sea region, the Persian Gulf, the Red Sea, and the developed eastern coastal areas of Africa may have contributed to the development of the South-western, western, and north-western ports of Sri Lanka.

Urathota or Kayts port can be identified as a place where Arab trade took place in the past. The Nainativu Tamil inscription, written in the Dravidian language by King Parakramabahu the Great (1153-1186 AD), describes how the cargo ships arrived at the port of Urathota (Indrapala, 1963:63). These merchant ships come from the Arabian Sea and are the best evidence of the progress of the elephant and horse trade during this period. The inscription location at the port facing the Arabian Sea indicates the connection between the western and north-western ports of India and the northern ports of Sri Lanka.

By this time, not only were merchants of various nationalities involved in the administration of Sri Lanka, but it is clear that this international trade was controlled by the King of Sri Lanka. Among these are important facts about the Arabs. The Culavamsa mentions that King Parakramabahu I (1153-1186 AD) ordered the ministers to make chiefs for the *Vessa* and *Yavana* (Cv:76: 264). Also, King Javaka invaded Sri Lanka twice in the 13th century AD for economic as well as religious purposes. He is from Tamralingaya or Malay Peninsula. However, the book *Yalpana Vaipava Malai* shows that under the then king Vijayabahu I (1055-1110) the *Yavakar* army lived on a salary from the king (*Yalpana Vaipava Malai*, 33). It is clear that the ruler of Sri Lanka has made a huge income from these trades. This revenue was derived not only from coastal ports but also from inland trade (Paranavitana, 1960:16-26). The discovery of a part of an inscription in Arabic dating to the 13th century AD on a rock reveals further evidence that Muslims lived in the area. This inscription mentions a blessing from an Arab scholar. Sri Pada, located in a gem-rich region of Sri Lanka, had become Muslims attraction area at that time (Alexander Johnstone, Vol.I:Part, I).

There is information about Colombo, a very important port facing the Arabian Sea by the 11th century AD. The location of this port was important for the accommodation of ships during the monsoon winds in the Indian Ocean. According to Nicholas, by the 10th century AD, Colombo had become a Muslim-dominated place (Nicholas, 1959:121). Ibn Battuta reports that Kolomthota is one of the best cities in Serendib. Five hundred Abyssinians served here under a ruler known as Jalasthi (Ibn Battuta, 223-224). Abyssinians are slaves in Africa who are involved in cargo loading and unloading. It means that they were participating in trade activities in the Indian Ocean. Ibn Battuta called the

ruler Jalasthi “Prince of the sea”. By this time the Muslims had reached to Colombo and built their warehouses here (Silva, 1951:22). Accordingly, Colombo or Kolomthota can be pointed out as another port for exchanging commodities to the western Indian Ocean or the Arabian Sea. It is revealed that Beruwala was another port where Muslims occupied. According to Sandesha poems, Beruwala is known as a Muslim trading center and a destination for foreign ships. The narrator describes “*Baburun*” as an Arab woman living in this city (GS, V.104, 105). The narrator describes ‘Baburun’ as an Arab woman living in this city (G.S.V.104, 105). Dambadeniya Asna refers to “*Barbaran*” (DA 34). Kokila and Gira Sandesha point to the Muslim women *Yonliyan* and the Mahavaligama inhabited by Muslim settlers (K.S., V 59 and G.S., V.104). Also, the Trilingual inscription in Galle, written in Persian in the 15th century AD, shows the Muslims who traded at this port (EZ Vol.III: No.36). The linguistic trilogy mentioned in the inscription further indicates that the port was a frequent haunt of Chinese, Muslim and South Indian merchants by the 15th century AD.

Conclusion

Based on the data obtained from the study of pre-systems and relations with the ports of Sri Lanka, the analysis confirms that Sri Lankan economic relations with the two major systemic regions of the Indian Ocean were active from 11th to 15th century AD. The first is the Bay of Bengal, which includes eastern and southern India, Burma, Thailand, Cambodia, Malaya, Java and Sumatra. The other region is the area centered on the Arabian Sea. After the 13th century, a large trade network was created, especially around the Arabian Sea. These include the Persian Gulf, the Red Sea, the north-western and western parts of India, and the eastern parts of Africa. We acknowledge that the shift of the capital to Polonnaruwa by the 11th century AD and the shift of the capitals to the southwest by the beginning of the 13th century centered on these two main world systems. Thus, the two systems can be identified on the map (Map 3).

Map 3 - Systems determining the economic and political background of Sri Lanka (11th to 15th century AD) (Kekulawala 2017)

References

- Braudel, Fernand. (1984). *Civilization and Capitalism, 15th-18th century*, New York:Harper & Row, Vol. III.
- Braudel, Fernand. (1996). *Mediterranean World in the Age of Philip ii*, Vol.I, Second Edition, Fontana Press.
- Buddhadatta, Polwathte. (1959). *Itha Parani Sinhala Bana Katha (in Sinhala)*, Rathna poth Pub. Colombo.
- Carswell, J ; Prickett, M.(1984). *The Excavation of Mantai 1980: A Preliminary Investigation*, Ancient Ceylon, Vol.V:3-80.
- Codrington, H.W. (1919). *A Sinhalese Embassy to Egypt*, Journal of Royal Asiatic Society Ceylon Branch, Vol.XXVIII, No.72: 82-85.
- Chaudhuri, K.N. (1985). *Trade and Civilization in the Indian Ocean, an Economic History from the rise of Islam to 1750*, Munshirama Publication.
- Culavamsa* (Cv.). (1925). Geiger, W., Vol.I, Oxford University Press.
- Culavamsa* (Cv.). (1927). Geiger, W., Vol.II, Oxford University Press.
- Dambadeni Asna (DA.). (1928).ed. D.D. Ranasinghe, Colombo.
- Frank, A.G; Gills, B.K. (1993).*The World System five hundred years or five thousand*, London and New York.
- Frank, A.G., and Gills, B.K. (2000). *The five Thousand Year World System in theory and praxis*, Denmark.
- Gira Sandeshaya* (GS.). (1949). Wijesekera,N.D., Printed and Published by Asoka Press, Colombo.
- Ibn Battuta. (1858). *Sanguinetti*, B.R., (tra) Ibn Battûta, Voyages d' Ibn Battuta, Vol. IV, Paris.
- Indrapala,K. (1963).*The Nainative Tamil Inscription of Parakramabahu I*, University of Ceylon Review, Vol. XXI, No.I: 63-70.
- Kekulawala, Nayomi. (2017). *Sri Lanka and the Indian Ocean special reference to Sri Lanka (from 11th to 15th Century AD)*, unpublished thesis.
- Kokila Sandesaya* (KS.). (1962). Gunawardhane, W.S., Mahabodhi Publication, Colombo.
- Lughod, Janet Abu. (1989). *Before European hegemony: the world system A.D. 1250-1350*, New York, Oxford University Press.
- Mahavamsa* (Mv.). (1912). Geiger, W., 1912(tra.), London.
- Nikaya Sangrahaya* (NS.). (1997). Buddhist Cultural Center, Dehivala.
- Paranavitana, S. (1933). *Tamil Inscription Gall Trilingual Slab*, Epigraphia Zeylanica, Vol.III, 270-277.
- Paranavitana, S. (1960). *Lankatilaka Inscriptions*, University of Ceylon Review, Vol.XVIII, No.I and 2:16-26.
- Paravi Sandesaya* (PS.). (1915). Munidasa, Kumaratunga, Colombo.
- Prematililleke,P.L.(1892) (2000). *Chinese Ceramics discovered in Sri Lanka, Sri Lanka and the Silk Road of the Sea*, ed. Senake Bandaranayake, Lona Dewaraja,Roland Silva and K.D.G.Wimalaratne,UNESCO and CCF:61-65.

- Pujavaliya*, (1998). Suraweera, A.V., Abeyawardene, H.A.P., and Patirana, H., Sri Lanka National Library, Colombo 7.
- Silva, De, K.M; Ray, C.M. (1959-1973), *History of Ceylon*, Colombo.
- Tempo, Moria. (1989). *Maritime Trade between China and the West, An Archaeological Study of the Ceramics from Siraf (Persian Gulf) 8th to 15th Centuries A.D.*, Great Britain.
- Shannon, T.R. (1996). *An Introduction to the World System perspective*, Colorado, USA.
- Singh, S.J. (2001). *Social Metabolism and Labour in a Local Context: Changing Environmental Relations on Trinket Island*. In *Population and Environment* 2 (1), 71-104.
- Wallerstein, Immanuel. (1974). *The Modern World-System: Capitalist Agriculture and the Origins of the European World-Economy in the Sixteenth Century*. New York: Academic Press.
- Yamamoto, N. (2004). *Periyapattinam/Nagapattinam/Devipattanam/Kayal/Kulasekarapattanam/Madurai Government Museum, In Search of Chinese Ceramic Sherds South India and Sri Lanka*, ed. Noboru Karashima, Taisho University Press, Japan: 22-27.

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Abstract:

Indigenous knowledge (IK) is a set of knowledge belong to a specific group or a community which cannot be seen either in the mainstream or in a dominant society. The knowledge systems developed by the ancestors of these groups have transmitted this knowledge system to their succeeding generations. This knowledge system has shaped their traditional way of life and culture throughout the history. Meemure inhabitants are one of the minority groups in Sri Lanka that have remarkable indigenous knowledge system (IKS). The main objective of this study was to explore their valuable IKS as a whole. Thus, questioner survey, interviews and observation methods were used as data collecting methods. Though the village cultural heritage is rich in precious indigenous pertaining tangible and intangible cultural heritage those are at risk of disappearing at present with the effects of new technologies and innovations. Capturing these IK as much as we can and making documents, films and ethnographies are the best methods to safeguard this invaluable indigenous heritage.

Keywords: *Meemure Village, Traditional Medicine, Traditional Foods, Indigenous Knowledge, Sri Lanka*

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1. Introduction

Indigenous knowledge systems (IKS) have defined by Julian T. Inglis (Executive Director of the International Program on Traditional Ecological Knowledge in 1993), as a “set of knowledge includes an intimate and detailed knowledge of plants, animals, and natural phenomena, the development and use of appropriate technologies for hunting, fishing, trapping, agriculture, and forestry, and a holistic knowledge, or “world view” which parallels the scientific discipline of ecology” (Miraglia, 1998). Similarly, Mistry (2009) stated that it is spatial and/or cultural context and as a specific, collective, and adaptive system of knowledge (Mistry, 2009). The holistic nature of the IK highlights the idea of its inclusion of the knowledge (both tangible and intangible in nature) of all aspects related to the lifestyle of a particular group of people (those who have unique knowledge systems) (Kottak, 2012; Campbell, 2006). UNESCO has given priority to preservation, protection and collection of IK and has defined it as “Local and indigenous knowledge refers to the understandings, skills and philosophies developed by societies with long histories of interaction with their natural surroundings” (Anon., 2017). Its Local and Indigenous Knowledge Systems (LINKS) program works to secure an active and equitable role for local communities in resource management; to strengthen knowledge transmission across and within generations; to explore pathways to balance community-based knowledge with global knowledge in formal and non-formal education; to support the meaningful inclusion of local and indigenous knowledge in biodiversity conservation and management (Anon., 2017). Therefore, at present the knowledge system of the local/traditional or indigenous groups has given special attention internationally and nationally. Even though it was previously ignored in the fields of development and conservation, currently its being incorporated into development projects as an essential factor (Mistry, 2009). However, there are many issues surrounding the recording of indigenous knowledge and its transference to other localities and contexts (Mistry, 2009).

IK has been evolved among groups/communities according to the geographic areas they live. Specially environment and culture affect the development of specific IK. To continue the transmission and growth of the IK that are owned by specific cultures/groups of people, the next generations should acquire and accept this knowledge system. Otherwise, it will be remained only among the older generations of the cultures/groups and will be disappeared without transmitting for tomorrow’s world (Barnouw, 1982).

Sri Lanka, located on an island near India, is a multi-ethnic, multi-religious country with a majority Sinhalese Buddhist ethnic population (75%). Among around 10 of the other ethnic groups that reside in the country, 11% are Sri Lankan Tamils and 9.2% are Sri Lankan Muslims; these are the second and third most prominent ethnic groups (Department of Census and Statistics 2012; Sri Lanka Demographics Profile 2019). Even though the Vedda people of the country represent only 0.05% of the country’s population, they are considered to be one of the unique Indigenous groups with a specific cultural identity (Silva & Punchihewa 2011; Department of Census and Statistics 2012; Ananda 2019). The island of Sri Lanka is exclusive in its topography since this distinctiveness

has given birth to various colorful, precious communities which are holding specific indigenous knowledge systems that cannot be found from anywhere else. Especially all the mentioned populations/groups own specific IK that can be considered as a treasure that should be revealed and preserved for future generations. Some of the subcultures under these main ethnic/religious groups have been formed as long-term geographical isolation. Those consist of unique cultures/IKs that are different and rich when compared with the IK of the prominent/dominant cultural system.

Meemure inhabitants are one such community that holds distinctive IK. They are Sinhalese Buddhists that have been living isolate (with minimum contact) from the dominant Sinhalese over hundreds of years. The name Meemure is said to be formed by the “*Mee trees*” (*Madhuca longifolia*) that can be seen around the Meemure area (English- “Honey Tree”). According to folklore “*honey*” that could have collected from the Meemure area had been another reason for the name Meemure. Sinhala term for honey – “*pani*” or “*mee*” has derived from the name Meemure. Besides the terms “*Mihi*” + “*Mure*” have been known to be formed as Meemure; the meaning is protecting the earth. Meemure Village is located in Sri Lanka’s mountainous and thickly forested interior. This mountain region has been described in the chronicles as “*Girimandala*”, “*Malaya Ratta*” or as “*Malaya desha*” (Ariyapala, 1969). It is mentioned in the first map of “*Taprobane*” by “*Claudius Ptolemy*” as “*Maleamount*” (Thomas, 1999). Sinhalese residents have traditionally referred to the area as *Dumbara Kanduvetiya* meaning mist-laden mountain range. Early British surveyors had assigned the name “*Knuckles*” to the mountain range because of the resembling shape of “*knuckle*” when viewed from certain locations in the Kandy District. The vast mountain range consists of 34 peaks in total such as “*Gombaniya*” (6248Ft), “*Knuckles*” (6112Ft), “*Dumbanagala*” (5339Ft), “*Kalupahana*” (5300Ft), “*Dothalugala*” (5164Ft), “*Lakegala*” (4324Ft) (Goonewardene, et al., 2006; Rajapaksha, 2007, Ananda & Nahallage 2014). Though the Meemure village is situated in the middle of this mountain range, the majority of the Meemure prehistory have built based on the mythical stories that have connected with “*Lakegala*” Mountain. “*Lakegala*” is a giant monolith-like projection at 1 km north of the Meemure village with an almost 90-degree angle. In ancient times this rock was known as “*Lanka Pabbata*” or “*Lankagiri*”, “*The Rock of Lanka*” is the meaning of “*Lakegala*” in the Sinhala language. Meemure people believe that the name ‘*Lanka*’ is derived based on the term “*lakegala*” (Lokubandara, 1959).

Further, the village is famous for its legendary stories related to King *Rawana* and for the unique cultural heritage it has. *Lakegala* Mountain situated in the corner of the Meemure village said to be King *Rawana*’s kingdom and the place prince *Sitha* was hidden. Prince *Rama* had come to the Meemure region to seek Prince *Sitha* (according to the folk tales of Meemure inhabitants). Although these legends revealed to us about King *Rawana* and his *yaksha* tribe, Meemure village had been habituated by people in the era of King *Wimaladharmasuriya I* (1542-1604). *Vedda* named *Beduruwa* was the first owner of the Meemure village and then cousins; *Herath Hami* and *Riti Hami* had moved to Meemure village with their families from *Poddalgoda* (Village in the Kandy District).

Henceforth they have adapted to the physical environment and have gradually developed their invaluable cultural heritage. The indigenous knowledge they own have accumulated throughout history, shows significant characteristics. Their agrarian lifestyle has been dependent on both paddy and Chena cultivation (Ananda & Nahallage 2014). There were no chemical toxins in their diets or water; the village was abundant with fresh vegetables and fruits. The only illness they acquire is tiredness resulting after hard agricultural works. For that, they had enough of popular medicines (*Ath beheth*) in their gardens. If they suspect that the illness is a result of a supernatural being, they have their powerful village deities to whom they pray for a cure. This simple and successful way of life is a consequence of their valuable indigenous knowledge system (traditional knowledge/ folk wisdom). Therefore, the main objective of this research was to study their remarkable indigenous knowledge system and to make ethnography a preservation method for tomorrow's world.

2. Methodology

2.1 Study Area

Meemure Village is situated in the Central Province, in Kandy District [N 07.433330 and E 08.833330] (Meemure, 2013). It belongs to Ududumbara Secretariat Division and Meemure Grama Niladari Division [Fig.1]. From Colombo to Kandy there are 115 km, Kandy to *Hunnasgiriya* 75 km. To reach Meemure village from *Hunnasgiriya*, one must go another 38 km. Both electricity and sufficient transporting facilities are absent to Meemure village.

Figure 1: Location of the Meemure village: A Kandy District, B Ududumbara Secretariat Division, C Meemure Grama Niladari Division (In Red Colour) Maps were collected by researcher from the Meemure GN Office records and edited.

2.2 Data Collection

The total population in Meemure Grama Niladari Division according to the census in 2011 consists of 331 people belonging to 115 families (primary data collection report 2011: *Ududumbara*). Out of this, forty families (40) were randomly selected and gathered information via a questionnaire (One member from each family belongs to Meemure village from the distant past). Thirty-five percent (35%) of the informants who participated in the questionnaire survey were females and 65% of them were males (14-Female, 26-Male). Their age ranges from 23 to 75 years. In-depth interviews were conducted with 8 informants (3 females and 5 males, age above 50) to gather information on their Indigenous Knowledge System. Qualitative data were analyzed using SPSS (16.0 for windows) and the content analysis method was used for the qualitative data analysis. This study was conducted from April 2013 to March 2014.

3. Results and Discussion

Indigenous knowledge on various aspects of Meemure people's life has been shown and discussed below under sub-themes generated through the analysis.

3.1 Indigenous Knowledge Pertaining to Agriculture: Chena and Paddy Cultivations

Every work in chena and paddy cultivation started in an auspicious time after lighting a lamp for Lord Buddha. All the works are done by balancing with the environmental condition. They decide a day to clean the canals in the paddy field after observing the sky (for rainy clouds). They listened carefully to the grasses; the sound of the lizard signifies the time when to start the cleaning of the lands for chena cultivations. Traditional paddy varieties such as *Sudu Vee*, *Heenati Vee*, *Kalu Vee*, *Kalu Kumara Vee*, *Murugakayan* and *Pachcha Perumal* are sowed. Even these traditional paddies produce small harvests it endured hard climate conditions throughout the season (*Kannaya*). *Divi Kaduru* (*Strychnosnux vomica* - Snakewood tree) and *mee* trees (*Madhuca loggifolia* - Honey tree) were farmer's friends which were used as organic fertilizers. The flock of bats that come for the fruits of *mee* tree with their feces fertile the entire paddy land with nitrogen and trace nutrients.

For the protection of paddy from weeds farmer control the water level; water must be spread into the entire field evenly, if not the places that water has not filled give opportunity for weeds to grow. As the fields begin to mature farmers increase the level of the water flow (*wakkada*) and control the water level of the field. When harvesting time is near paddy covers the earth and prevents sunlight from falling on the earth. During this stage, weeds cannot grow as sunlight is absent.

In chena cultivation, the major task is to make a strong fence around the entire chena land for the prevention of animals entering the chena (even small rodents) to feed on the crops. The knowledge of making *Pendi Wata* (type of a fence they create) is highly effective and is a unique feature of Meemure inhabitant's IK system. First, at the bottom of the land forked prop is placed and timbers are used to fill the forked prop. The spaces

between timbers are filled with stones or small logs. As a starting point of the *Pendi Wata* they select cliff place or any other place that prevents animals from entering the Chena such as boulder or peak place of the Chena land [Fig. 2]. Furthermore, every practice of their cultivation is adorned by the indigenous knowledge they have inherited from their forefathers [making of *Chena Pala*, *Piduru Panthala* - mushroom-shaped hey store, *Vee Atuwa* - traditional paddy storing system similar to *vee bissa*, etc.] (Ananda, & Nahallage, 2014).

Figure 2: Structure of *Pendi wata* (Ananda & Nahallage 2014).

3.2.1 Secrete Treatments (*Kem Karma*)

Meemure inhabitant's indigenous agricultural knowledge consists of extraordinary secrete treatments (*Kem Karma*) that used for the protection of the harvest. Small buds of *Kurakkan* (*Eleusine coracana*) and green chilli plants are highly effective to prevent crop damage by the small verity of locust called *Golawella*. Before sunrise or birds singing farmer goes to the middle of the chena land and captures 4 or 5 locust and put them into dried chillies. While chanting a *manthra* (charm) he puts these chillies into a fireplace. No locust will ever harm the plants thereafter. For the rats in the paddy field, they get sands from a place that human haven not stepped. A powerful *manthra* (charm) is chant to the sands and spread to the stretch of paddy land. Diseases of their cattle are also treated by using these secrete treatments.

3.3 Food Preservation

The knowledge of food preservation for future purposes is useful since those foods are not available year-round. Kernel of the jack fruit, sliced bread fruit, jack fruit seeds, long beans, papaw, *Kiri Alakola* (*Dioscorea alata*), manioc, manioc bark, salted lime, orange etc. are stored using various methods and consume when these foods are not available.

Kernel of the Jack Fruit and sliced Bread Fruit dried and stored in the loft (*Massa*) for use when jack fruits and bread fruits are not available. Dried jack fruit called “*Atukos*” and bread fruit called “*Delatu Kos*”. Also jack fruit seeds stored under the sands for preserve, it calls “*Valli Kos Ata*”. These dried foods can be consumed even after one year.

Long Beans stored on the loft (*Massa*-wooden made rack above fireplace use to store foods) after dried under sun light. *Malluma* is prepared from it. Papaw also stored in the same way and used to make *Malluma*. *Kiri alakola* (*Dioscorea alata*), sliced into small round pieces and dried, then can be used to make *malluma*.

They prepare *Irigu Bath* (buck wheat rice) same as milk rice using buck wheat. Buck wheat pound to get rice size pieces. Then mixed it with green gram and long bean nuts and fried. These grains cooked with coconut syrup and ate with *Lunumiris* (onions, chillies, salt mixture)

Sliced Manioc can preserve after dried. Then it can be used to make curries and fried with chillies. Also fried manioc slice is eaten as a sweet with honey. Manioc bark washed well and dried then store on the loft. After fried in deep oil it can eat like appalams. IKS regarding food preserving methods among Meemure inhabitancies are valuable as those are natural and healthy and as vary from junk foods which causes to increase health problems in contemporary society.

3.4 Traditional Foods

Traditional food consumed by Meemure Inhabitancies are another evidence for prove the richness of their IKS. “*Pusnambu*” is one such example for that. *Pusnambu* is famous food among Meemure inhabitancies which is made for special occasions such as Sinhala New Year, ploughing ceremony, *Paritta* ceremony, alms-giving ceremonies (*Dana*), and for weddings etc. It is made of rice flour and *Undu* flour (*Phaseolus mungo*). (They have grown *undu* plants in their gardens) *Undu* and rice flour mixed with water and then keep one night. After sugar and honey are mixed again to that mixture and steamed well. Steamed *Pusanambu* is like a cake and can taste after cutting into pieces.

For the ***Adukku Pujawa*** (*Adukku Pujawa* or *Adukku* offering is a religious practice of Meemure inhabitants. The first portion of their harvest is kept aside and offers it to the village deities on the *Addukku* offering day) they prepare *Kiriroti* or *Kiri Kawum*. It is made out of rice flour and coconut milk. This mixture pours on to the *Rotti Kabala* (plate use to make *rotti*) and can be made one by one *kiri roti* (Ananda & Nahallage, 2015a; 2016).

Kiripani hodda is made to eat with *kiri rotti*. It is made of coconut milk and sugar. Small amount of ginger, pepper and garlic are added into it.

Hathmaluwa (curry made of seven vegetables) is one of common food they prepare in special occasions to eat with rice, *Kiri Rotti*, *Madu Thalapa* and *Kurakkan Thalapa*. It is made by pumpkin, ash pumpkin, bread fruit, young jack fruit, ash plantain,

melon and cucumber. These vegetables mixed well with spices and cooked with small amount of coconut milk.

Kiri Rotti, Kiri Pani Hodda or *Hath Maluwa* are prepared for religious practices such as *Adukku Pujawa* only by men. But after offering it to the deities everyone gets permissions to collectively taste these foods (Ananda & Nahallage, 2016).

Nikadawula Asmi is another traditional sweet it is made of *Nikadawula* leaves (*Vitex negundo*), rice flour and coconut. *Nikadawula* leaves cut into small pieces and mixed with water. Then leave it for 2 hours to mix well with water and then filtered to get the syrup. Then rice flour and coconut mixed with this *Nikadawula* syrup. Using sieve this lotion strain into the deep heated oil as strings. The oval shape is made by spoon while fried. Then honey can be bedaubed on the fried *Nikadawula Asmi* for get tastier.

3.5 Traditional Self-Medication for Common Illnesses and Traditional Medicinal System

Meemure Inhabitancies are highly knowledgeable about popular medicines and village is abundant with popular medicinal plants. For joint pains, the most common disease among the Meemure villagers, they use verity of self-medication practices. Most common one is *Mee* oil (*Madhuca longifolia*) massage. They use dried *Mee* seeds to make *Mee* oil. First dried *mee* seeds are pounded using mortar. Then powder was steamed well covered by *Hakarilla Dalu* in a large earthen pot. Places that steam can be exits were covered by *Humbas Mati* (ant-hill clay). Then the steamed powder was put into the *Mee ata paha* (pouch made of cane) and press tightly using *Pattale* (wooden made small pestle). Then the *mee* oil was strained through *Mee Ata Paha* [Fig.3].

Figure 3: A- *Mee* seeds B- Dry *mee* seeds under the sun light C- *Mee ata paha* and pounded *mee* seeds (Photos by Author)

In addition, dried *adathoda* leaves (Malabar nut-*Adhathoda zeylanica*) barks and a root were boiled and was given to drink. Also steamed *adathoda* leaves, barks and roots are used to ferment the joints. *Yak naran* (*Atalantia zeylanica*) leaves, orange leaves (*Citrus aurantium*), lemon leaves (*Citrus aurantifolia*), and ginger and garlic boiled together and drink for arthritis as well as for cold. For worm diseases they eat *katu eramudu* leaves (*Erythrina suberosa*) *malluma* (mixed with coconut). *Kowakka* leaf (Baby gourd-*Coccinia grandis*) *mallum* is used for diabetes and *thepu* leaves (Crep ginger-*Costus speciosus*),

kowakka leaves and (*thoratiya mallum*) are used for blood pressure (diabetes and blood pressure was reported in lower than 1% of adult inhabitants).

Meemure specific IK has become more brighten with its glorious medicinal system. From the beginning of the Meemure village traditional medicinal generation too has established in the village named

“*Valithuduwe Veda Paramparava*” (*Valithuduwe* medicine generation). At present fourth generation contribute its traditional knowledge for the welfare of the villagers. Mostly this “*Valithuduwe veda paramparava*” is famous for Serpent’s venom (*Sarpa Visha Vedakama*), Fractures (*Kadum Bindum Vedakama*), Treatments of boils (*Gedi Veda Kama*), Rheumatic disease (*Vatha Roga*) and for Arthritis (joint pain).

Herbal plants and other medicinal herbs are collected from forests that have spread around the village. These forests are abundant with valuable herbs such as *Iru Raja*, *Sanda Raja*, *Vanaraja* (*Anaectochilus setaceus*), *Gururaja* (*Moringa oleifera*) and various kinds of other herbs. Thus, there are no need to cultivate herbs in the garden and *veda mahaththaya* (village physician) believe that natural herbs are powerful than cultivated herbs.

Veda mahaththaya and few men go to the forest twice a month to collect herbs before sun rise and before birds wake up. When the herb collecting day is reached, they observe higher precept and prevent eating meats or any kinds of impure foods (fish, dried fish, eggs, maldive fish etc.) herbs are collect carefully without harming to the forest’s biosphere. Medicines are prepared in the house by *veda mahaththaya* with the help of villagers.

All the treatments and other duties are done without any of charge until diseased person get well. All the expenses for treatments are manage by the *veda mahaththaya*’s own income he gets from paddy farming.

3.5.1 Serpent’s Venom Medicine

Verities of serpents are living in Meemure village. Dense forest around the village and the presence of small bushes, other trees, and plants inside of the village have given opportunity to them to spread well. Medicines and treatment methods differ as the serpent that has stung. When the serpent has not recognized special charmed herbs are given to the attacked person. Those herbs useful for reduce the venom.

Treatments for Cobra Venom

- I. *Bombu* (*Symplocos cochinchinensis*) leaves, barks, and roots were crushed and apply on the wound.
- II. *Hathawariya* (*Asparagus racemosus*), curry leaves (*Murraya koenigii Spreng*), garlic (*Allium sativum*), honey and *endaru* (*Jatropha curcuras*) mixed gruel.
- III. Pepper; curry leaves, garlic, tamarind (*Tamarindus indica*), *sahindalunu* (kind of salt) mixed curry.

- IV. Lemon, orange, curry leaves, leaves of the neem tree (*Azadirachta indica*), *savandara* roots (*Andropogon squarrosus*), traumatic mixed herbal water bath.

Treatments for Tholissa (kunakatuwa) sting (Merrem's hump-nosed viper- Hypnale hypnale)

- I. *Tholaboo* leaves (spider lilly -*Crinum asiaticum*), traumatic, salt, lemon crushed together and apply on the wound.
- II. Indian sarsaparilla (*Iramusu-Hemidesmus indicus*), butter leaves (*wedaru*), coconut milk, *sahinda lunu* mixed gruel.
- III. Lemon, orange, curry leaves, neem tree leaves, *savandara* roots, traumatic mixed herbal water bath.

Treatments for Divimakuluwa Venom (Tarantula- Poecilotheria fasciata)

- I. All the parts of the *divikaduru* (Snake wood tree-*strychnos nux-vomica*) tree used for the treatments. *Divikaduru* leaves, fruits, barks, roots, traumatic, sat, lime mixed well and apply on the wound. And this mixture used to foment the body it used to prevent crouch the person. (they believe after stung by *divi makuluwa* stung person is crouched)
- II. Foment the body by steamed *Mee muruwata* (recrement of *mee* seeds after oil is extracted)
- III. Let person to drink *Udupiyaliya* leaves (*Desmodium triflorum*), lime, coconut milk, ghee, and jiggery mixture.

3.5.2 Fracture Medicine

When bone is fractured *veda mhaththaya* examine the place by touching and find out which bone has fractured and how. If there is contusions and wounds treatments are differing and must treat the wound at first. Though there are wounds in fractured place before treat to fracture wound must be treated. For wounds crushed *Hakarilla* leaves (*Solanum mauritianum*) are applied. If there is a contusion *Milala* leaves, bark pounded and applied.

For fractures most famous herbal plant is “*Samadana*” (*Blepharis repens*). Its leaves crushed and applied on the fractured place. And “*Gonu Kaa Kola*” (*Hoya ovalifolia*) used for joining the fractured bones. There is folk tale around the *Gonu Ka Kola*. A bull had fallen down from high place and its bones had fractured. It had been laid down in the place and had eaten leaves that had grown around it. After few days bull had been able to stand and walk. Its fractured bones had been joined together with the power of leaves that it had eaten. That leaves named as *Gonu Ka Kola* (leaves eaten by bull) and used for fractures from that day for humans too.

Fractures are not only treated by applying herbs but *veda mahaththaya* use *paththu* (made of bamboo flakes) to join the fractured bones. Bamboo flakes use to strap around the fractured place. Several of herbs use and the time that *paththu* must be wore depend on place and type of the fracture.

3.5.3 Treatments of Boils

Mostly Boils are occurred when blood get poisoned. And bacterial infections, insect's bites or allergies may cause to boils. In the traditional treatments of boils at first herbs apply on the boil to rive it. *Kumburu* leaves (*Caesalpinia bonduc*), lime juice mixed and heat together and apply on the boil for rive. And then wound is covered after applying heated *masbadda* leaves (*Gymnema syivestre*), raw traumatic, and sesame oil mixture on it.

3.6 Indigenous Embalming Knowledge

After someone died in the village and if the body is kept in house for more than one day it needs to be embalmed. For that they use traditional knowledge of embalming. Soon after a person dies, honey is poured into the mouth of the diseased person. Honey helps to postpone the putrefaction. Then the body is washed, and rectum is closed by cotton or small piece of cloth for prevent body fluids coming out. Then the throat is filled with betel and arecanut mixture. *Mee* (*Madhuca longifolia*) leaves, seeds, barks and traumatic are pounded and applied on stomach around navel and bandaged to prevent putrefaction. A large earthen pot with charcoal is kept near the coffin. Citrus leafs such as lime, orange, musk lime, tangerines etc. were put on charcoal and its smoke was used as germicide (Ananda & Nahallage, 2017).

3.7 Indigenous Knowledge Used in Architecture

In the west side of the Meemure village there is a house with different features that cannot be seen in other houses in the village. This house is the only house that shows ancient house planning and architectural features. It is made above the ground on about 70 cm height soling basement. This house consists of 6 rooms. Doors and door frames were elaborated by designs and for doorstep a rectangular shaped stone has used. Cow dung is applied on the floor. There is a stone path goes to the door step of the house. Then ancient door opens into the squire shaped compound which would have made to lighten the house in the daytime.

In the corner of the compound there is a flat stone layer which was used to pound grains (rice, *Kurakkan*, *undu* etc). It reveals the art of traditional pounding of grains. Five women can use pestles at one time to pound grains standing around the flat stone layer. After bringing the harvest in to the house responsibility is handed over to the women to take care of rest works such as pounding, drying under sunlight etc. which would be the reason of having stone ponding layer inside the house. [Fig. 4]. Stone path and stone fence also specific features of their housing systems. All over the village these kinds of stone fences can be seen. They have not used any kind of cement or plaster to harden the

stones together. Only they used is the traditional knowledge of their forefathers for build these stone fences. Oval and round shape stones can be seen all around the village thus the task have not hard for them to collect those and to arrange one on another carefully until about 25 m fence is finished [Fig. 5].

Figure 4: Stone Fences in the Meemure village (Photos by Author)

A

B

C

D

R

F

G

4. Conclusion

Antique household instruments, religious practices were also a part of their indigenous knowledge which represent both intangible and tangible cultural heritage. Minority groups like Meemure people have been exposed to innovations and technologies. Consequently, indigenous knowledge that they have hold become less and less usable with the new technologies. Present young people do not follow their ancestor's indigenous knowledge as they prefer modern technology that needs less physically strenuous work (Ananda and Nahallage, 2015b). The speed of the increase in the human population

throughout the globe has caused many global crises. Human is the only animal that makes conscious choices which are bad for his survival.

Today many scholars and organizations such as UNESCO, World Bank, World Health Organization have given their attention to the Indigenous Knowledge Systems of communities throughout the world.

Their nature-loving knowledge systems are the best methods that we can use for making tomorrow's world a better place to live. Padmasiri (2017) in his research has shown that the universities, museums, and libraries as the Government institutions that have the responsibility to identify, collect, preserve, and disseminate indigenous knowledge for the benefit of the local and global community (Padmasiri, 2018). Also, the methods such as ethnographies (e.g. present study), digital library systems, database systems, community archives can use to preserve the IK in the forms of images, videos (films/short films), recordings, documents, drawings, paintings, diaries (ethnographies/virtual ethnographies) for the protection and preservation for the future (Padmasiri, 2018; Poorna, et al., 2014).

References

- Ananda, T. (2019). *A Comparative Anthropological Study on Yakkure and Henanigala Indigenous Groups in Sri Lanka (Unpublished PhD Thesis)*. University of Sri Jayewardenepura.
- Ananda, T. and Nahallage, C. (2014) Traditional Agricultural Practises unique to Meemure village, Kandy district Sri Lanka, *International Journal of Multidisciplinary Studies*. 01 (1): pp. 11-21.
- Ananda, T. and Nahallage, C. (2015a) Religious Practices Performed by Meemure Villagers in Kandy District Sri Lanka, International Conference on Humanities, Faculty of Humanities, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka: p. 31.
- Ananda, T. and Nahallage, C. (2015b) Socio-Cultural Change in Meemure Village in Kandy District: Twenty Years after the Prohibition of Chena Cultivation-Young Scientists Forum Symposium, National Science and Technology Commission, Hector Kobbakaduwa Agrarian Research and Training Institute, Sri Lanka., 23rd January 2015. Oral presentation. Extended Abstract 9 -12 pp.
- Ananda, T. and Nahallage, C. (2016) Unique Religious and Cultural Practices as Evident in the Kandyan Village of Meemure, *Selected Papers from the International Conference of the Humanities 2015*, K. Herath and D. Fernando (Eds.), Faculty of Humanities, University of Kelaniya, pp. 73-82.
- Ananda, T. and Nahallage, C. (2017). Rites of Passages among Meemure Inhabitants Living in Kandy District, Sri Lanka, *18th International Postgraduate Research Conference*, Faculty of Graduate Studies, University of Kelaniya, Sri Lanka, 08th December 2017. (Oral Presentation). Abstract p. 139.
- Anon., 2017. *Local and Indigenous Knowledge Systems*. [Online]
- Available at: <http://www.unesco.org/new/en/natural-sciences/priority-areas/links/related-information/what-islocal-and-indigenous-knowledge> [Accessed 18 10 2021].

- Ariyapala, M. B. (1959). *Madyakalina Lanka Sanskruthiya*. Colombo: M D Gunasena.
- Barnouw, V., 1982. *Ethnology: An Introduction to the Anthropology*. USA: The Dorsey Press.
- Campbell, B. G. L. J. D. U. K. C., 2006. *Biological Anthropology: The Natural History of Humankind*. Canada: Pearson Education, Inc..
- Department of Census and Statistics. (2012). *Census of Population and Housing 2012*. <http://www.statistics.gov.lk/Population/StaticInformation/CPH2011/CensusPopulationHousing2012FinalReport>
- Goonewardene, S., Drake, J. & De Silva, A., 2006. *The Herpetofauna of the Knuckles Range*, s.l.: Project Knuckles 2004 and 2005: University of Edinburgh Research Expedition. Amphibia and Reptile Research Organisation of Sri Lanka (ARROS)..
- Kottak, C. P., 2012. *Mirror for Humanity: An Introduction to Cultural Anthropology*. 8th ed. ed. New York: Mc-Graw Hill.
- Lokubandara, W. M. (1959). *Lakegala, Sri Lanka, 11(02)*, January, p8.
- Miraglia, R. A. (1998). *Traditional Ecological Knowledge Handbook: A Training Manual And Reference Guide For Designing, Conducting, and Participating in Research Projects using Traditional Ecological Knowledge*, Alaska Department of Fish and Game, Division of Subsistence: Alaska.
- Mistry, J. (2009). Indigenous Knowledges, R. Kitchin, N. Thrift (Eds.) *International Encyclopedia of Human Geography*, Elsevier, 371-376, DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-008044910-4.00101-2>.
- Padmasiri, G. R., 2018. Management of indigenous knowledge in Sri Lanka, with special reference to indigenous medicine. *Information Development*, 34(5), pp. 475-488.
- Poorna, R. L., Mymoon, M. & Hariharan, A., 2014. Preservation and protection of traditional knowledge— diverse documentation initiatives across the globe. *Current Science*, Volume 2014, pp. 1240-1246.
- Rajapaksha, S. (2007). *Meemure*. Ja Ella: Samanthi Publications.
- Silva, P. D., & Punchihewa, A. G. (2011). *Socio-Anthropological Research Project on Vedda Community in Sri Lanka*.
- Thomas, S., 1999. *Early Mapping of Southeast Asia*. s.l.:Periplus Editions.
- Wikipedia (2013) *Meemure*, 10 October, the free encyclopaedia, accessed on 10-10-2013. <http://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Meemure>

Introducing mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales to Sri Lankan German language learners. (A case study)

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Abstract:

This paper examines the pitfalls of introducing mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales to Sri Lankan German language learners. The research is conducted as a case study where both the teacher's and learners' experience during the classroom sessions are analyzed to identify which teaching materials can be used to introduce Grimm's mythical creatures to Sri Lankan German language learners. The research sample consisted of learners who follow the German first-year special degree program at the department of modern languages, University of Kelaniya. Three classroom sessions were observed using different teaching materials to analyze how the learning process should be gradually developed. The learners' experience of learning Grimm's mythical characters was examined through the distribution of a questionnaire. According to the findings of the research, it was evident that the Sri Lankan learners' perception of mythical creatures is influenced by the Sri Lankan folktales, which contain a wide variety of mythical characters from Indian mythology. Therefore, it was encountered by the researcher that the learners' previous knowledge about mythical beings is an obstacle for the learning process. Yet the data collected from the classroom observations and questionnaires has indicated that it is possible through carefully selected visual materials such as images, documentaries, and written manuscripts of legends and myths to introduce the Grimm's mythical fairy tale characters to Sri Lankan German language learners more effectively.

Keywords: *German language learners, Grimm's fairy tales, introduce, mythical creatures, Sri Lankan*

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Introduction

The Grimm's famous fairy tale collection of "Children's and household stories" by Brother Grimm, first published in 1812 with 82 fairy tales, has laid the foundations for many research disciplines related to German literature. During the fairy tale collection period in 1785, Germany was divided into several states and was going through the Napoleonic wars, which prevented Germany from being united as a country. The civilians were afraid of losing their national and cultural heritage due to the changing of borders and foreign influences.

According to Brother Grimm, the most natural and pure roots of any culture are hidden in folklore in its purest form, untainted by foreign influences. Therefore, they believed that acquiring a philological understanding of old German literature, which is handed over from one generation to the other by word of mouth and entails natural language, would motivate the people to identify the connection between customs, laws, and beliefs of their origins and unite them as one nation. Their effort in collecting and documenting folklore has saved the folktales from extinction and has bequeathed the preserved folklore as a common cultural identity to German people of all social classes.

German folklore shares many similarities with Scandinavian and English folklore, and all these three folklore traditions have their origins in German mythology. The folklore of Germanic tribes was rich in early Christian pantheon and magical characters depicted as supernatural spirits. Although belief in pre-Christian pagan rituals faded with Christianization, some supernatural spirits from early Germanic mythology, such as witches, elves, dwarfs, kobolds, nymphs, fairies, and water spirits, later became prominent figures in German folklore.

Grimm's fairy tale collection, which is highly influenced by the ideologies of dark romanticism and the early Germanic mythologies, contains high fantasy and supernatural elements. These elements are either derived from a magical person (from a witch or from a fairy god mother) a magical object (a magic mirror or a magic pot) or an enchantment (Snow white is awakened by a kiss). Moreover, the magical or mythical characters depicted in Grimm's tales are rather complex as they either appear as positive spirits who comfort and help the protagonist (fairies, mermaids, nymphs, fairy god mothers, and dwarfs) or as characters with dark negative spirits (witches, demons, Kobolds) who play the role of antagonists. Yet the human nature of the protagonist's character is clearly depicted through the interaction between the protagonist and the mythical creatures. Therefore, studying the nature of mythical beings is considered important when studying fairy tales as a literary genre as it allows the reader to closely examine the motif, setting, themes and the plot of the story.

Instructors in various academic disciplines, especially in Germanistik¹, have identified Grimm's fairy tales as a pedagogical tool, which offers a broad range of

1 The study of German language and literature from its inception to the present day, in terms of its social and cultural relationships, as well as its theoretical underpinnings.

educational needs for learners to strengthen their writing and reading skills, explore cultural values and enhance critical thinking. Jakob and Wilhelm Grimm have also named their fairy tale collection as an educational manual (Erziehungsbuch) which can be used in universities for folklore and medieval literature studies of early Germanic tribes.

Grimm's fairy tale collection is used as a study material for German special degree first year students at the department of modern languages, university of Kelaniya for the course unit 'Analysis and interpretation of German literature'. The objective of this course unit is to introduce learners to different folklore genres in Germany, such as fairy tales, legends, and fables. Learners are expected to identify the characteristics of each genre and analyze their narrative form, structure, characters, themes and plot. Furthermore, they conduct research, group projects, and presentations to be familiarized with the historical evidence of the origin of the stories, their oral traditions, and engage in exercises which enhance their intercultural skills about folklore genres in Germany and Sri Lanka.

Learners who are familiar with German fairy tales either through Disney films or through Sinhala and English translations, find it interesting to read the original versions of the stories written in German and are surprised to see the differences between the content of the stories they have already known and the original German version. Yet introducing mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales to Sri Lankan German language learners was a challenging experience for teachers, as the language learners had their own perceptions of mythical creatures due to the influence of Sri Lankan folktales.

The students' images of certain mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales were formed based on their knowledge of mythical creatures depicted in jataka tales² and in Sri Lankan folktales. Yet the mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales that originated from Germanic mythologies rarely share similarities with the mythical creatures in Sri Lankan folklore. Therefore, the objective of this research was to examine the pitfalls of introducing mythical creatures from Grimm's fairy tales to Sri Lankan German language learners. The research was conducted as a case study where both the teacher's and learners' experiences during the class room sessions are analyzed to identify which teaching materials can be suggested to introduce Grimm's mythical creatures to Sri Lankan German language learners more effectively.

Literature Review

Grimm's fairy tales are alive with supernatural creatures such as fairies, dwarfs, witches, mermaids, nymphs, and sorcerers who were part of the pre-Christian imagination, which believed that another unseen world existed alongside our own. According to Rieti, witches in folklore are considered as ambiguous mythical creatures with complex characteristics who appear as monstrous evil spirits. But in some stories, we find witches being kind and loving and playing the role of a maternal benefactress to the protagonist.

2 A voluminous body of literature native to India concerning the previous births of Gautama Buddha in both human and animal form.

Aside from that, witches are associated with healing powers, knowledge of medicinal herbs, and a close relationship with nature. Rieti, B. (2008)³

Sigrid Brauner explains in her book ‘Fearless Wives and Frightened Shrews: The Construction of the Witch in Early Modern Germany’, how Grimm’s fairy tale witch character was influenced by the witch trials in Germany. She states that witch hunts existed throughout Europe until 1750, and the last witch execution took place in Germany about fifty years before the first fairy tale collection was published in 1812.

Yet, the belief and fear of witches and supernatural powers were not easily erased after the executions were stopped but remained during the times when the Grimm brothers were writing their first manuscripts of the fairy tale collection. Moreover, she mentions that although the fairy tale witch character in Grimm’s fairy tales would seem like an imaginary character to modern-day readers, it was more closely considered real by readers who came from a generation that had experienced witch trials with their own eyes. Brauner, S. (2001)⁴

The nature of the mythical witch character in Grimm’s fairy tales is further studied by Meghan Hill in the research article ‘A Comparative Analysis of Character Depiction in the Grimm’s Kinder-und Hausmärchen and Modern Fairytale Adaptations’, where she has highlighted the complexity of Grimm’s witch character with examples from popular fairy tales. Meghan Hill has identified two types of witch characters in Grimm’s fairy tales, which she has categorized as witches who use excess use of magic powers and witches who practice magic in isolation. The witch in Rapunzel, who owns a lush garden and has raised her daughter for several years without revealing her secret, is considered by Meghan as a witch who uses her magic powers only in isolation, while the witches in Hansel and Gretel and Snow White seem to be witches who use excessive magic powers on a daily basis. Yet the fairy tales give evidence that both types of these witch characters need magic powers to fight or to defend themselves, and without the magic, they are helpless as normal human beings. Hill, M. (2015)⁵

Grimm’s fairy tales have inherited significant features from folktales, which have roots in mythological stories and consist of themes such as cannibalism and infanticide, which are portrayed mainly by the character of a witch or by mythical creatures such as dwarfs, kobolds, or werewolves. According to Maria Tatar, cannibalism and infanticide are included in Grimm’s fairy tales not because the children prefer them, but because the adults expected through that to pass their internal message to the next generation. Tatar, M (1992)⁶

3 Rieti, B. (2008), *Making Witches: Newfoundland Traditions of Spells and Counterspells*, McGill-Queen’s University Press, Montreal & Kingston

4 Brauner, S. (2001), *Fearless Wives and Frightened Shrews: The Construction of the Witch in Early Modern Germany*, University of Massachusetts Press, Amherst

5 Hill, M. (2015), *A Comparative Analysis of Character Depiction in the Grimm’s Kinder-und Hausmärchen and Modern Fairytale Adaptations*, Honors Theses, Union College, Schenectady, New York

6 Tatar, M. (1992), *Off with Their Heads: Fairy Tales and the Culture of Childhood*, Princeton University Press, Princeton

Hansel and Gretel is one of the most well-known Grimm's fairy tale with cannibalistic elements. In this story, the cannibalism theme is represented through the character of an old witch who lives in isolation in the deep forest and wishes to kill the little children and eat their flesh. "a wicked witch" who "lay in wait for children and had built her little house of bread to tempt them, and whenever one of them got into her power, she killed it, cooked it, and ate it, and that was for her a day to celebrate" Zipes, J. (1987)⁷

In the fairy tale snow white, the antagonist's role is played by a queen who is also a witch who fears that snow white will become more beautiful than her. She orders a huntsman to kill Snow White and bring her heart and liver as proof. But not knowing that the huntsman had brought the heart and lungs of a wild pig, the queen orders the cook to cook them for her. "Boil them in salt, and the wicked woman ate them and thought she had eaten Snow White's lungs and liver." Zipes, J. (1987)⁸

In Grimm's fairy tales, the witches are not always portrayed as black magic practitioners but also as white magic practitioners or as healers who help the protagonist on their journey. According to Federici, wise women knew much about nature, berries, plants, and how to help people with their pains. One can say that a wise woman was a kind of healer, which was a typical characteristic of good witches. Federici, S. (2012)⁹ In German literature, white witches are referred to as "Weise Frauen" (wise women). In the Sleeping Beauty fairy tale, the king arranges a celebration and invites thirteen 'Weise Frauen' to bless the new born child. Yet it is said that the thirteenth wise woman, who was angry at not being served a plate, cursed the child. "The king's daughter shall in her fifteenth year be wounded by a spindle, and fall down dead. Kemptner, D. (2009)¹⁰"

Then the twelfth, who had not yet given her gift, came forward and said "the king's daughter should not die, but fall asleep for a hundred years". Grimm, J., Grimm, W. (2011)¹¹ In the fairy tale of the Seven Brothers, the brothers are turned into seven crows after picking seven white lilies growing in the backyard. Then an old woman suddenly appears and tells the princess that she should not have allowed her brothers to pick the white lilies helps the princess what she should do to save her seven brothers from the curse. Therefore, it is evident that witches in Grimm's fairy tales are identified as magical supernatural creatures who can execute both black and white magic.

Similar to the character of witches, one of the other most prominent mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales are dwarfs. According to Reynold, dwarfs in Grimm's fairy tales are depicted as friendly, helpful mythical creatures who are safe to accompany. It is suggested through their hospitality in the Snow White fairy tale, where the seven

7 Zipes, J. (1987), *The Complete Fairy Tales of The Brothers Grimm*, Bantam Books, New York

8 Zipes, J. (1987), *The Complete Fairy Tales of The Brothers Grimm*, Bantam Books, New York

9 Federici, S. (2012), *Witch-Hunting, Past and Present, and the Fear of the Power of Women*, Hate Cantz Verlag, Ostfildern

10 Kemptner, D. (2009), *Sleeping Beauty and her many relatives*, "Thesis, Georgia State University, Atlanta

11 Grimm, J., Grimm, W., (2011), *Grimm's Fairy Tales*, Kindle Edition, Amazon Publishing.

dwarfs provide Snow White with a safe environment to protect her from her evil stepmother. (Reynolds, 2017)¹² furthermore they are presented as mine workers who excavate precious natural stones and rare rocks during the day. Yet in the fairy tale ‘Rumpelstilzchen’ (Rumpelstiltskin), another mythical creature who is similar to a dwarf or a kobold in appearance plays the role of the antagonist. Meghan Hill has analyzed the characteristics of the dwarf figure in the Rumpelstilzchen fairy tale, where she states that Rumpelstilzchen seems to be a non-human antagonist who possesses supernatural powers, because he helps the miller’s daughter to turn hay into gold, yet takes full advantage of the situation for his own benefit, finally making her promise to give him her firstborn child.

Although the fairy tale did not clearly explain why the dwarf needed the new born infant, it is mentioned that he sings in the evening sitting in front of his hut saying “Heute back ich, Morgen brau ich”, which means “today I am baking and tomorrow I am brewing”, which means his intention is to kill the infant. Hill, M. (2015)¹³ Therefore, the depiction of the dwarfs as mythical creatures is not similar in all Grimm’s fairy tales, where in some they are presented as trustworthy, friendly, and protective creatures, whereas in others they are shown as cruel, inhuman, and not trustworthy supernatural beings.

Another important supernatural appearance in Grimm’s fairy tales is the fairy god mothers who play the role of well-wishers and protectors of neglected children. The mythical character of the fairy godmother, who is a very frequent mythical figure in Grimm’s fairy tales, appears when the protagonist is in need of help or in danger. She is presented in the form of a fairy or an old woman who watches over the spiritual development and well-being of the child. In Cinderella, a fairy god mother appears and helps Cinderella to grant her wishes. Yet it is questionable whether the character of the fairy god mother is a form of a supernatural being or whether the character resembles the role of a human god mother. Because in most fairy tales, the fairy Godmother appears in front of orphans who lack motherly affection and are being ill-treated by society. In oral tradition, in certain European regions, grandmothers are often known as godmothers, and even uncles and aunts of the child will be known as godparents. Francisco, S. (2000)¹⁴ Therefore, perhaps the supernatural figure of the fairy god mother in Grimm’s fairy tales symbolizes the motherly affection, warmth, and care that an orphan misses during his or her childhood.

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- 12 Reynolds, S. (2017). Grimm Fairy Tales & Their Successors: A Study on Snow White. [online]. Available at: <https://medium.com/@renwald12/grimm-fairy-tales-their-successors-a-study-on-snow-white-4e11fb7d3c77/> (Accessed 22 June 2021)
- 13 Hill, M. (2015), A Comparative Analysis of Character Depiction in the Grimm’s Kinder-und Hausmärchen and Modern Fairytale Adaptations, Honors Theses, Union College, Schenectady, New York
- 14 Francisco, S. (2000) “Complex Entities in the Universe of Fairy Tales.” *Marvels & Tales*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 219–243. JSTOR. Available at: www.jstor.org/stable/41388560./ (Accessed 24 June 2021)

Mother Holle in the 'Frau Holle' fairy tale, is another well-known mythical figure in German folklore. The old woman named Mother Holle in Grimm's fairy tales is a kind old lady with big teeth who lives in a house in the sky and helps the clever, hard-working girls by presenting gifts and good fortune, and on the other hand, punishes the lazy, stubborn girls. According to the fairy tale, she shakes her pillow in the morning to release white feathers which fall as snowflakes to the earth. Therefore, her character is presented as a fairy or as a white spirit who is in charge of the elements of nature. The origin of the mythical figure 'Frau Holle' lies in Germanic and Scandinavian mythology, where she is considered as a supernatural spirit similar to a witch who enters homes during Christmas and checks to see that all the household work and spinning is done. If the ladies of the house are lazy and not hardworking, she will punish them. But if the house is clean and tidy, she will be impressed and gift the young women of the house with spindles¹⁵. Gray, H. (2021)¹⁶

Apart from the above mentioned mythical creatures, Grimm's fairy tales consist of nymphs, kobolds, and many other supernatural beings belonging to Germanic and Scandinavian mythology. When analyzing these mythical creatures, it is noted that each of these mythical characters has complex personalities, and even certain mythical creatures, such as dwarfs and witches, play both black and white roles in different fairy tales. Therefore, studying mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales is a challenging task for Sri Lankan learners with limited knowledge of mythical figures in European mythology. Although there was research being conducted about the attributes of mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales, less research was being carried out to identify how these mythical creatures should be introduced to language learners from a different cultural setting. Therefore, it is expected that this research will add new insights and novel knowledge to the foreign language literature and folklore research discipline.

Data Collection

The research sample consisted of 15 students who were following the German first-year Special Degree program at the Department of Modern Languages, University of Kelaniya. Three class room observations were conducted, each consisting of two hours of observation to observe how the learners try to identify the mythical characters in Grimm's with what they are already familiar with. At the end of the final observation, a questionnaire was distributed to analyze the learners' experience. This is a local case study research where the researcher was motivated to conduct the research after encountering that the learners' previous knowledge about Sri Lankan mythical creatures is an obstacle when being introduced to mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales.

The main focus of the data collection was given to the researcher's observation during class room sessions in order to identify which teaching materials are more effective

15 A slender, rounded rod with tapered ends is used in hand spinning to twist and wind thread from a mass of wool or flax held on a distaff.

16 Gray, H. (2021). *Frau Holle, the Germanic Winter Goddess* | *Hag Stone Journal*. [online] Available at: <https://hagstonejournal.com/frau-holle-the-germanic-winter-goddess/> (Accessed 23 June 2021)

when introducing Grimm's mythical characters to Sri Lankan learners.

Data analysis

The data collected through class observations is analyzed to examine through which teaching exercises and materials learners' pre knowledge of mythical creatures can be tested. Class room observations were conducted in three sessions, with each session containing a different set of teaching materials and exercises. The first class room session was conducted with the use of images, and the second class room session was conducted using a worksheet with a reading text and guided questions, and the third class room session was conducted for evaluation, where the learners presented their research findings through a poster presentation.

Class room session 01

During the first class room session, the learners were divided into four groups, each consisting of five learners, and each group was given five black and white images of mythical figures selected from the Grimm's fairy tales to describe. The groups were numbered from 1 to 5, and the images should be described in three steps. First, the learners should describe the appearance of the person whom they see in the image using adjectives, and then, as the second step, they should write down what reminds them of this image and whether they have seen this person before, and as the third step, they should guess the name of this mythical creature and what magical powers it possesses. The learners were not told that these images represent mythical creatures because some of the images are similar to humans in appearance. The expected learning outcome of this exercise was to test the learners' ability to identify mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales by using their previous knowledge of Sri Lankan myths and memories based on children's stories. The five images consisted of an image of a witch, a dwarf, a fairy god mother, a nymph and an elf. The five sets of images which were used for exercise 01 are given below.

Figure 01: The images in the worksheet (a witch, a dwarf, a fairy god mother, a nymph and an elf)

The first image, which is an image of a witch, was described by each group using adjectives such as wicked, old, cruel, ugly, evil, unsympathetic, cunning, and cruel. In every group, the learners have identified the character as a witch. To the question of what reminds them of this character and where they have seen this figure before, groups 1, 2, and 4 have written that this character reminds them of 'bata kola achchi'¹⁷ in Sri Lankan fairy tales. The group 3 and 5 have written that this reminds them of the evil witch in Disney fairy tale movies. Almost every group has stated that they have seen this character in films, fairy tale books, and have heard of it during folk tale narrations by their parents and grandparents during their childhood. Through the adjectives the learners have used to describe the character of the witch, the researcher observed that the learners identify the character of the witch as an old evil woman, and they were first introduced to this character by their parents and grandparents, and later through Disney fairy tale films.

The image of the dwarf was described by each group using words such as funny, small, relaxed, friendly, helpful, protective, imaginary and intelligent. The researcher could not observe much difference between the descriptions provided by each group for this picture description. They all have mentioned that this image brings back their memories of the fairy tale snow white and have mentioned that they have seen this creature in animated fairy tale films and in children's story books. The learners' description has provided the researcher information to identify that they are familiar with the concept of dwarfs, because it is a common mythical creature found in both European and in Asian fairy tales. Yet their description has indicated that they identify dwarfs as extremely friendly, helpful and loyal creatures and are not aware of the fact that dwarfs in Grimm's fairy tale convey a mixed personality of good and evil.

¹⁷ Sri Lankan fairy tale witch character

The learners have used vocabulary such as old, kind, loving, mother like, helpful, magical and fairy like to describe the image of the fairy godmother. They have written that this image reminds them of the fairy tale Cinderella. Because of the fairy wings and magic wand in her hand, they have guessed that she is similar to a fairy. And all the groups have mentioned that they have previously seen a similar image in Disney animated movies. Yet the students were unable to provide a proper explanation about who this person actually is.

Group 1 and 3 have written that this person could be an old fairy and group 2 and 4 have written that this character is a female sorcerer and the group number 5 has just written the word ‘grandma’ as an answer. Through the learners’ efforts to guess who this character is, the researcher realized that although they have seen this character before, this is not a familiar mythical figure for them, because this mythical character is rarely seen in Sri Lankan folktales. Therefore, the concept of fairy god mother seems to be an unfamiliar term for the Sri Lankan German language learners.

The adjectives used to describe the image of the nymph¹⁸ by groups 1 and 3 include “beautiful,” “enchanted,” “magical,” and “unreal.” To the question of what memories they associate with this image, each group had different answers. Group 1 has written that this image reminds them of a fairy. Group two has written that it looks like a deity, and group number three has written that it is a princess. Group number four has written that it could be a young lady from a rich family, and group number five has written that it could be a ghost. Two groups (groups 3 and 5) have not answered the question of where they have seen this kind of image earlier, but group number 1 has stated that this image is similar to the maidens in the Sigiriya frescoes.

Group number 2 has written that these are similar to the paintings of deities in Buddhist temples and group number 4 has written that this mythical character reminds them of ‘kinduro and Kinduriyo’¹⁹ in ‘sanda kinduru jathakaya’²⁰. The description of the learners and their effort to identify similarities between nymphs and Sri Lankan deities was a signal to indicate that although they did not fully understand the concept of nymphs, they were able to guess the character attributes by comparing them with mythical creatures in Buddhist jataka tales.

In contrast to the reaction of the learners when identifying the character of the nymph, it was noted the image of the elf²¹ which has a similar appearance to humans, has somewhat misled the learners. Because of the long cloak he wears and his noble personality, the learners have assumed he is a warrior lord or a prince. But his pointed ears gave them a hint that he could not be a human being. The learners have written that they have seen similar characters in films, and they especially mentioned the film ‘Lord of the Rings’. But they mentioned that they exactly don’t know what this mythical creature is.

18 In ancient Greek mythology, a minor female nature deity

19 A form of deity similar to nymphs, found in Buddhist Jataka tales.

20 A Buddhist jataka tale

21 A humanoid supernatural being in north Germanic mythology

Class Room session 02

During this session, the learners were given a worksheet with a reading text on medieval witches and witch trials in Germany along with a set of guided questions to be answered during the reading. This exercise was conducted as pair work. As it was mentioned in the literature review, the witch character in Grimm's fairy tales is a complex character who was influenced by the beliefs of the people during the witch trials in Germany. For example, studying the historical context would allow learners to understand how the fairy witch character was created based on real historical evidence. It was expected of the learners through this exercise, to be familiarized with the beliefs of the medieval superstitious, related to witches and to possess a thorough knowledge of the reasons for the witch trials in Germany. The answers were discussed in the class and the learners' opinion about providing a reading text with historical evidence about medieval witch hunts was analyzed through the distribution of a questionnaire at the end of the third class room session.

Class Room session 03

As for the third exercise, the learners were again divided into 5 groups, and each group was given a mythical character which they had described during the first activity. The learners were instructed to do research on the origins of these mythical creatures based on German folklore and mythology, and analyze their character evaluation in Grimm's fairy tales. The findings of their research were presented in groups to the class as an oral presentation, and this exercise was used to evaluate their knowledge and understanding of the mythical characters in Grimm's fairy tales. The learners have used web sites and journal articles as primary sources for their research and as secondary resources they have retrieved information from documentaries.

The learners' have analyzed the origins of the mythical creatures from written sources on Germanic mythology and have identified that the attributes of the mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales and in mythology are completely different from the depiction of mythical creatures in fairy tale films and in Disney cartoons. Therefore, they have avoided using films and animated cartoons for this research, as they have realized, that the contents of these products can be misleading and cannot be used as a trustworthy source of information, when analyzing Grimm's mythical creatures.

This opinion was solely based on the research findings of the learners and noted by the researcher, as one of the most interesting and surprising encounters of the class room observations where the learners have identified themselves, through which sources they can best learn about the mythical creatures of Grimm's fairy tales.

Data collected from questionnaires.

After the end of the class room sessions, the learners were distributed a questionnaire to analyze their learning experiences during the three exercises. As for the first question, the learners were asked how they got to know about mythical creatures. To this question,

72% of the participants have answered that they were introduced to these characters by their parents during their childhood through children's stories. 54% have stated that they were familiarized with mythical creatures through films and documentaries and through Buddhist jataka tales. 36% of the learners mentioned Sri Lankan folktales and translated European fairy tales as the source of information, and only 18% of the learners selected Disney animated cartoons as their first experience of seeing these characters.

Figure 02: The sources from which learners' knowledge about mythical creatures were influenced.

To examine the impact of learning about European mythical creatures, the learners were asked whether they had changed their image of certain mythical creatures after the class room sessions. The learners had a mixed answer to this question where some have marked yes and some have stated that their image in mind was not harmed by the learning of mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales. But it was noted that they have identified that there is a considerable change in the attributes of mythical figures in Asian and European folklore.

When inquiring whether the learners have observed any similarities or differences between mythical characters in Sri Lanka and in German folktales, some learners have mentioned that Sri Lankan folktales have a limited number of mythical creatures compared to the mythical creatures in German folklore. An interesting answer provided by one of the learners was, that mythical creatures in Sri Lankan folklore tend to be furry creatures who are large in size, and creatures like dwarfs are rarely recognized in Sinhala folklore. In terms of morality, the supernatural beings in Sri Lankan stories are often attributed to evil and harmful actions, yet in German folklore they could also be helpful and bring good luck.

One of the main objectives of this research was to examine the impact of the previous knowledge of learners about mythical creatures. Therefore, when questioning whether the learners have encountered their previous knowledge of supernatural beings

as a plus point or as an obstacle, almost every learner has marked that their previous knowledge of mythical creatures based on Sri Lankan folklore and information they received from digital media were helpful for them to recognize the mythical creatures in Grimm's fairy tales. Yet, the researcher who observed their class room sessions believes, have identified that their previous knowledge was more of an obstacle than an assistance to them. The image of the mythical creatures formed in the learners' mind was based on Sri Lankan folklore. Nonetheless, Sri Lankan folklore, which was heavily influenced by Indian subcontinent myths and legends, contains a wide range of mythical creatures, including Indian deities and supernatural beings. Therefore, the picture that they had visualized was a very complicated image with different mythical creatures from several cultures.

When asked about the learners' opinion about using a reading exercise to teach about the historical background, some learners stated that, it is important to study superstitions related to witches in history in order to understand how this character was created by the brother Grimm, as witches are part of European history. Nonetheless, almost all of the students identified similarities between the medieval witches and the witch character in Grimm's fairy tales, which made them believe that the medieval witch hunt had inspired the Grimm brothers to create their own fairy tale witch character. Therefore, an in-depth study of medieval history was considered essential, by the learners, to critically analyze the contents of the witch character in Grimm's fairy tales.

The learners were then asked why they believe it is important to study mythical creatures when studying folklore literature. This question was used to identify whether the learners had understood why it was necessary to make a huge effort (to spend three class sessions which consisted of more than six hours of lecture) to introduce the mythical creatures of Grimm's fairy tales. Few learners have written that mythical creatures are part of the folklore tradition and folktales without mythical beings do not exist. Apart from that, all the other learners stated that mythical creatures are part of the imagination of a particular group of people or a tribe. Therefore, the students have mentioned that, studying these creatures will allow language learners to become familiar with the beliefs, customs, norms, and ideologies of people from a distant culture.

Discussion of findings

The class room observations have indicated that the Sri Lankan learners' perceptions of mythical creatures are formed through Sri Lankan folktales, Buddhist jataka tales, and through Indian legends. Because of foreign invasions and the arrival of settlers from India since the era of the ancient kingdoms, Sri Lankan mythology has been heavily influenced by Indian myths, with mythical creatures from Indian mythologies accepted as part of Sri Lankan folktales. Apart from that, Sri Lankan children have been familiarized with Sinhala and English translations of myths, legends, and European fairy tales since their childhood. Therefore, the image of the mythical creatures in Sri Lankan German language learners' minds can be considered as a twisted image which is

a combination of Sri Lankan, Indian, and European mythical creatures. Therefore, their previous knowledge of mythical beings is considered by the researcher as an obstacle to the learning process. The learners have mentioned that the image of the fairy witch character reminds them of the Sri Lankan fairy witch character 'bata kola achchi'. The learners describe the character of Bata Kola Achchi as a wicked old woman who practices black magic. Yet, the European witch in Grimm's fairy tale is a more advanced portrayal of a witch character who is not always presented as an old woman, but sometimes as a queen or a beautiful young lady with power and fortune who plays both the roles of a destroyer and a benefactor. Furthermore, the learners have identified similarities between the nymphs and the maidens in the Sigiriya frescos. Some learners have related the nymphs to the 'kinduru and kinduriyo' in Sanda Kinduru Jathakaya, yet nymphs in Sri Lankan literature, are depicted as previous births of Buddha or else as holy deities.

However, in European mythology, nymphs are considered a minor female nature deity who is portrayed as a personification of nature in literature, usually as extremely beautiful maidens. They are believed to be excellent singers and dancers and fortune tellers who can seduce humans through their voice. But they are not considered as holy spirits in European literature, but rather as spirits with twisted personalities who can be good and evil. Therefore, although there is a considerable similarity between the characters in both cultures, each culture has its own perception of the origin of these mythical creatures.

The objective of using images during the first class room session was to introduce the learners to the topic through images and to make them familiar with the basic key words related to the topic. Apart from that, visual materials, which are far more memorable than spoken words or written text, have assisted the learners in bringing back their childhood memories of these mythical creatures .

Yet the first class room session has proven that images are not only sufficient as learning materials when introducing, mythical characters of a distant culture. Therefore, the reading text with guided questions has allowed the learners to engage in an in-depth analysis of the historical background and understand how mythical creatures can be created based on historical incidents. Apart from that, the reading exercise has made the learners aware that the Grimm's witch character has a more historical origin than the Sri Lankan witch character, which was created by the mere fascination of translators who have translated the European fairy tales into Sinhala.

The third class room session, where the learners have conducted group research, has allowed them to engage in self-study without the interruption of the teachers, where they are instructed to find out about the origin of the mythical characters in Grimm's fairy tales through Germanic myths and other suitable online sources.

This exercise was helpful for the learners to decide themselves which materials are more suitable for them for the learning process. By asking the learner to present their findings through a post presentation, the researcher expected the learners' to connect different study materials such as visual and written text materials, and use their creativity to

present the research findings. During the evaluation process, the researcher was impressed to see how the learners had achieved the learning outcomes by using Germanic myths as the primary sources of data collection and how they had carefully used trustworthy online sources for their secondary data collection. Therefore, based on the class room observations and data collected from the questionnaires, the researcher can state that the main learning outcome of the lesson, which was to introduce the learners to mythical creatures in Grimm's Fairy Tales through suitable learning materials, was successfully achieved by incorporating images, reading text materials, and encouraging the learners to engage in self-learning exercises.

Conclusion

According to the findings of the research, it is evident that the mythical creatures are part of the imagination of people which represents their beliefs, customs, traditions, and thinking patterns. The perception of mythical creatures in children's' minds is formed by the oral narrations of the elderly during childhood. The pre knowledge of learners about mythical characters based on native folklore is an obstacle when introducing mythical creatures of a distant culture. Yet it is possible, through the study of carefully selected visual materials such as images, documentaries, and written manuscripts of legends and myths, to become familiar with the mythical creatures of a foreign culture.

References

1. Brauner ,S. (2001). *Fearless Wives and Frightened Shrews: The Construction of the Witch in Early Modern Germany*, University of Massachusetts Press, Amherst
2. Federici, S. (2012). *Witch-Hunting, Past and Present, and the Fear of the Power of Women*, Hate Cantz Verlag, Ostfildern
3. Francisco,S. (2000). "Complex Entities in the Universe of Fairy Tales." *Marvels & Tales*, vol. 14, no. 2, pp. 219–243. *JSTOR*. Available at: www.jstor.org/stable/41388560./ (Accessed 24 June 2021)
4. Gray, H. (2021). *Frau Holle, the Germanic Winter Goddess* | *Hag Stone Journal*. [online] Available at: <https://hagstonejournal.com/frau-holle-the-germanic-winter-goddess/> (Accessed 23 June 2021)
5. Grimm, J., Grimm, W.,(2011). *Grimm's Fairy Tales*, Kindle Edition, Amazon Publishing.
6. Hill, M. (2015). *A Comparative Analysis of Character Depiction in the Grimm's Kinder- und Hausmärchen and Modern Fairytale Adaptations*, Honors Theses, Union College, Schenectady, New York
7. Kemptner, D. (2009). *Sleeping Beauty and her many relatives*, " Thesis, Georgia State University,Atlanta

8. Reynolds, S. (2017). *Grimm Fairy Tales & Their Successors: A Study on Snow White*. [online] Available at: <https://medium.com/@renwald12/grimm-fairy-tales-their-successors-a-study-on-snow-white-4e11fb7d3c77/> (Accessed 22 June 2021)
9. Rieti, B. (2008). *Making Witches: Newfoundland Traditions of Spells and Counterspells*, McGill-Queen's University Press, Montreal & Kingston
10. Tatar, M. (1992). *Off with Their Heads: Fairy Tales and the Culture of Childhood*, Princeton University Press, Princeton
11. Zipes, J. (1987). *The Complete Fairy Tales of The Brothers Grimm*, Bantam Books, New York

Impact of Socioeconomic Factors on Period Poverty in Sri Lanka: Evidence from Selected Rural Area in Kurunegala District

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Abstract:

Period poverty is a raising socioeconomic and health issue today, in both global and national levels. At present, in the Sri Lankan rural society, most of the girls and women are directly facing menstrual problem in their period time and it is a latent phenomenon in every household. The identified research problem for this research is; are there socioeconomic impact on period poverty in rural areas in Sri Lanka? The main objective of this research was to examine whether there is a relationship between the socioeconomic factors and period poverty in rural areas in Sri Lanka. Specific objectives of this study were to identify, the impact of economic and education status on period poverty, impact of taboos on period poverty and the fallouts in existing service delivery system by Sri Lankan government and non-government organization for decreasing period poverty in rural areas. A sample of 110 girls and women from *palugolla 230B Grama Niladari* Division of Kurunegala District in Sri Lanka were selected for this research using systematic random sampling method, and the mix method research approach has been applied. The study revealed that the unavailability of drinking water in the household, Family low income level and lack of access to sanitary products, Lack of sanitation facilities, lack of education about menstruation, cultural beliefs and restrictions during menstruation were the key issues of period poverty related to girls and women in the sample.

Keywords: *Menstrual, Period Poverty, Rural Areas, Socioeconomic*

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Introduction

Period (menstruation) is a natural fact and monthly occurrence for 1.8 billion girls, women, transgender women, non-binary persons of reproductive age all over the globe since they attend their puberty (UNICEF, 2015). It is a normal vaginal bleeding that is a natural part of a healthy monthly cycle for a person with a uterus and ovaries. Every month in the years between puberty (typically age 11–14) and menopause (typically age 45–55) every girl and woman gets period unless they get pregnancy. The average person who menstruates loses about 2–3 tablespoons of blood during their period and the time between periods (last day to first day) typically averages 28 days. Period can last between 3 and 8 days, but it will usually last for about 5 days. The bleeding tends to be heaviest in the first 2 days. Even though a period considers as a natural occurrence, many girls and women of menstruating age are suffering in silence. Millions of menstrual across the world are denied the right to manage their monthly menstrual cycle in a dignified and healthy way. According to the UNICEF “Meeting the hygiene needs of all adolescent girls is a fundamental issue of human rights, dignity and public health” (UNICEF, 2015).

The lack of education on menstruation, as well as having little or no access to essential sanitation for basic hygiene during the menstruation period or feel unable to manage their periods with dignity defined as Period Poverty and it is not a phenomenon that only affects to the developing world but is an issue that women and girls globally are contending with. However, the consequences of period poverty are far more severe in the developing countries especially in nations that have large socio-economic disparities. According to UNICEF, 2.3 million people live without basic sanitation services and in developing countries less than 30% of people have adequate hand washing facilities at home (2015). As a result, it is difficult for women and young girls to manage their periods safely. Menstruation is stigmatized around the world especially in South Asia. Poor menstrual hygiene exhibits risks and has been linked to reproductive morbidities. Moreover, it stops women from reaching their full potential due to miss opportunities crucial to their growth. Young girls who do not receive any education are more likely to enter marriages at early age and experience, early pregnancy, domestic violence, undernourishment and pregnant complications. Period shame has diverse negative mental effects as well. It disempowers women causing them to feel embarrassed about a normal biological process. As a result, women and young girls suffer from a sense of inferiority adding to their mental burden. The cultural shame attached to this natural process and poor access/ shortage of resources stop women from working and going to school every day. Furthermore, most of the chronic reproductive morbidities are associated with poor sanitary hygiene. This has diverse implications as chronic reproductive diseases indicate a continuous expenditure on health which disturbs the financial discipline of the family.

Decreasing period poverty is compulsory to improve menstrual hygiene among young girls and women all over the world, and according to WHO/UNICEF (2012), menstrual hygiene improvement basically based on; women and adolescents girls being able to use clean materials to absorb or collect menstrual blood and to change them in

privacy as often as necessary throughout their menstrual period, Being able to use soap and water for washing the body as required and having access to safe and convenient facilities to dispose of used menstrual management materials, Women and girls having access to basic information about the menstrual cycle and how to manage it with dignity without discomfort or fear. Improved menstrual hygiene is directly linked to fulfilling several of the proposed Sustainable Development Goals (SDG), including Goal 4 (Ensure inclusive and equitable quality education and promote lifelong learning opportunities for all), Goal 5 (Achieve gender equality and empower all women and girls) and Goal 6 (Ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all (UNICEF, 2015).

Problem Statement

Sri Lanka is an island located in South Asia known for its tropical temperatures, rich cultures and diverse wildlife. Sri Lanka has Eastern orientation roots and stigmatization on sexual and reproductive health in extreme levels. Talking and representing those topics in front of the society or communities consider as a socially unacceptable action and try to keep them as secret and highly confidential facts for only limited within the person. Getting period (Menstruation) also related to reproductive health and it also being marginalized as hidden and filthy occurrence which anyone never should not talk with others personally or in front of the society. Like many other nations, Sri Lanka has a long way to go in terms of gender equality. Despite the progressive strides the country has made in the last couple of decades, Sri Lanka is still ranked 102 out of 153 countries in the gender equality index (WHO/ UNICEF, 2012). Period poverty also one of major hygienic and public health issues in Sri Lanka. According to many researches period poverty in Sri Lanka is triggered by three main causes: Inaccessibility to low cost feminine hygiene products, Unavailability of effective educational tools to teach menstrual hygiene and Lack of infrastructure (Water, Sanitation and hygiene facilities within school premises, work places, homes and other public places) to address these specific needs during period (Jayathilake, 2020).

Unlike urban and semi- urban areas period poverty could be high in rural areas due to disparities of resource distribution within the country. According to the existing researches; A significant gap can be seen between urban and rural community in many ways such as communication barriers, quality of education, geographical aspects, opportunities and many more (De Silva, 2013; Manike, 2015; Kumara, 2012). Particular study focused on Kurunegala District, since the district shows some remarkable statistics in poverty rather than other districts except Jaffna, Batticalo, Badulla, Monaragala and Ampara (Department of Census and Statistics, 2009/10).

Recently the period poverty has become an impressive debate in Sri Lankan political campaigns as well. Many of the responsible parties and general public raised their voices against the tax increment on sanitary products considering menstruation as a part of biological process in human body and common to many of the girls and women in the country.

Objectives of the Study

The main objective of this study is to determine whether there is a relationship between the socioeconomic factors and period poverty in rural areas in *Kurunegala* district (230 B *Palugolla Grama Niladari* Division) in Sri Lanka.

Specific objectives are:

- To examine the impact of educational level on period poverty.
- To examine the impact of economic status on period poverty.
- To explore the impact of taboos on period poverty.
- To identify the fallouts in existing service delivery system by Sri Lankan Government, Non-Governmental Organizations, and other responsible organizations for decreasing period poverty in rural areas.

Literature Review

According to data survey of Plan International in 2017, it was found that around half of the girls, aged 14- 21 were still embarrassed by their periods. Almost 71% of girls said they felt embarrassed about buying period products, 1 in 10 girls had been asked not to talk about their periods in front of their parents, only 1 in 5 girls felt comfortable discussing their period with their teacher, further Lucy Russell (UK Campaign Manager, Plan International, 2017) said, Period poverty is a very real challenge facing many girls in the UK and its devastating to hear of the impact it is having on girls' lives, their ability to be themselves and their self-esteem. For too many girls dealing with their period each month is proving a tough challenge- and 21 century Britain, this shouldn't be the case. It is clear that this is a problem of stigma as well as affordability. Girls feel embarrassed by their periods and that can't be right. We need a society wide approach to eradicate the taboo and an education program which addresses the shocking reality that too many girls lack the knowledge and understanding of how to manage their period and are too afraid to ask for advice.

Period poverty is a problem in every country. According to the UNICEF findings, it is a widespread problem in Kenya, 7% of women and girls that they surveyed relying on old clothes, pieces of blankets, chicken feathers mud and newspapers. 46% used disposable pads and 6% used reusable pads. Currently, Australia is leading the way in fighting period poverty by officially removing the tampon tax for residents beginning on 1st January 2019. The Menstrual Equity Non-profit Organization noted that 35 US states have so called tampon tax, where products are subject to a value added levy, unlike other necessities (UNICEF, 2015).

Located off the southern coast of India, Sri Lanka is home to almost 22 million people. 52% of whom are female. Despite its small geographical size, the country ranks 102 out of 153 countries in the gender equality index in 2020. (Gender Gap Report 2020) Gender stereotypes and outdated cultural norms inhibit women from having access to

equal education, employment and economic opportunities. On particularly pressing aspect of gender discrimination is a lack of access to safe and affordable menstrual hygiene in Sri Lanka. In emerging economies such as Sri Lanka, whose pace of development is calculated on infrastructural growth and macro development, socioeconomic aspects often fall through the cracks of the process, especially those related to period poverty, hence it is essential when discussing sustainable development and gender equity that a country's calculation of growth factors beyond just the Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Indicators such as the Human Development Index are more holistic ways of gauging a country's progress because it factors in life expectancy, access to education and Gross National Income per capital. Period poverty refers to the lack of education on menstruation, as well as having no or little access to essential sanitation for basic hygiene during the menstruation period, frequently result in social stigma that exclude women from basic activities such as attending school or work and can lead to physical health risks. Period poverty in Sri Lanka takes the form of association with the impurity of the body. The subject is taboo, creating a culture of fear and misinformation. In a survey from 2015, 66% of girls were going to have a period until their first one occurred. As well as survey found that more than half of Sri Lankan girls had to miss school when they were menstruating and another study found that 60% of teachers associated menstrual blood with impurity. In a survey of adolescent girls in Sri Lanka when asked why they missed school while on their periods, 68% to 81% mentioned pain and physical discomfort and 23% to 40% said that it was due to fear of staining clothes (UNICEF, 2015).

Apart from cultural stigma high cost of hygiene products and unhygienic practices due to inaccessibility cause to increase period poverty in Sri Lanka. In this particular study researchers going to explore the relation between socioeconomic factors which triggered period poverty in rural areas since Sri Lankan rural areas got hit by disparities of resource distribution rather than urban and semi urban areas. Particular research focused on *Palugolla 230 B Grama Niladhari* Division which belongs to *Kotawehera* Divisional Secretariat and this intended area located in Kurunegala district of North Western Province in Sri Lanka.

According to the World Bank Report in 2019, Sri Lanka is still a low- middle-income country with the per capita GDP of USD 3,852 and the total population of 21.8 million. Following 30 years' war which ended in 2009, the economy grew at an average of 5.3 percent during the period 2010- 2019 reflecting peace dividend and a determined policy thrust towards reconstruction and growth, although growth slowed down in the last few years. The economy is transitioning from a predominantly rural based economy towards a more urbanized economy oriented around manufacturing and services. Based on census data from the Department of Census and Statistics (2012), total population of the country is reported as 20,359,439 and Sri Lanka has divided into 9 provinces for the administrative purposes. Majority of population in Sri Lanka is in rural sector (77.4%) urban population share of the country is 18.2 percent while the estate population consists of 4.4 percent. Urbanization is relatively high in Western Province (38.8%) and

very low in North Central (4.0%) and North Western (4.1%) provinces. The highest rural population is reported from North Central Province (96.0%) and secondly reported from North Western Province (95.5%). Statistics revealed only about 8.9 percent of the total population of the country is poor according to the official poverty line (Rs. 3028 real total expenditure per person per month in 2009/2010) this means that income of 8,9 percent of the individuals is inadequate to meet the specific nutritional requirements and to consume other essential non- food items. The contribution of the rural sector to total poverty is 84.7 percent. About 1.53 million individuals are poor in this sector. The number of poor in the estate sector is about 117,000 while the number in urban sector is about 153,000. The number of the poor in the rural sector is ten times higher than that of the estate sector and 13 times than that of the urban sector. Thus, the population of each sector and the total number of the poor reveals that the poverty burden is highest in the rural sector and lowest in the urban sector.

According to the data published by Department of Census and Statistics through its Households Income and Expenditure Surveys in 2009/10 (covered 22 districts out of 25) and 2012/13 as well as poverty indicators in 2016, Kurunegala district shows high statistics in number of poor population and contribution to total poverty. According to the recent statistics in 2016, number of poor population shows as 47930 and contribution to total poverty indicated as 5.7. These numbers only less than other five districts named Kandy, Rathnapura, Batticaloa, Kegalle and Badulla respectively out of 25 districts in the country. This research discussed the socioeconomic factors which affected on period poverty in *Palugolla* GN, in Kurunegala district as selected rural area and further generalized the results as rural areas according to the given above literature review based on the Head Count Ratio(HCR) and Poverty Gap Indexes (PGI) as standard indicators in measuring poverty Nationally as well as Internationally.

Methodology

This research carried out under the mixed method approach for validity, reliability and generalization of the research conclusion. Researches wanted to find out the numeric data such as household's income level and their expenditure, education level, sanitary and hygienic facilities level. There for researchers used quantitative research method to collect numeric data and since menstruation (Period) is a latent topic in rural area more than urban area qualitative research method used to get comprehensive answers and sufficient details as quantitative research cannot explain human feelings, creeds and beliefs and experience of period poverty.

Selection of the Study Area

This particular study focused on rural areas in Sri Lanka and in order to researchers selected Kurunegala District as their study area. Kurunegala district belongs to North Western Province and it is the second highest rural province (95.5%) among the other provinces. According to the data of Department of Census and Statistics through its Households Income and Expenditure Surveys (HIES, 2009/10) remarked poverty

incidents high in Kurunegala District. Another reason to select this area as our study area is, it is a first author's home town and it was convenient for researchers to make necessary arrangement for fieldwork during Covid-19 pandemic. This rational of rural and poverty status was led to conduct the research of socio-economic impact on period poverty in Kurunegala District. Thus we wanted to find out socio-economic impact on period poverty issue and to identify possibilities to overcome this increasing social issue. Then we selected a *Grama Niladari* Division (*Palugolla 230 B – Kotawehera* Divisional Secretariat Division) from the Kurunegala District, North western province in Sri Lanka. Most of the people in this area employed in agriculture and labour sectors and some of them occupy both governmental and private sectors. However, agriculture consider as main economic activity in this GN Division.

Sampling Techniques

In the selected area, there are 334 households and for this study 110 girls and women were responded from 290 different households through systematic random sampling method. As initial step, researchers were taken a list of families that have at least one girl or woman age between 13- 48(age appropriate for having period). Family details were taken from *Grama Niladhari* (GN) as secondary data tools. Researchers were able to select 290 families from total of 334 households and started selection from the first house address that noted as 1 to 290. Then systematic random sampling was carried out remained one interval between two addresses. Through this systematic pattern 145 households were selected out of 290 of total population. The survey questionnaires were used for gathering quantitative data from the 110 girls and women from selected sample size of 145 households since 35 households were rejected to participate for the survey. 10 in-depth interviews were carried out from 05 girls age between 14 - 21 and 05 married women age between 21- 48 for gathering of qualitative data. Although mathematically 3 % of proportion was selected from 290 households for the selection of 10 interviewees that helped to consume time and cost.

Source of Data

Both primary and the secondary data were used for the research purposes. Primary data were collected through structured questionnaire, Interviews with household's girls and women, Personal observation and photography. For the study secondary data was collected from various types of documentations and reports from *Grama Niladari* and Development officer in the GN division, Internet (for get location map etc.), National and International article related to period poverty.

Results and Discussion

This part basically focuses on data presenting, analyses and discussion on affected factors on period poverty.

Family Income Influence on Education and Period Poverty

Income can be defined as a one of the important factor for human beings. According to the gathered data, different family income levels were identified in the sample as given in figure one.

Figure 1: Family Income Level

Source: Field Study (2020)

According to figure 01, there are 44 respondents who have less than SLR 15,000 income per month. 23 have SLR 15,000-25,000 monthly income and 15 of respondents have SLR 25,000 to 35,000 of it. 12 have SLR 35,000-25,000 monthly income and other 6 respondents give monthly family income as more than SLR 45,000.

Figure 2: Level of Education

Source: Field Study (2020)

When considering the education level of the selected area, most of them have primary education (38%). 9 % and 13% of them mentioned maximum level of education is illiterate and able to sign. 28% respondents have secondary level education and 12% of respondents are higher educational qualification.

Figure 3: Use Materials in Periods

Source: Field Study (2020)

The materials which is use their period time can be used to evaluate the period poverty. The figure below shows the main materials of the menstruation. According to the surveyed 58 percent respondents were used sanitary pads, 37% respondents used piece of clothes and 5 percent used other things for their period time.

According to the relevant data a respondent who is the use piece of clothes for their period, explained her ideas when we asked about what is the reason for use this materials her period time like below.

“In our home here are four members have period every month. One packet is not enough for each and at least two packets need for each every month. Then the cost near 1000 rupees and cannot afford that much amount for pads. We used to use piece of clothes at home and use pads for schools when they are schooling” (Field Study, 2020).

This explanation tells us their family income not enough for their livelihood expenditure. Income condition has affected their period adversely and they do not have access to sanitary products. The quotation implies that relationship between monthly family income and period poverty. Further when we considering this situation, respondent’s family income directly effect for their education and period poverty and it can be explain by chi- square test.

Table 01: Identify Family Income on Education and Period Poverty

Variable	X2	Df	P value	Decision
Relationship between family monthly income and education	26.828	16	0.043	Accepted
Relationship between family income and use materials of period	17.130	8	0.029	Accepted

Source: Field Study (2020)

According to the results shown in table 1, respondent’s monthly income significantly affects for their education and period poverty.

Household's Condition and Period Poverty

Dwelling home is one of the basic needs of the human beings. According to the data some of them do not have financial facilities to develop their house. They build their houses with bank loans. But this situation have affected on period poverty and here you can see one of the 16 years old respondent's explanation regarding her period issues.

"In this home, there are two families live together. My mother has been in abroad for five years and my father works in Colombo. I am 16 years old and I don't have separate room at my home. At least there are no proper doors for any room. When I get period, it is really difficult to change pads comfortably without a proper space. Feel to leave this home and go to friend's home." (Field Study, 2020)

When considering her answer, she has said directly she cannot live in this house. Because of does not good situation to change her sanitation pads during her period time. The houses do not have proper facilities (Observation: There are no proper doors for many houses in this selected sample) and enough room for all family members of the households in rural are linked period poverty.

Sanitation and Infrastructure Facilities of Toilet Units

Sanitation and infrastructure facilities are can be defined as an evaluation method of the people living standard. Especially these facilities related to the women's menstruation health condition. Considering the toilets facilities of the sample there are 71% respondents use pour flush toilets and 28% use cistern flush toilets. About one respondent use wood which located back at home as her toilet. According to her answer we could understand her toilet was very old one and not proper to use and she do not have asset to build the toilet. Thus when we considering the survey sanitation facilities are not in proper condition in the most of the housing units. (Observation: Many of house in this village took electricity for their toilets illegally and many toilets built separately at outside. As well as most of them have not proper doors and those toilets make insecurity feel at night as well as day time). Furthermore, some houses are in good condition but they don't have water and electricity facilities adequately inside their toilets.

Figure 4: Water and Electricity Facilities Inside the Toilets

Source: Field Study (2020)

The questionnaire survey revealed that 61% of the households do not have water facilities and about 39% percent of the households have water facilities inside their toilets. 43% have electric facilities and about 57% respondents do not have electric facilities inside their toilets.

Furthermore considering the water supply in this study area most of them used water from community based water development project in area and some of them used well's water. However the respondents are not satisfied with the water supply. Because of their faced many problems during dry seasons. Many people said that they are receiving water is too brackishness and do not proper to drink. So they bring water from filter service in village (One Litre is SLR 2) Thus the irregular water supply is one of the very complex social issue in rural area and directly this problem is very much related to the menstruation (period) poverty.

Under qualitative research method interviews were carried out by the researchers and they collected information related social stigma and taboos. For the convenient of data analysis main topic divided into two themes and again divided into sub themes for organizing gathered data easily.

Societal stigma and taboos related period poverty

Main theme: Rituals and customs

Sub theme: Celebrate puberty and related rituals during first occurrence of blood

In rural areas in many countries people practice some rituals and customs when someone attained puberty, they follow those rituals and customs by generation to generation and sometimes they compel to practice them without modern society's consents. Especially in South Asian countries these kind of practices are high since they have rituals based cultures. One of our two interviewees said,

"When a girl got her first occurrence of blood, we keep her in a locked room, never let her to see a man's face even her father or brothers. We keep her inside at least a week and we check her horoscope and make auspicious time for first bathing after the puberty, after have bath we guide her to follow some rituals according to our belief system such like bath from herbal water, break a pot, cut the tree which has milk like jack fruit or any, break the coconut and many other rituals".

"I have three daughters and I never let them to go outside after 5 at the evening when they have periods. We believe evening and night time not good for unmarried girls and women who has their periods, because some invisible demons called "Kalu Kumaraya" can be come to them and tortured them when their bodies are impurity" (Field Study, 2020).

According to the interviewees, it was after the ceremony they were confined to home for a period raging from fifteen days to three months and during that time was not allowed to meet any males. However, the important fact is it seems that almost every Sinhala girl irrespective of class differences experiences the rituals and celebration of puberty.

Audrey Richards (1956) in her book, *Chisungu*, on female imitation ceremony among the Bemba of Zambia points out that rituals, rites and symbols in such ceremonies are connected with sex, fertility, matrimony/motherhood and subordination. Though there is no overt expression of such ideas it is clear that the Sri Lankan ceremony of puberty is connected with those. Hence, it is not a surprise that the ceremony is still in practice and regarded as only second importance to a girl's marriage.

Main theme: Myths and beliefs

Sub theme: Impurity of the body

Majority of people in Sri Lanka think, menstruation blood is bad or unhealthy blood which discharge from the female body in every month. But according to the UNICEF/WHO period blood isn't rejected bloody fluids or the body's way of flushing out toxins. It has evolved vaginal secretion- there's a little bit of blood, uterine tissue, mucus lining and bacteria. Because of the contain period blood is very different from blood that moves continuously through the veins. It's less concentrated blood. It has fewer blood cells than ordinary blood. In this study interviewees responded that period blood is purely impure and unhealthy.

"I'm 15 years old and my mother always say, avoid worship to Lord Buddha or go to temple or any other religious places when I have periods. She says that period blood is impure and here older people called "kili" for that period blood" (Field Study, 2020).

This situation in the above mentioned can be understood she have no opportunity worship lord Buddha and any other religious activities during her menstrual time and regarding the influence of parental traditional beliefs and thinking for girls menstruation.

Sub theme: Avoid some selected food such like meat, fish and fried food

According to Doshi (1995), "Food is a bio-chemical process and products which sustain life. But is not merely the source of bio-chemical needs; it also has a cultural dimension which helps a person to determine his food and nutrition habits and choices" (Doshi, 1995, p.11). Food can be defined as a one of the significant needs for human sustain body. Thus Sri Lanka which is south Asian society, food behaviour and consumption are significant tools in period poverty. When we consider about effect of food behaviour to period poverty, it is essential to study about how women and girls select their foods during their periods.

"Now I'm 45 years old and since my puberty I have never eaten chicken, fish, egg or even one fried chili. We believe when we eat those things they cause to make blood smelly and invisible powers can be come to us".

Another interviewee said,

"My mother never let me to eat chicken, fish, egg and fried food when I have period. Normally I have periods for three, four days, all those days I eat food that

only cooked from coconut milk. Sometimes I hate to eat like this, but I should obey to my mother's word, she is my mom and they also follow those food behaviours like us, sometimes there could be some truth behind these avoidance". (Field Study, 2020)

According to the respondents' replies most of them used traditional food behaviour of their period time and parents are influencing to their daughters' food consumption. Thus food habits play an important role in identifying period poverty and it is an important fact which influence the period poverty in rural area in Sri Lanka. It had been proven through the above statements of the 45 years old women and 18 years old school girl.

Sub theme: Avoid Bathing

Avoid bathing in during menstrual period is another important variable that influence for the period poverty in rural area. Some think that having a bath or even taking a shower during your period is unsafe. According to the health experts there is no any rational for not having bathing during the periods. But this thought goes by generation to generation in Sri Lankan context.

"I'm 38 years old and work as an account in a private company, after I got this job I live in Colombo and come to village at weekends, still I try to avoid have a bath at first day of my period, since I feel and believe if I have a bath on first day I will get severe headache. This not only a belief, actually I experienced this kind of headache in two times because of had a bath."

"My mother and grandmother don't allow me to have a bath on first two days when I got periods. These days are really awful and embarrassing myself since I feel I'm dirty and filthy, if I have school and extra classes this awful feeling would be doubled". (Field Study, 2020)

The women who stated the above statement, think that having a bath during their period is unsafe and this beliefs affect their health. When we consider above statement of the school girl, her mother and grandmother have controlled her bathing during menstrual time. Thus, we can realize that, beliefs also affects period poverty in rural areas.

To examine fallouts in existing service system by Sri Lankan Government NGOs and other organizations for decreasing period poverty

In Sri Lanka sanitary pads consider as semi luxury product and making it inaccessible to the majority of women and girls in the country. Prior to September 26, 2018 sanitary pads were taxed 101.2% following the removal of certain tariffs that tax fell to 62.60% and to a further 52% following the vat reform. Although one may argue that taxation has fallen making it more accessible, reality of the situation is that 52% is still too high. (Galappaththi & Gunasekara, 2020).

"...We are farmers and our monthly income is too low, money for the one sanitary pad packet even we can't afford, there are four members need pads for each month, if government or any other authorized institution may give pads for free or low cost as we can afford, we also love to use them".

“I’m 13 years old and last year I attained puberty. Due to high cost my parents can’t afford the amount for sanitary napkins every month. I use piece of clothes and still I don’t know how to wear it properly, often it has gotten leak and my school uniform get stain from the blood, I feel embarrass and I don’t like to go to school when I have period. My school is a mix school and I feel ashamed and I always try to hide myself when I get stains in my school uniform” (Field Study, 2020).

The lack of proper water, sanitary and hygiene facilities within the school premises, workplaces and general public act as a strong deterrent for women and girls to engage in normal daily activities. Especially in *Palugolla Grama Niladhari* Division already beaten by this water problem.

Having considered the above mentioned analysis, the following findings are emphasized.

- The study area has a high level economic instability. Most of them have not significant monthly income and that scarcity is linking negative impact on their education system and period poverty.
- The study revealed that most of the households not complete. Because of their low income level, they not have proper housing unit to live. Further they do not have enough rooms for family members and is a basic impact on period poverty.
- Another important fact we found, there are no any water supply from national water supply and drainage board. Therefore they are using water from community based water project in this area. However, they haven’t regular water supply and they are not satisfied about it. Many people said that they are not receiving water daily and it is very brackishness. So all the villagers use filter service for drinking water purpose.
- The study revealed that sanitation facilities are not in good condition. Many toilets do not have water inside them, proper door and electricity. Thus this condition directly effects on period poverty in rural area in Sri Lanka.
- In this area most of the girls miss their school during period time due to lack of sanitary facilities for change and throw their sanitary pads in toilets in school premises.
- We found many cultural religious beliefs follow by people regarding menstruation. Ways of food consumption, sexual intercourse, bathing, celebrate puberty and related rituals during first occurrence of blood, rituals all the experience affected on period poverty in rural areas more than urban area in Sri Lanka. This beliefs and practices were all interrelated to the period hygiene management.
- Accordingly the study when we evaluate present existing service by government and non-government organization for decreasing period poverty in rural areas, programs related period poverty and period hygiene management have not conducted and provided considerable help to overcome the period poverty situation.

Recommendation to Overcome the Period Poverty

To eliminate issues on period poverty could be unsuccessful until increase accesses for sanitary products, increase level of education regarding menstrual health and develop a policy which accepted menstrual as a common biological process for every girls, women, transgender women, non- binary persons of reproductive age in all over the country. Government should introduce appropriate policy and legal framework for management of menstrual poverty. Existing taxes are the one of the main barriers against eliminate the period poverty. Fortunately in 2018 tariff levied became to less from previous amount and responsible parties have started to raise their voices for further decrement of tax on sanitary products. This initiative should be become as legally embedded and should be promoted gender equality through new policy. Meanwhile developing a National policy for the diminishing or cut off of taxation and tariffs on sanitary products there should be initiative pilot projects giving priority for the under privileged groups in society, as example at initial step *Samurdhi* beneficiaries and disable people should be have free distribution of sanitary products. Distribution of menstrual products should be free of cost in schools and other education institute in Sri Lanka. Financial support should be given to the institutions to carry out the researches in the related of period poverty in rural areas in Sri Lanka. Non-government organization should come forward to educate rural people about menstruation, diseases related to poor hygiene, importance to toilets facilities etc. Make guidance to start self-development and Agriculture sector in rural area should be developed under a strategic plan focused on economic development in Sri Lanka. Based on the GAD (Gender and Development) projects should be established to address gender issues in rural areas. Menstrual hygiene management should be include an integral part of Sri Lankan education curriculum and both male and female teachers should be well educated about menstruation and menstrual hygiene management. Proper water supply projects and facilities should be conducted in rural areas in Sri Lanka as a solution to water problem. As well as government and non-government sectors should encourage local entrepreneurs to manufacture sanitary products inside the country. Therefore start loan facilities for local manufactures through government as well as private banks would be an effective step for continuing production process.

Conclusion

Menstrual is a natural and normal process. It is not just a women or girl's issue. But it is still a taboo and in Sri Lankan traditional society as it is considered unclean, impure and dirty. Furthermore income level directly affected on period poverty in rural areas in Sri Lanka. When period poverty in rural area could be identified as the depended variable of the present study and many independent variables, which can be considered as factors of economic, education, taboos and existing service delivery system by government and non-government organization, were identified. Finally this study identified that have a significant relationship between socioeconomic factors and period poverty in rural area in Sri Lanka.

Limitations and Future Directions

Due to COVID 19 Pandemic researchers had to limit time duration of interviews and limited of probing questions. Observations from gestures and postures also would be hidden hence respondents had to wear masks according to the health guidelines. Since in this area, period (menstruation) consider as secret and unethical to talk in front of the society, majority of respondents of interviews do not allow researchers to record their thoughts, opinions and free views regarding period and their real situation.

As future directions, researchers should be done more researches on period poverty in rural and estate sectors since those areas have already threaten by the disparity of the resources which help someone to maintain quality life. In Sri Lanka there should be created a common platform for abolish gender inequality with help of government and non-government sectors. A step towards gender sensitive budgetary proposals would reflect lifting such barriers and taking action to stop the passing inhibitive budgetary reforms for women and girls.

Since period poverty could be affected on every dimensions of quality of life such as social, financial, environmental, psychological, spiritual and occupational and ultimately on total wellbeing, professionals and activists such as educators, social activists, social workers, doctors and health officers, lawyers and policy makers, parliamentarians and many other professionals should raise their voices against issues on menstruation. The right to overcome period poverty should involve women's participation in developing policies and it should not left to a Sri Lankan parliament that consists 95 percent of male representatives.

As responsible citizens and women it is our duty to continue the discourse on period poverty until Sri Lanka sees progressive positive changes because improving of quality of life must be both sustainable and inclusive without any discrimination.

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References

- Allen, K. R. Goldberg, A. E. *Sexual activity during menstruation: A qualitative study*. 2009. 46(6), 535-545.
- Delaney, J. Lupton, M. J. and Toth, E. (1988). *The curse: A cultural history of menstruation*. University of Illinois Press.
- Department of Census and Statistics. (2009/2010/2016). *Poverty Indicators, Household Income and Expenditure Survey Report*: Department of Census and Statistics, Ministry of Finance and Planning, Sri Lanka. Accessed on 2-1-2021. <https://www.statistics.gov.lk/>
- De Silva, I. (2013). *Endorsements versus returns: Counterfactual quantile decomposition of urban-rural inequality in Sri Lanka*, Asian Development Bank, Colombo, Sri Lanka.
- Doshi, S. L. (1995). *Anthropology of food and Nutrition*: India, Rawat Publications.
- Galappaththi, p. and Gunasekara, D. (2020). *The conversation around period poverty in SL: The Sunday morning*, Accessed on 10-1-2021. <https://www.themorning.lk/donttaxmyperiod-the-conversation-around-period-poverty-in-SL>
- Garg, R. Goyal, S. and Gupta, S. *India moves towards menstrual hygiene: subsidized sanitary napkins for rural adolescent girls issues and challenges*. *Matern Child Health J* 2012: 16(4).
- Jayathilake, L. (2020). *The Health Cost of Period Poverty*, *Groundviews: Journalism for citizens*, accessed on 27-12-2020. <https://groundviews.org/2020/12/08/the-health-cost-of-period-poverty/>
- Kuhlman, A. S. Henry, K. and Wall, L. L. *menstrual hygiene management in resource-poor countries*. *Obstet Gynecol Surv* 2017: 72(6).
- Kumara, T. (2012). *Decomposing spatial inequality in Sri Lanka: A quantile regression approach*, *Inequalities and Development: new challenges new measurements?* Bordeaux, France, University of Bordeaux.
- Manike, H. A. (2015). *Rural-urban disparity in Sri Lanka*, *IPASJ International Journal of Management*: 1-12.
- Richards, A. (1982). *Chisungu: A Girl's Initiation Ceremony Among the Bemba of Zambia*, Taylor and Francis.
- Sharma, N. Sharma, P. Wavare, R. R. and Gautam, B. A cross-sectional study of knowledge , attitude and practices of menstrual hygiene among medical students in north India. *Int J Phytopharm* 2013: 2(5).
- UNICEF Annual Report, (2012/2015). Accessed on 1-1-2021. www.unicef.org/publications
- WHO Annual Report, (2015). Accessed on 12-2-2021. <https://www.who.int/gho/en/>
- World Bank Report, (2019) *Sri Lanka poverty assessment*, World Bank, Washington DC, Accessed on 21-2-2021. <https://www.worldbank.org/en/country/srilanka/overview>

Glass Beads in Ancient Ruhuna

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Abstract:

Bead making and trading of beads is one of the oldest industries in the world. Beads are small, colourful, symmetrical, and often quite beautiful. They are frequently standardized, inexpensive units that can be arranged in almost endless configurations. They can be seen not only in familiar forms of necklaces and bracelets but also on anklets, headbands, and headdresses. Beads are small, but important finds from Archaeological investigations. Especially, the discovery of beads creates enormous interest among the excavator, researchers and layman. It provides excellent information to the understanding of various aspects of the human past. While a couple of studies surmise of bead production no study has been confined to study bead making industry of Ancient Ruhuna. Therefore, the purpose of this study is to examine if there was a glass bead making technology in Ancient Ruhuna.

Keywords: *Glass Beads, Bead Technology, Product, Colour Bead*

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Introduction

Sri Lankan context, there is a dearth of historical accounts on ancient bead production, the origin of sources of raw materials, and on the communities involved in the industry. Despite of lack of historical sources on beads thousands of them are attested from excavations and explorations in Sri Lanka. A probe into literature revealed that previous research on beads found in Sri Lanka is very scarce. Sources of raw materials used to produce this array of beads have not been clearly identified so far. While few studies have taken place on beads aimed at providing typological aspects, some describes about trade links discovered by beads.

A Handful of studies whilst investigating the beads found in the particular excavations suggest the local bead production in Ancient Sri Lanka. For an example, on the basis of waste materials found in Gedige excavation Deraniyala (1972) implies there would have been local bead making in Ancient Sri Lanka. Coningham (2006) providing more concrete evidence on the basis of Anuradhapura Salgahawatta British Sri Lankan Excavations hypothesized about bead-making at the site. Although not much attention is paid to Ancient Ruhuna until recent past in archaeological perspective, thousands of beads attested from the sites such as Ridiyagama, Akurugoda and Godawaya etc. indicate that beads have played a significant role in many aspects of the life of the community of Ancient Ruhuna. Therefore, more recent efforts can be seen in discussing the evidence on bead making in Ancient Ruhuna by scholars such as Bopearachchi (1995), Hannibal-Deraniyala (2001), and Somadeva (2006). The Tissamaharama Archaeological Research Area is one of the major trading centers in the Southern Province of Sri Lanka and a prominent place for a major beads manufacturing center.

Methodology

Beads can be pointed out as the main materials of the research paper. In here, the research is conducted in several stages. The first phase discusses glass beads and their technology, while the second phase collects data from previous research reports in the research area. The glass bead making technology that existed in this research area is being studied. In here, the study of glass bead technology found in Tissamaharama is based on the evidence of ancient glass bead production in India. Under the final stage, a glass bead technology related to Tissamaharama will be discussed.

Results and Discussion

Glass Beads Technology

Silica (Si) in the form of quartz sand (SiO_2) is the most common metalloid used in glass. Glass is amorphous, without a crystalline structure (Francis, 1988/1989:1-21). Because the melting point of pure silica was too high for ancient furnaces to achieve, a flux, generally an alkali (usually soda [Na_2O] or potash [K_2O]) was (and still is) added to lower the melting point. Lime (CaO) or some other stabilizer must also be added. The ancients may not have known this; the lime was nearly always present as an impurity in the sand (Turner, 1956:10-21). These ingredients are heated for several days, forming a

dark, hard substance called “frit” Glassmakers break this up, add some scrap glass (cullet) and perhaps colorants, and then heat the mixture again. As if by magic, it melts and flows, and molten glass results. When glass is first made, it is translucent green because of the universal impurity of iron in both ferric and ferrous states. This color is called “bottle green,” because cheap bottles are made from this untreated glass. Many substances, chiefly metallic oxides, are added to impart various properties to glass. The most common additives are the colorants. With only iron or copper and the proper handling of the furnace (blowing air into it, muffling it, or leaving it open) nearly every colour may be archived.

Special colorants, notably cobalt (Co) and manganese (Mn), have been used since antiquity. Even tiny amounts of cobalt yield a pleasing dark blue. Manganese in small quantity produces pink, which cancels out “bottle green” and clarifies the glass, earning it the name “glassmaker’s soap” Larger amounts produce violet. Antimony, tin, and arsenic were employed as opacifiers. Black glass is usually deep green or violet, made with large amounts of iron or manganese; an organic black glass also exists. Many colorants have been experimented with in recent centuries as the science of chemistry has developed (Weyl; Woldemar, 1959:10-25). The most important other additive to glass is lead. Lead is a glass former, and glass with 90 percent lead has been recorded. Lead makes glass softer, easier to melt and cut, and more brilliant, especially when used with potash. Lead also aids in dissolving other metals added to colour the glass.

The most ancient and universal way to make a glass bead is by “furnace-winding. A worker reaches into a furnace with an iron rod (a mandrel) and forms a peak of glass atop the batch held in a crucible. From the peak, he builds a bead on the mandrel by twisting it in the glass. He can decorate the bead with other colours or shape it with a paddle or other tool. After the bead has been worked, he gives it a final heating. The bead can be knocked off the mandrel during a brief period when the iron cools and contracts faster than the glass. It is deposited into an annealing chamber, where it cools slowly. Cold glass can be heated at a fire and dripped onto a wire or other mandrel in a process called “drip-winding”. In recent centuries, concentrated heat sources have been developed that allow workers to heat a glass rod (cane) and wind the soft glass around a wire; this is called “lamp-winding”. Drip-and lamp-wound beads are not easily detached from the mandrel, so the mandrel is coated with a separator to help release the bead; the separator is often detectable.

The other Major category of glass beads are “drawn” cut from tubes that have been pulled or drawn out from a hollow gather of glass and usually heated to round them off. The drawn beads of interest here are Indo-Pacific beads. There are several minor techniques used to make glass beads “Segmented” beads are made by constricting a heated tube to form bulges that are cut apart as single or multiple beads. The only archaeologically confirmed tools to make these are stone blocks with grooves in one face (Rodziewicz; Mieczyslaw, 1984: 25/75). “Folded” beads are made by heating one or two plaques of glass, bending them around a wire, and joining the edges. “Pierced” beads are made by a heated plaque in the center and forming a bead. “Melded” beads include mosaic and other types made by joining several pieces of glass around a mandrel. Glass bead manufacturing

techniques produce distinct characteristics, providing clues to the origin of the beads. Most of these clues can be recognized by an informed examination of the bead. With practice, some colorants can be identified by sight. Fluorescence under ultraviolet light is a helpful tool. Lead glass can be detected by determining the specific gravity of the bead. Chemical glass analysis can be very useful, but must be interpreted properly (Francis, 1989:1-5). All wound glass beads have the fabric of the glass and any small bubbles (called “seed”) oriented around the perforation. Furnace-wound beads generally have a thin layer of black iron oxide deposited by the mandrel in their perforations. Drip and lamp-wound beads often have powdery deposits of the separator. All such deposits may be removed by friction in time. In drawn beads, the glass is oriented along the perforation. These beads have no perforation deposits and are generally less decorative than wound beads. Segmented beads are hollow; folded and melded beads have seams.

Fig, Glass beads in Tissamaharma

Glass Beads in Ancient Ruhuna

Archaeological sites around the Ruhuna confirm the evidence for the manufacture of glass beads. In the study of the technology of the glass, the evidence found in Tissamaharama is highlighted for the ancient Ruhuna Archaeological site. Accordingly, the factors found in Tissamaharama are very important in the study of glass technology in Ruhuna.

In 2001 KAVA Project published the results and analysis of Tissa-Akurugoda excavation under the title of Ancient Ruhuna: Sri Lankan-German archaeological project in the southern province by H.J. Weisshaar et. al. This publication shed a leading light on to the research on beads of Sri Lanka, providing two significant articles on the beads found from *Tissa Akurugoda* excavation.

Production methods that are used to this day in Indian workshops for making beads come from a long tradition, stretching back to ancient times and can shed light on how the drawn and the wound beads from *Tissamaharama* were made. The drawn beads were mostly prepared by the ladha method, details of which are given by Francis and Stern. A mass of glass, around 50kg, softened in a furnace, was attached to the end of a long iron and rolled until it was forming a cone and placed in the kiln.

With the help of a metal hook the tip of the cone was slowly pulled out of the kiln by one or two men drawing it out between them. Later on the glass tube was broken into longer pieces and, depending on the desired bead size, divided into small segments. To

round off the sharp edges of the segments they were returned to a small kiln, where they were heated and stirred with care taken to keep them separate.

In terms of glass bead production, no site has recorded ample number of glass wasters in Ancient Ruhuna. Glass beads discovered in Ancient Ruhuna reveal three techniques followed to produce monochrome and polychrome glass beads. They are namely: Drawn, wound and multi-technique.

Wound beads

They melt one of the glass rods at one end and fold it round a copper or iron wire, which they hold in the other hand. When the glass ring is closed round the wire, the rest of the rod is cut off and the wire with the glass ring is turned and heated till the ring is nicely round or oval in shape. When three or five rings have been turned around the wire it is laid aside to cool. In cooling the metal contracts more than the glass and the beads can be stripped off. According to the diameter of the wire, we get a wide or narrow perforation. When the wire tapers, the perforation will taper too, which often happened in the old days, then, too, the heat was often not strong enough to melt a thick rod of glass and larger beads could only be made by winding a rod of 1 or 2 mm diameter several times around the tapering wire or other core. We must, therefore, emphasize a division between simple wound and multiple wound beads. The latter will in several places be the oldest glass beads known (Francis, 2002).

Fig. Wound Bead

The reader will easily understand that this way of making beads is a very tedious one as every single bead must be made singly by hand. Most ornamented beads, which we will treat later, are made thus singly by hand. This newer process has made a much more mechanical method, that gave us the bead, drawn bead was later discovered, and beads since the beginning of our era. Moreover, it is not only the simple globular or oval bead that can be drawn. drawn beads may when still hot, easily be modelled into barrels or cubes or cylinders, prisms, etc., by pressing them with metal objects or by using

small moulds, for instance of melon bead form, fastened on the end of pincers, already been described and figured by Antonio Neri (1612) in his *L'Arte Vetraria* (Van der Sleen, 1974:19-30).

Wound beads can be produced in two ways, either with an iron rod, known as mandrel, where a small amount of glass is taken from the main mass and wound around the tip (so called “furnace winding” or “glass is taken up in a scoop” and a small amount of glass is trailed around the iron rod, being known as “scoop winding”. The tip of this rod was prepared so that the glass would not stick to the iron. The still soft glass was shaped now, for with a small flat paddle. Because the iron rod cooled more quickly than the glass, the beads could be slipped off it and had to cool slowly. Special forms of wound beads comprise the pressed monochrome ones, called “round tablet beads with raised edge and centre” by Francis and are named “stupa beads”. These beads presumably had a thin collar around the string hole on both sides, in most cases now broken off, as seen in the seven samples from Court’s Garden. Beads with a blue-white-blue colour combination could be, according to Francis, either twisted or folded. Folding involves bending coloured glass stripes together over a metal rod leaving a seam

Fig. 02 .Drawn Bead

Drawn beads

Before the lump of red-hot glass is taken out of the furnace with an iron bar, it must have been decided whether drawn or wound beads are to be made. To make drawn beads the man who took the glass on his bar will take another bit of iron and work the lump of red-hot glass into a sort of funnel, which he then closes again, so that a large air bubble is included in the glass (Francis, 2002). Then the second iron is taken away again by the second man and now it is not a glass that comes into existence but a great length of glass tube. This long tube is cut or broken into 90 cm. lengths and a bundle of these tubes is chopped into pieces of 3 mm. or 12 mm, each little piece being a small cylindrical tube, that may be called a bead. Of course, the process is not as simple as I describe it, but it can be readily understood each tube, however long it is, will be reduced in a few minutes to perfect beads. Perfect? Well, the sharp corners must be polished off, but this, too, can be done mechanically, tens of thousands in one revolving barrel. In the bead-trade most

of the drawn beads are called pound beads, as they are generally sold by weight and not by number. These beads are often ground with sharp sand in tumbling-machines that turn them from real cylinders into oblates and even globular beads.

Drawn beads can be ornamented, too, with very few manipulations. We find, for instance, red beads with a white core. To make these the hot bulb of white glass in which an air-filled cavity has already been formed, is rolled over a marble plate to smooth (marver) it. Then it is rolled over a plate of half-molten red glass which sticks to it and when the mass is drawn out, a red bead with a white core is the result, a bead thought so beautiful by natives that only one tea-spoonful of these small beads was taken as payment for a full day's work in about 1900 (Francis, 2002).

The same result may be reached by dipping the hollow bulb of white glass in a crucible containing molten red glass, that will gather around the white glass so that a tube, drawn out from the bulb, will show the same result, viz. red on white glass, that can be cut down to red on white beads.

Another way of ornamenting drawn beads is to lay different coloured strips of glass over the air-filled bulb of glass before drawing out begins. This produces the striped beads that are so often seen. In the first few centuries of our era globular beads were pinched off from the viscous tube of glass with a pair of pincers, resembling those used to make ice-cream balls, but smaller. In this way segmented beads were made in a long row. These would be broken or sawn into single beads, but often two or three beads were left together. We find this form in the Roman gold-leaf beads and in a blue variety too. Many of the well-known Roman blue melon beads have been made this way. These kinds of beads are sometimes wrongly called moulded beads, but in glass terminology, moulded objects are blown into a form or mould, which I do not think was ever done with such small objects as beads.

Sometime as many as six layers of different coloured glass are wound around the hollow glass bulb and when the mass thus formed is drawn out ground and polished chevron beads (rosette or star beads) will be the result. Some people talk and write about cane beads, meaning cylindrical tube-beads, but a cane is a stick or rod and can never be cut into tubular beads. There are however a few other methods of beads fabrication which we have to consider, namely folded, pressed, spiral, blown and hand perforated beads.

Accordingly, the technique involves pulling a glass rod out of a gather of hot glass and cutting the rods into small segments. Beads are then reheated to remove sharp edges that resulted from cutting. Use of this technique is reported from Kopai site, Uttar Pradesh of Northern India about 700 B.C. (Kanungo & Brill, 2009:11-25), and around 500 B.C. in Arikamedu, situated in southeastern part of India. Production of drawn glass beads is still practiced in Papanaidupet, India, following ancient techniques.

Drawn beads are quick and simple to produce, unlike the more difficult wound beads. Over 70% of the glass beads from *Akurugoda* were produced from drawn glass rods, 339 pieces had edges left unrounded. At *Akurugoda* little pieces of glass tubes were formed into simple shapes such as oblate, barrel or tubular beads. To produce

“collar” beads, which according to Francis “beads decorated with an extra bit of material surrounding the two perforations”, the gently heated glass tubes were shaped (for example in round or barrel shapes) with a paddle. “Groove-collar” beads have a groove near the string hole slightly engraved by a flat tool, “lug-collar” beads a more exaggerated groove and both ends are pinched, resulting in a collar and standing further out from the body of the bead.

Besides the monochrome drawn beads there are also those with two layers. This “layering” technique is described as follows by Kidd: a small lump of glass was attached to a blowing-rod and then blown hollow. The glass was then immersed in a mass of glass of either the same colour or, as in samples found at *Tissamaharama*, of another colour. These beads, also known as Cornalined’Aleppo, were found in *Akurugoda* and Court’s Garden only in the two-colour variety. In *Tissamaharama* Court’s Garden segmented beads consist of several oblate-circular beads joined by a narrow central bridge. One assumes that a reheated longer tube was gently squeezed with something like small pliers at regular, as in the production of gold-glass. From this row single or groups of beads could be broken off. striped beads were produced, according to bronson, by putting a hot glass cylinder on a thin metal rod and rolling it over thin strips which were pressed into its surface” Now the glass cylinder was cut into smaller pieces and reheated to round off the edges.

Conclusions

This research is mainly based on a study of beads. Tissamaharama has been explored and excavated many times until now, and a number of beads, raw material, and fragments were found here. The manufacturing process and the technology of the beads are an important milestone in the study of beads. Making of beads requires specialized skills, equipment and tools. It is a noticeable fact that the methods of the manufacturing of beads had reached a highly developed stage in the beads found in Ancient Ruhuna. Raw materials and skills for bead production must have arrived Southern coasts through these commercial links. Therefore, diffusion of knowledge, skills as well as manpower required for bead production must have been transmitted rapidly as a result of trading and seafaring activities during the time.

Reference

- Alok K. K. (2004) *Glass Beads in Ancient India and Furnace-Wound Beads at Purdalpur: An Ethnoarchaeological Approach*, Asian Perspectives 43(1).
- Basa. K.K. (1992). *Early glass Beads in India*. South Asian Studies,
- Dubin, L. S. (1995). *The History of Beads from 30,000 B.C. to the Present*. New York.
- Francis Jr, P. (1989). *Beads and The Bead Trade in Southeast Asia*. 1st Edn., Center for Bead Research, Lake Placid, N.Y.
- Francis, P. (1982). *Experiments with early techniques for making whole shells into Beads*, Current Anthropology Chicago, Ill., 23(6).

- Francis, P. (2002). *Asia's Maritime Bead Trade: 300 B.C. to the Present*. Honolulu: University of Hawaii Press.
- Francis, P. (1984). *Some Observations on the Glass Beads of Arikamedu*, *Revue Historique de Pondichery*.
- Francis, P. J.; Ghana. (1994). *West Africa: Where Beads are Love. Lake Placid: The Center for Bead Research*. 1993/ Francis, P. J.; African Trade Beads, *Antique Trader Weekly* 3 8(20).
- Francis, P. J. (1990). *Glass Beads of China*; *Arts of Asia* 20(5).
- Francis, P. J. (1982). *The Glass Beads of India*, *The World of Beads Monograph Series 7*, Lake Placid.
- Francis, P. J. (1988). *The Glass Trade Beads of Europe: Their Manufacture, Their History, and Their Identification*, *The World of Beads Monograph Lake Placid, Series 8*.
- Francis, P. (2004). 'Beads and Selected Small Finds from the 1989-1992 Excavations', *In The Ancient Port of Arikamedu: New Excavations and Researches*, Begley, V. Francis, P., (eds.)
- Francis, P. (1992). *Easy Steps to Identifying Most Beads in Most Collections*, New York: Lapis Route Books.
- Francis, P. (1994). *African Trade Beads*, *Antique Trader Weekly* 3 8(20).
- Francis, P. (1994). *Beads of the World*; *Schiffer*, Atglen, PA.
- Francis, P. (1990). *Glass beads in Asia*, part II, Indo-Pacific beads; *Asian Perspectives* 29(1).
- Francis, P. (1982). *A Handbook of Bead materials*; *WBMS 6*. Lake Placid; N.Y, Lapis Route.
- Van der Sleen, W. G. N. (1973). *Handbook on Beads*, Liberty Capital Books, York, Pennsylvania.
- Weisshaar, H. j, Roth and W. H. Wejeyapala. (2000). *Ancient Ruhuna, Beads from Ancient Sri Lanka First results of a Systematic material Analysis*, Weisshar HJ. Roth.H. Wijepala.W (ed).